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**Enhanced Ransomware
Detection and Response Using
Programmable Data
Infrastructure**

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Abstract

This paper presents the design and implementation of a managed detection and response (MDR) system for ransomware threats targeting relational databases. The solution is built on top of Delphix, leveraging its capabilities as a Programmable Data Infrastructure to enable a fast, flexible, and fully automated control process.

The development is based on the client's existing infrastructure, where highly confidential database records are replicated across multiple testing environments within a CI/CD pipeline. These environments reside in a less isolated network segment, accessible by heterogeneous identities by design, introducing inherent security risks.

The paper begins with a background and motivation section, outlining key concepts necessary to understand the solution and its alignment with business requirements. The discussion is risk-driven, starting with critical vulnerabilities and documented attack kill chains in CI/CD pipelines, followed by security constraints in complex cloud environments, and culminating in an analysis of the most pervasive and damaging threat, the *ransomware*.

Next, the project chapter details the state-of-the-art solution, covering the final infrastructure design, control logic, data flows, and critical software components. The execution workflow of these components is explored through code snippets, highlighting key design and implementation choices that establish the solution as a flexible framework for enforcing various security controls across heterogeneous environments.

Introduction

The era of digital transformation, from an enterprises operations outlook, forced enterprises to increasingly adopt modern IT paradigms such as DevOps, DataOps, and Hybrid Multi-Cloud infrastructures to enhance agility, scalability, and efficiency. However, these advancements introduce new security challenges, particularly in software development, data protection, and cloud security. One of the outcomes of such paradigms adoption is the widespread of Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines. Their rise has revolutionized software delivery, yet it has also emerged as a prime target for cyber threats. Attack vectors such as supply chain attacks, pipeline poisoning, and insufficient artifact integrity verification pose significant risks, as highlighted by cybersecurity frameworks like OWASP and MITRE ATT&CK. Furthermore, as businesses rely on hybrid and multi-cloud infrastructures, they face increased complexities in ensuring regulatory compliance, data governance, and system resilience. Adhering to stringent data protection regulations such as GDPR and HIPAA requires robust strategies to secure data across heterogeneous environments.

The paper cover in depth the threat targeted by the solution - Ransomware. The ransomware threats target landscape is wide and scattered across multiple nations and sectors, this is just one of the main reasons, along with the missing reporting of incidents, why ransomware data articles from leading research organizations report similar but not identical results. Nevertheless, the trend is evident: ransomware has become the predominant monetization strategy employed by attackers. Its prevalence continues to increase annually, along with its associated financial impact.

Particularly, the client's system, which integrates production data in testing environments, through Delphix engines, further expands the attack surface. Designing systems to provision masked data directly from production data repositories to testing environments is actually a common pattern to assure the quality of testing, and in some cases, the data is not even masked. This continuous integration between production and multiple testing environments across different segments of the perimeter can be leveraged to in-

ject malicious payloads in production environments, hosting mission-critical databases. Since, testing environments, by design, are often exposed to various threats and cannot always be secured further without negatively impacting efficiency and quality.

To address these challenges, organizations are increasingly leveraging Programmable Data Infrastructure (PDI) and DataOps methodologies to streamline data provisioning, ensure data fidelity, and enhance security measures. Delphix, a leading DevOps data platform, plays a crucial role in mitigating these risks by providing automated data masking, virtualization, and compliance capabilities. Its Continuous Data Engine and Continuous Compliance Engine enable enterprises to manage sensitive data securely while maintaining agility in software development and deployment processes.

The second part of this paper illustrates a real-world implementation of a solution that seek to mitigate ransomware risks employing the illustrated technologies in the client infrastructure. The Enterprise Recovery Vault (ERV) solution was designed to ensure data integrity simultaneously to an existing CI/CD-driven software development environment. By integrating Delphix engines, custom masking algorithm and an orchestration appliance, the ERV project aims to mitigate ransomware threats in relational databases, satisfying all requirements outlined in the ransomware chapter, including control robustness, speed and frequency. While establishing an automated back-up workflow, which continuously update back-up repository(Vault) with clean copies of data with an high frequency, ensuring few to none discrepancies to production. Therefore the system seek to guarantee an high degree of operational resiliency, ensuring continuous data integrity verification and minimal recovery time and data loss in the event of an incident.

The following sections provide an in-depth analysis of the background concepts, including DevOps security, hybrid multi-cloud challenges, DataOps principles, and ransomware threats. Subsequently, the ERV project is presented, detailing its architecture, data integrity control mechanism, Delphix engine integration, and custom security measures. By bridging state-of-the-art security methodologies with a real-world enterprise implementation, this paper contributes to the ongoing discourse on securing modern IT environments.

Chapter 1

Background & Motivation

1.1 DevOps

In recent years, many companies have faced an unrelenting demand for digital transformation. It has become imperative to leverage the new opportunities offered by technological advancements to remain competitive. The majority of corporate technology domains have shifted their primary focus to emphasize digital transformation initiatives as a means of survival in this rapidly evolving landscape. These transformations have driven organizations to reshape their core structure across three fundamental dimensions, simultaneously:

Modernization of Technologies: Modernization of technologies has been crucial to reducing costs and increasing the efficiency of development processes. Modernization refers to transitioning from legacy systems, such as mainframe-based systems with high resource demands and fully managed by the owner, to cloud computing services.

There are three main cloud computing models, each varying in the degree of configuration and resource management offered to the client, as summarised in Figure 1.1:

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS): In an IaaS model, the service provider offers computing, storage, and network resources, giving the client the flexibility to deploy and run applications, including operating systems and third-party software.

Platform as a Service (PaaS): In a PaaS model, the cloud infrastructure provided by the service provider includes the resources of IaaS, along with a pre-configured operating system. The client

can install third-party applications compatible with the system provided within the infrastructure.

Software as a Service (SaaS): In a SaaS model, the service provider grants access to proprietary applications through specific client applications such as web browsers or mobile apps. The client cannot modify the cloud infrastructure, except for minimal customizations made by the service provider for that client.

Figure 1.1: Cloud computing models [15]

In recent years, these models have continued to evolve in various ways, most notably through the adoption of Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) in the context of web applications. CDNs enable greater resource distribution, allowing personalized delivery based on the client's location.

Common examples of IaaS include AWS EC2, Microsoft Azure VM, and Google Cloud Platform (GCP). These serve as foundations for the corresponding PaaS offerings. Other popular PaaS platforms include Heroku, IBM Cloud, and Salesforce.

Resources Migration: Strongly tied to the modernization of technologies,

as technologies like IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS are cloud-based, organizations have had to migrate their resources from their traditional infrastructure to cloud services, both for storage and computing, utilizing different architectures. Adopting a cloud-based approach is a complex process that demands a range of technical skills. It is crucial to ensure proper orchestration and integration of services and fully leverage their capabilities. To ensure maximum synergy with the cloud service, it is essential to evaluate which type of architecture to adopt: private cloud, public cloud, hybrid, or pure SaaS.

Software Microtization: *Microtization* refers to the process of breaking down traditional monolithic applications, which are self-contained and lack flexibility, interoperability, fault tolerance, and scalability, into smaller, independent components called microservices. These microservices typically communicate with each other through APIs, using lightweight protocols such as LDAP. This architectural choice is often referred to as a microservices architecture. It is characterized by weak dependencies between components, service separation, and high granularity. This approach brings several benefits, including ease of scalability and understanding, greater flexibility, faster release cycles, and resilience to architectural changes. One of the main advantages of this microservices architecture is its high synergy with DevOps practices, which are aimed at optimizing and shortening the software development lifecycle, ensuring an efficient and stable product. The implementation of DevOps practices in development processes involves key approaches such as Continuous Delivery & Deployment (CD) and Continuous Integration (CI).

Continuous Transformation

Figure 1.2: Organization transformation over different macro aspects [5]

However, the implementation of DevOps practices, typically embodied in CI/CD pipelines, is crucial today to enable organizations to meet the relentless demand for new digital features or updates to existing ones in response to technological or natural changes, within unprecedented timeframes. As a result, many organizations have shifted their architectural choices towards systems organized into micro, self-contained, and independent units that can be developed, tested, and released individually by smaller, dedicated teams, as opposed to larger teams in traditional development settings. Each team, however, adheres to shared guidelines and is typically supervised by a designated figure.

Figure 1.3: Microservice tailored release workflow [17]

DevOps is a term widely used in the software development industry to refer to a set of practices, tools, and a cultural framework aimed at integrating software development teams (Dev) and IT operations teams (Ops) to automate and continuously enhance the processes of application development, testing, and deployment. The primary goal of DevOps is to accelerate the software development lifecycle while improving product quality and reducing

release times.

Figure 1.4: DevSecOps paradigm diagram [18]

With the rise of automation practices, industry experts have identified a gap in the fundamental security properties of final artifacts, as traditional development processes often performed these checks directly within the development environment. This shortcoming led to the evolution of the DevOps culture through the integration of security controls, giving rise to the term DevSecOps, which emphasizes embedding security measures within the DevOps workflow.

According to the Global DevSecOps Report by GitLab, a widely adopted platform for implementing CI/CD pipelines, security remains the top investment priority for 5,000 DevOps professionals in 2024. To detect vulnerabilities earlier, apply patches more easily, and reduce costs, the DevSecOps culture stresses the importance of shifting security controls to the left in the development process. Key practices include:

Static Code Analysis (SCA): Conduct static analysis of code to identify known vulnerabilities, including cross-references with CVE (Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures) and CWE (Common Weakness Enumeration) catalogs.

Dependency Analysis: Automate the verification of third-party libraries for known vulnerabilities (referencing CVEs and CWEs), authenticity, and integrity (ensuring the presence and correctness of code signing).

Infrastructure as Code (IaC) Configurations: Validate cloud service provider configurations (e.g., Terraform templates).

Containerization and Virtualization Security: Perform integrity checks on Docker images or virtual machine templates.

Dynamic Code Analysis (DCA): Conduct dynamic tests on applications during runtime.

A robust DevSecOps culture also includes proactive activities such as threat modeling and continuous monitoring to ensure application security during runtime:

Threat Modeling: Holistic analysis of potential threats to the system, conducted during system design and significant updates introducing new functionality. It serves as the primary source of information for subsequent security controls and monitoring activities.

Definition of Security Policies: Establish security standards, such as acceptable risk levels, access control policies, and secret management practices.

Monitoring, Alerts, and Response Systems: Once in production, applications must be continuously monitored to detect anomalies, triggering alerts and responses as needed. These capabilities can be implemented through systems like SIEM (Security Information and Event Management), IDR (Intrusion Detection and Response), XDR (Extended Detection and Response), and SOAR (Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response).

The implementation of DevOps practices has evolved into a comprehensive culture within organizations, making the entire IT stack automated and API-driven. State-of-the-art DevOps processes provide dedicated tools for automating and managing every phase of the development lifecycle and all components of the stack.

Figure 1.5: DevSecOps tools periodic table [1]

To correctly understand a CI/CD pipeline, it is essential to have a clear understanding of the context in which it operates: the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC). Within the SDLC lies the software release pipeline, a sequence of dependent stages through which code, packages, or artifacts flow from the developer’s environment to a production server.

The primary stages that define all release pipelines, through which code must pass, are:

Check-in: the updated version of the code is submitted to a version control system, where it is stored in a shared repository.

Test: execution of static code tests.

Build: compilation and preparation for deployment.

Deploy: deployment to a staging environment, and subsequently to production upon passing dynamic tests.

Most of the actions involved in these stages are manual and often repetitive. Progression through these stages typically relies on human feedback. However, a fundamental characteristic of software is efficiency, which engineers have strived to bring to the development process itself by automating these labor-intensive actions. This transformation has led to the emergence of two primary processes that together form a CI/CD pipeline:

Continuous Integration (CI): This refers to the automated process of integrating code changes into the main branch of a shared source repository. The CI pipeline is triggered by a push to the shared repository, which may occur in a branch other than the main one. After static

code analysis tests are performed (to check for vulnerabilities, inefficient syntax, or style compliance), the changes are merged into the main branch. The code is then compiled, and an executable is built along with all dependencies. Automated tests of various granularities are subsequently executed to identify functional errors introduced by the changes: unit tests verify individual software components (e.g., classes, methods); integration tests assess interactions between different modules; end-to-end tests simulate user behaviour to ensure the application functions as intended. If these tests are successful, packages or containers encapsulating the application are created, making it ready for deployment. The artifacts produced are stored in dedicated repositories for future use or distribution.

Continuous Delivery/Deployment (CD): This involves the automated distribution of artifacts to staging environments (Delivery), such as testing, development, or QA. If checks in these environments are successful, the artifacts are released to production (Deployment).

These processes together form the backbone of modern software development workflows, ensuring faster, more reliable delivery of high-quality applications.

Figure 1.6: Example CI/CD pipeline [2]

According to a Harvard Business School survey conducted across 654 enterprise-scale organizations, 77% have implemented CI/CD pipelines in their software release processes. However, only 10% consider themselves capable of releasing software quickly or having fully automated pipelines. These findings align with a RedGate survey of 3,200 medium-to-large organizations, where 74% reported adopting DevOps practices in some form, yet most remain far from achieving significant efficiency improvements.

The leading benchmark for assessing the state of DevOps adoption, Google's DORA (DevOps Research & Assessment) report, categorizes organizations into four performance groups based on their software release processes. These are evaluated using the following four key metrics:

- Mean Change Lead Time (MCLT): The average time it takes to implement a code change.
- Deployment Frequency: The rate at which software is released.
- Defective Version Rate: The frequency of defective releases impacting end users in production.
- Mean Time to Recovery (MTTR): The average time required to recover from a failed release.

Performance level	Change lead time	Deployment frequency	Change fail rate	Failed deployment recovery time	Percentage of respondents*
Elite	Less than one day	On demand (multiple deploys per day)	5%	Less than one hour	19% (18-20%)
High	Between one day and one week	Between once per day and once per week	20%	Less than one day	22% (21-23%)
Medium	Between one week and one month	Between once per week and once per month	10%	Less than one day	35% (33-36%)
Low	Between one month and six months	Between once per month and once every six months	40%	Between one week and one month	25% (23-26%)

Figure 1.7: Outcomes Global DevSecOps survey [12]

Capital One serves as a prime example of successful software release process transformation, achieving Elite-level performance according to DORA metrics.

As a digital bank with over 70 million customer accounts and 49,000 employees worldwide, Capital One adopted a DevOps strategy to address challenges like inconsistent releases, multiple handoff points, and time-consuming manual errors in development. The company implemented a fully automated CI/CD pipeline, migrated its monolithic applications to a microservices architecture to enhance flexibility and scalability, and completely overhauled its infrastructure by transitioning to the public cloud to eliminate the burden of managing on-premises infrastructure.

The outcomes of this transformation are remarkable. A relatively small DevOps team supports a community of nearly 7,000 engineers, managing a platform that handles over 500,000 automated Jenkins pipelines daily, more than 50,000 build, test, and deployment tasks per day. The adoption of DevOps practices allowed Capital One to reduce time-to-market by 75%, cut their mean change lead time from 6 weeks to 10 minutes, substantially increase deployment frequency, with some teams releasing code up to 50 times a day, this success highlights the transformative potential of DevOps practices when strategically implemented across an organization.

1.1.1 Microservices : DevOps tailored architecture

The implementation of a Continuous Deployment (CD) approach faces several challenges closely tied to software architecture. Many failed implementation attempts are due to overly traditional principles. A traditional monolithic architecture is characterized by:

Single Codebase: Functional logic, user interface, and persistent data are tightly interconnected, meaning they are developed and released together. This makes it difficult to scale individual components without impacting the entire codebase.

Unified Technology Stack: The entire application stack is often built using a single technology. Applications tied to one technology cannot easily adapt diverse modules to specific tasks.

These characteristics lead to a deployability level, in terms of system downtime, that is unacceptable for the frequency of releases required by a CD approach, along with a lack of flexibility. While flexibility is already a fundamental requirement in any application, the level typically achieved with monolithic architectures is insufficient for CD. Flexibility is a critical factor

that determines release speed. To ensure good flexibility, the software must exhibit modularity, extensibility, and interoperability. Additionally, in an application with tightly coupled components, achieving high test coverage during CI and ensuring reliable unit tests is challenging. These aspects are priorities in a microservices architecture.[3]

An application with a traditional monolithic architecture must undergo a transformation to excel in a CD process. This transformation will inevitably disrupt the original design in favor of a microservices-based paradigm, which offers:

Independent deployment: Changes to individual services can be deployed to production or designated environments regardless of the state of other services. This contrasts with monolithic architectures where: "When one team made a change, that team was unable to release it independently. Instead, they first needed to merge the change into the master branch. To avoid chaos caused by multiple simultaneous merges, they often needed to queue the merge. The merge could involve conflicts, requiring coordination with other teams. After merging, the entire application needed to be re-tested to identify any new errors."

Shorter release times: Releasing a single service requires significantly less testing effort compared to the entire application. With a dedicated pipeline for each service, workload is distributed, and release times are drastically reduced, unlike a single pipeline for the entire application, which required comprehensive testing.

Simplified deployment procedures: Closely tied to the ability to create a unified toolchain for all pipelines.

Faster incremental changes: "For most small incremental functional changes, we have reduced the cycle time from multiple months to two to five days." Fewer people are involved in decision-making for changes, and communication pathways from the end user to the assigned engineer are shorter.

Easier technology changes: "After we moved a system to microservices, each team can upgrade independently because each service no longer shares the same codebase, compilation process, and language runtime (e.g., Java Virtual Machine) with other parts of the system. This independence accelerates the adoption of new features in updated libraries or language versions, enabling us to deliver enhancements to customers faster than competitors." In addition, language and library developers are also adopting CD, increasing the speed at which they release

new versions. This trend underscores the importance of simplifying upgrades for languages and libraries in microservices-based applications.

1.1.2 CI/CD Security

As with the entire landscape of cyber attacks, attacks on software supply chains and CI/CD pipelines are growing rapidly, as reported by organizations such as the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) and StepSecurity. This is not surprising given the critical role a CI/CD pipeline plays in the SDLC, the flow of intellectual property it processes, and the sensitive data stored by the tools supporting the pipeline.

SolarWinds Supply Chain Hack

It is therefore not surprising that the hack of the supply chain of one of SolarWinds' products, a company that provides monitoring and management solutions for systems, networks, and infrastructures, is considered one of the most significant in terms of the magnitude of its impact. The Orion hack was a compromise of its code signing and build process. Essentially, the attackers were able to first gain access to the CI/CD pipeline, then modify the behavior of the msbuild.exe compiler to allow, after auditing the source code (to verify the legitimacy of the code and detect tampering), the insertion of a malicious payload into the source code before it was compiled. The attackers then modified the legitimate and digitally signed SolarWinds.Orion.Core.BusinessLayer.dll file. This .dll file acted as a plugin for Orion, opened by the SolarWinds process SolarWinds.BusinessLayerHost(x64).exe when Orion ran. The tampered .dll file, added to the legitimate HotFix #5 package for SolarWinds Orion (CORE-2019.4.5220.20574-SolarWinds-Core-v2019.4.5220-Hotfix5.msp), was a trojanized technique in the software supply chain attack.

The attack technique can be traced to a Command and Control (C2) approach. The trojan contained an obfuscated backdoor that allowed the attackers to access the infected environments completely invisibly to the victim's intrusion detection systems, as the HTTP traffic between the backdoor and the attackers was disguised as legitimate Orion performance data (Orion Improvement Program (OIP) protocol). The backdoor also employed evasion tactics such as remaining dormant for two weeks after installation and disabling all antivirus and forensic applications by exploiting the elevated privileges required by Orion to function properly.

Orion was a widely used tool by various organizations worldwide, primarily in the U.S., which SolarWinds itself estimated to be about 275,000, including more than 425 Fortune 500 organizations, all 10 major U.S. telecommunications companies, all five branches of the U.S. military, and five U.S. govern-

Figure 1.8: Attack process overview [19]

ment agencies. Once released into production, it was estimated that around 18,000 organizations installed one of the updates released between March and June 2020, and around 100 organizations were actually compromised. This estimate was made by FireEye (a company providing network and system security solutions and consulting) following the analysis of systems from potential malware victims. FireEye itself was one of the compromised companies and the first to detect the intrusion into their systems.

The actual malicious activities performed by the malware on the victim systems began with data exfiltration, allowing the attackers to identify the victim and, if they were a potential target, assign a C2 domain to the backdoor to manage the attack individually or otherwise completely disable the malware. Once a unique C2 domain was assigned to the victim, the attackers proceeded with manual activities to expand within the victim's perimeter, establish persistence, and exfiltrate additional confidential information. They then carried out what is called RainDrop and TearDrop, an attack methodology aimed at installing a well-known penetration testing application on the victim's system to detect further vulnerabilities in the infrastructure, Cobalt Strike Beacon, in order to find more dangerous ways to exploit the victims. Considering the limited metadata available, it is difficult to outline the attack's timeline precisely. It is still unclear how the attackers were able to access SolarWinds' CI/CD pipeline. However, the biggest question left behind by this attack is its impact. Given how sophisticated it was, the extent of the victims, and its duration, it is almost impossible to trace the potential

information exfiltrated and determine the full scope of this attack. Three years later, it is believed that this attack was the root cause of several APTs (Advanced Persistent Threats) that followed in the subsequent years worldwide.

1.1.3 CI/CD Threats

According to OWASP [23], potential risks that can impact a CI/CD pipeline include:

Insufficient Flow Control Mechanism: Insufficient flow control refers to the ability of an attacker, who has obtained highly privileged permissions in the system running a CI/CD process, to upload malicious code or artifacts into the source control management (SCM) and trigger the pipeline due to the lack of a mechanism enforcing additional approval and review checks. At least theoretically, a CI/CD flow is designed for full automation, allowing artifacts to reach production environments with minimal human intervention. It is essential to enforce targeted controls to ensure that unauthorized entities cannot arbitrarily upload code, and these controls must be stringent. Otherwise, an attacker who has bypassed identity and access controls in the SCM, CI systems, or any systems in the CD or monitoring components could exploit this. The closer the compromised node is to the end of the pipeline, the more likely it is that the malicious artifact will reach production environments, as compliance and security checks are typically performed at earlier nodes. Although nodes at the end of the pipeline do not natively support artifact uploads, complex manipulation could result in indirect uploads through provided functions. Final nodes typically include artifact storage repositories (e.g., JFrog, integrated repositories in providers like Azure, AWS, Google), performance evaluation systems (e.g., Apache JMeter, Gatling, k6), or deployment orchestration systems for staging environments (e.g., Ansible, Kubernetes, Chef, Puppet), as well as parallel pipeline monitoring systems (e.g., ELK stack, Splunk). In fact, such attacks often involve injecting malicious code through the initial SCM system, such as GitLab, GitHub, or Bitbucket, which serve as the root repositories for application code and configuration files. These systems are all based on Git, a widely used utility in software development that enables version tracking, rollback to previous versions, conflict-free collaboration among developers, isolated development environments for functional integration, and granular change history for debugging and compliance. These systems are essentially

Git interface platforms, which may seem trivial but in DevOps contexts expose essential functionalities for seamless CI/CD integration, including fully managed, pre-configured, auto-scalable CI/CD pipelines with predefined tools, requiring minimal configuration of job triggers, identity and access management policies, secret management policies, and optionally additional controls. That said, it is crucial to clarify that one of the highly recommended practices in CI/CD processes, widely adopted, is the manual review of the final artifact before release to production, at least for sensitive application components. However, despite meticulous manual reviews, attackers often employ obfuscation techniques that make malicious attributes difficult to detect even for human experts. These techniques are beyond the scope of this thesis. Speaking of attack techniques that can be linked to this threat, we have:

- Pushing code to a repository branch that is automatically deployed through the CI/CD pipeline to production.
- Pushing code to a repository branch and then manually triggering a pipeline that deploys the code to production.
- Directly pushing code to a third-party library used by code running in a production system.
- Exploiting an auto-merge rule in the continuous integration (CI) system that automatically merges pull requests meeting predefined criteria, thereby pushing unreviewed malicious code.
- Exploiting insufficient branch protection rules—for example, excluding specific users or branches to bypass protections and push unreviewed malicious code.
- Uploading an artifact to an artifact repository, such as a package or container, embedded as a legitimate artifact generated by the build environment. In this scenario, the absence of controls or checks could allow the deployment pipeline to acquire and deploy the artifact to production.
- Directly accessing the production environment and modifying application code or infrastructure (e.g., AWS Lambda function) without further approval or verification.

Mitigating this type of threat involves implementing the following measures:

- **Configuring branch protection rules:** Apply branch protection rules to branches hosting code used in production or other sensitive systems. Avoid, where possible, excluding user accounts or branches from branch protection rules. If user accounts are granted permission to push unreviewed code to a repository, ensure these accounts cannot trigger deployment pipelines linked to that repository.
- **Limiting the use of auto-merge rules:** Minimize scenarios where auto-merge rules are used. Carefully review the code of all auto-merge rules to ensure they cannot be bypassed. Avoid importing third-party code into the auto-merge process.
- **Preventing unauthorized activation of production nodes:** Where applicable, prevent accounts from triggering build and deployment pipelines in production without further approval or review.
- **Controlling artifact flow in the pipeline:** Allow artifacts to pass through the pipeline only if created by a pre-approved CI service account. Block artifacts uploaded by other accounts unless they undergo secondary review and approval.
- **Detecting and preventing inconsistencies:** Detect and correct discrepancies between code running in production and its CI/CD origin. Modify any resource containing deviations to align with expected standards.

Dependency Chain Abuse: Risks related to dependency chain abuse refer to an attacker's ability to exploit vulnerabilities in how development workstations and build environments retrieve code dependencies. This type of abuse can lead to the unintended retrieval and execution of a malicious package locally. Dependencies are often managed via dedicated clients for each programming language, using a combination of internally managed repositories, such as JFrog Artifactory, and language-specific SaaS repositories, such as npm for Node.js, PyPI for Python, and RubyGems for Ruby. When using dependencies, it is crucial to implement controls ensuring the security of the dependency ecosystem, including securing the dependency retrieval process and additional analyses like SCA and DCA once dependencies are integrated into the code. Inadequate configurations can lead to an engineer or, worse, a build system downloading a malicious package instead of the intended one, resulting in its immediate execution via pre-installation scripts configured in the pipeline.

The main attack vectors for this threat include:

- Dependency confusion: Publishing malicious packages in public repositories with the same name as private packages.
- Dependency hijacking: An attacker gaining control of a maintainer's account to upload malicious versions of widely used packages.
- Typosquatting: Creating packages with names similar to popular ones to induce typos.
- Brandjacking: Creating malicious packages using naming conventions associated with trusted brands to deceive developers.

Through these techniques, malicious code is executed in a pipeline node that downloaded it, typically resulting in credential theft or lateral movement via Command and Control (C2) attack methods. In some cases, the malicious code can reach production environments, also exploiting the previously mentioned threat of insufficient flow control mechanisms. Once in production, this type of malware, known as Trojans, can potentially have devastating impacts, constituting advanced persistent threats that disrupt business continuity or, in the worst cases, necessitate complete reconstruction of enterprise infrastructure.

Mitigation measures are numerous and depend on the specific configuration of dependency management clients for different languages, primarily regarding the use of internal proxies and external repositories. That said, all guidelines share common principles:

- Where possible, always use local or internal repositories containing pre-verified packages, such as centralized repositories provided by major cloud computing providers (e.g., GitLab Package Registry, Azure Artifacts, AWS CodeArtifact). If it is not possible to use only local repositories and third-party packages must be downloaded from external, mostly public repositories, it is good practice to configure an internal proxy (reverse proxy) between the machine hosting the final source code and the internet, to implement additional compliance checks and caching mechanisms on the proxy server. Applications like Nginx or Squid Proxy are widely used as reverse proxy engines.
- Implement additional package verification, such as checksum comparison and signature verification with official packages to ensure package integrity. With npm, use `npm audit` and `npm --verify-signatures`; with pip, use `pip install --require-hashes`; and with Maven, use the `maven-gpg-plugin`.

- Enforce the installation of specific stable and secure versions instead of the latest version, using techniques provided by the framework or directives, such as specifying dependency versions in package-lock.json, requirements.txt, and pom.xml files for npm, pip, and Maven, respectively.
- Associate private packages with an organizational scope and configure clients to access them exclusively from the internal registry.

These practices are generally implementable via the dependency management clients by modifying their configuration files (e.g., .npmrc, pip.conf, or settings.xml for Maven). Alternatively, tools like Artifactory or Nexus Repository offer more specific functionalities to automate these practices, easy integration with standard tools like Snyk (SCA/DCA), and active monitoring.

Poisoned Pipeline Execution (PPE): The risk of manipulated pipeline execution refers to an attacker’s ability, with access to version control systems (SCM) but without access to build environments, to manipulate the build process by injecting malicious code/commands into the pipeline configuration, essentially “poisoning” the pipeline and causing the execution of malicious code as part of the build process. Users with permissions to modify CI (Continuous Integration) configuration files or other files on which the pipeline job depends can alter these files by inserting malicious commands, thereby compromising the CI pipeline execution. Pipelines executing unreviewed code, such as those triggered directly by pull requests or commits to arbitrary repository branches, are more susceptible to PPE. This is because such scenarios inherently include code that has not undergone any review or approval. In an ideal scenario, the CI configuration file resides in the same repository as the source code or in one of its branches, accessible via the version control system (SCM). If an attacker gains access to this repository, they could modify the CI configuration file, for example, by directly uploading the change to an unprotected branch or submitting a pull request (PR) with the change from a branch or fork. Since the CI pipeline execution is triggered by these “push” or “PR” events, and the execution is defined by the commands in the modified CI configuration file, the attacker’s malicious commands are inevitably executed in a build node when the pipeline is triggered. This threat is known as Direct Poisoned Pipeline Execution (D-PPE).

Commonly, however, the CI configuration file is not available in the repository or a branch accessible to the attacker. The pipeline might

be configured to retrieve the CI configuration file from a protected branch of the same repository. The file could be stored in a separate repository from the source code, with no direct modification capability for users. Alternatively, the CI build configuration might be defined directly within the CI system.

Even in these cases, an attacker could still poison the pipeline by injecting malicious code into files referenced by the pipeline configuration, inevitably leading to the execution of malicious commands in pipeline nodes, for example:

Makefile: Execution of commands defined in the “Makefile,” used to provide build instructions specific to the language.

Referenced scripts: Scripts directly invoked by the pipeline configuration file, stored in the same repository as the source code.

Code tests: Testing frameworks operating on application code during the build process rely on dedicated files stored in the same repository as the source code. Attackers who manipulate these files can execute malicious commands during the build.

Automated tools: Linters and security scanners used in CI often rely on configuration files in the repository. These configurations often involve loading and executing external code defined in the configuration file itself.

In both scenarios, it is assumed that the SCM is protected by authentication mechanisms forcing the attacker to impersonate an authorized entity to inject malicious code into the configuration. However, in some cases, CI pipeline poisoning is accessible even to anonymous attackers on the internet. Public repositories (e.g., open-source projects) often allow any user to contribute, typically via pull requests with suggested code changes. These projects are commonly tested and built automatically using CI solutions, similar to private projects. If the CI pipeline of a public repository executes unreviewed code suggested by anonymous users, this is known as a Public PPE attack or simply 3P.

This attack method typically leads to the exfiltration of sensitive information. Malicious code executed on one or more pipeline nodes assumes the same permissions as the dedicated user with whom the CI/CD server accesses resources, which are typically highly privileged. This allows access to credentials or other secrets stored in environment variables, for example, which nodes are rich in as they need to access various external assets like cloud environments, artifact registries, and the SCM. Alternatively, a common practice is to exfiltrate com-

mand history to extract still valid keys or codes; in Linux-based shell languages, this is achievable simply with the history command or by downloading the contents of specific files like `.bash_history`, `.zsh_history`, or `.dash_history`. This sensitive information is then exploited to perform lateral movement within the organization’s infrastructure.

Practices to prevent this type of threat primarily involve a remote repository or dedicated branch for the pipeline configuration file and all configuration files used throughout the pipeline, with protection rules. Where the triggered pipeline involves nodes with sensitive information, security checks on configuration files must be performed before execution, and manual approval should be sought if possible. Another highly recommended practice is ensuring the execution of pipeline steps in as isolated nodes as possible, meaning nodes not potentially exposed to secrets and sensitive environments. Secret management is a broad topic beyond the scope of this thesis; in general, in CI/CD contexts with multi-hybrid cloud infrastructures, centralized secret management with cloud-agnostic services and robust client-side encryption with ephemeral keys (single-use) is recommended.

Insufficient Pipeline-Based Access Controls (PBAC): Actions resulting from pipeline poisoning almost always involve lateral movement within the CI/CD infrastructure or the entire organization’s infrastructure, exploiting the permissions attributed to the pipeline job. The executor nodes (runners) of pipeline jobs (steps), i.e., the commands specified in the pipeline configuration, perform inherently sensitive activities already extensively mentioned earlier. PBAC includes access controls to numerous elements such as environment variables, sensitive files, other pipelines, other nodes, the virtual machine’s file system, and the hosting host, network filters to internal and external resources. They therefore concern the context in which each pipeline—and each individual job within it (step)—is executed. Given the highly sensitive and critical nature of each pipeline, it is essential to limit each pipeline to the exact set of data and resources necessary for its intended functionality. Ideally, each pipeline and step should be restricted in such a way that, in the event an adversary manages to execute malicious code in the pipeline’s context, the potential damage is minimized. The extent of potential damage caused by malicious code is strongly determined by the granularity and robustness of PBAC in the environment where it is executed. These controls favor role-based access control (RBAC) models. Roles are assigned based on access mechanisms fol-

lowing a challenge-and-response model, which can only be overcome if in possession of certain secret information. To prevent the exfiltration of these secrets by malicious code executing on pipeline nodes, during the pipeline design phase, it is good practice to adhere to fundamental principles such as:

- First and foremost, always ensure compliance with the principle of least privilege (“deny by default”): Jobs should assume only the permissions strictly necessary to provide their functionality; the more granular these permissions are, the less damaging their exploitation by an attacker. This principle must be applied to at least three areas: secrets for accessing third-party resources across the infrastructure, access to additional nodes in the pipeline, and the OS user account the job assumes. For example, if a pipeline job needs to access an AWS service to complete its function, the AWS credentials used in that pipeline should only be able to perform specific operations on the specific services and resources necessary for the service.
- Never share a node between pipelines with different sensitivities or, even more so, different natures. Moreover, never instantiate a built-in node on the host running the pipeline controller, as it is a highly sensitive environment.
- Isolation at both the network and application levels. Design the infrastructure to enable micro-segmentation of environments. Create separate contexts in which scripts are executed. Additionally, where possible, configure network firewall rules to block all communication to and from the internet by default, allowing traffic only through secure channels like mutual TLS (mTLS) to and from known static IP addresses; if access to remote resources via domain is necessary, configure a trusted fixed DNS server (e.g., 1.1.1.1 Cloudflare) or an internal one and encapsulate the connection always in a secure channel using protocols like DNSSEC and DNS over HTTPS (DoH) or DNS over TLS (DoT).

Regardless of how stringent and granular PBACs are, once the roles dedicated to pipeline jobs are assumed, completely blocking the exfiltration of secrets and thus lateral movement across the entire infrastructure in a node is nearly impossible. Therefore, security strategies have undergone a transformation shifting their focus from the perimeter to resources, implying the principle “never trust, always verify,” at the core of Zero-Trust Architecture (ZTA). Applying such an architecture

in an automated context like CI/CD involves significant complexities, as automation contrasts with robust security, in addition to adding significant delays. ZTA will be discussed later.

Insufficient Credential Hygiene: As mentioned multiple times in previous threats, one of the most sought-after pieces of information for an attacker is credentials stored in pipeline systems, to use for lateral movement. Often, the acquisition of such credentials is facilitated by flaws in secret and key management or access to the systems storing them. Given that CI/CD systems, consisting of components authenticating with multiple varied components, via multiple authentication methods using different credentials with associated storage techniques, are highly complex to secure in terms of credential hygiene. The most common hygiene flaws include:

- Accidentally or deliberately hardcoding plain or encrypted credentials in the source code. Typically, these are credentials used for authentication with SaaS APIs or databases. These credentials become immediately visible to anyone with read access to the repository. Even if removed later, they remain in the commit history.
- Similarly, for pipeline configuration files and tools used, if critical credentials are hardcoded in such files, they are exposed not only to unauthorized users but also to the scripts the pipeline executes.
- Container images can contain credentials necessary for building the container in their layers, making them available to anyone able to download the container.
- Printing credentials used in plaintext or encrypted in the output console, voluntarily or accidentally, remaining exposed in plaintext in logs, which are also centralized in a log management system, further expanding the exposure surface.
- Failure to rotate credentials, especially in CI/CD environments where multiple applications share the same credentials for pipeline and environment access.

Secure credential management involves:

- Continuous mapping and monitoring of credentials: Maintain a relational track of credential-resource-service to have a clear view of the credential ecosystem and whether some can be made even more granular (LPP). Use tools enabling continuous monitoring of

compliance with outlined policy conditions—e.g., AWS IAM Access Analyzer (Azure equivalent), IAM Policy Conditions (Azure equivalent).

- Dynamically generated and ephemeral credentials (OTP), frequent rotation of static credentials—e.g., Azure Managed Identity and Azure Key Vault.
- Preventing secret detection in code: Use specialized tools for data leak detection in repositories, both in source code, configuration directives, and containers. Apply continuous monitoring throughout the CI/CD—e.g., GitGuardian, Trivy. If necessary, declare secrets in pipeline configuration files using the appropriate mechanisms provided by platforms like GitHub Actions Secrets.

Insufficient Artifact Integrity Verification: This threat falls under the broader category of insufficient flow control in the pipeline and focuses on the validation checks performed on source code and artifacts uploaded to the pipeline. As previously mentioned, if a compromised resource infiltrates the delivery process without encountering security checks, it is highly likely to flow through the pipeline to the production environment, masquerading as a legitimate resource.

The presence of mechanisms to verify the integrity and legitimacy of artifacts is therefore of fundamental importance. It is considered best practice to configure multiple security gates along the pipeline, ideally after the most critical nodes—those that perform a high number of external actions or interact directly with the artifact. At these security gates, the following controls can be implemented:

- Source Code Management (SCM) Signing: SCM systems provide functionality for signing contributions with a unique key per contributor, allowing individual commits or container images to be signed using algorithms like GPG.
- Signature Verification: If the signatures of uploaded artifacts pass the initial check, the signature must be validated at all subsequent gates. Additionally, static code analysis tools like SonarQube can be used to scan for vulnerabilities in the code.
- Configuration File Checks: Similar controls must be applied to configuration files to detect discrepancies in resource management. It is of primary importance to ensure that Infrastructure as Code (IaC) templates are always signed with a predefined, authorized key.

Inadequate Identity and Access Management (IAM): Many of the threats listed above involve the prior compromise of authentication mechanisms for one or more systems, enabled by poor management of identities and access across various systems. Proper configuration can be challenging, especially in complex software delivery systems that involve multiple pipelines of different types (e.g., DevOps, DataOps, MLOps, SecOps), often interconnected, with each pipeline consisting of multiple sequential applications offering various access methods (e.g., username/password, personal tokens, SSO, SSH keys). These applications must grant access to users from diverse origins (internal, federated organizations, non-engineering departments, external collaborators, or other applications) and assign specific permissions with varying granularity. Ensuring best practices in identity lifecycle management—such as the Least Privilege Principle, Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA), account deprovisioning, and scheduled password resets—is critical to preventing account compromise or the creation of malicious accounts. The large attack surface, combined with the highly privileged permissions typically and inevitably assigned to these accounts, makes Identity and Access Management (IAM) a prime target for malicious entities. In fact, IAM is often the initial infection vector for reaching production environments through various means. It is important to clarify that this threat is not strictly tied to CI/CD systems but affects the entire IT sphere of an organization, with compromises often resulting from human error—research indicates that over 80% of incidents are caused by human mistakes.

To mitigate this risk, the following practices are essential:

- **Continuous Identity Analysis:** Perform ongoing analysis of identities within systems, mapping providers, granted and used permissions, and including all programmatic access methods. Remove unnecessary permissions and deactivate/remove inactive accounts according to a predefined schedule.
- **Federated Access (SSO):** Implement a centralized federated access system managed via an Identity Provider (IdP), avoiding locally managed accounts. Enforce security policies such as password constraints, MFA, lockout policies, and extend access control algorithms with parameters like IP, device, and geolocation. Limit external collaborators' permissions to the minimum necessary, with predefined expiration dates, and disable accounts once their work is complete.
- **Avoid Personal Emails and Non-Business Domains:** Prohibit the

use of personal emails or non-corporate domains for accessing critical systems. Do not allow self-registrations or grant default permissions to all users. Use dedicated accounts for each context, avoiding shared accounts, and assign permissions specific to their purpose.

Insufficient Logging and Visibility: Time and data are considered the most valuable resources for an organization under attack. Time is critical to limiting the extent of damage. In this regard, it is vital to have robust logging systems and detailed, comprehensive visibility across the entire CI/CD system. Furthermore, the information gathered is crucial for post-incident investigations to identify the techniques, tactics, and procedures (TTPs) used and to update security strategies to mitigate such scenarios in the future.

Given the sophisticated nature of attack vectors related to CI/CD systems, it is essential to give equal importance to both system audit logs (e.g., access, user creation, modifications) and application logs (e.g., commits, pushes, pulls, fetches, as in Prometheus). Additionally, centralizing logs from monitoring systems is necessary to enable proper integration with Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) tools. These tools automate the notification of events that could impact system security and are part of the broader context of Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response (SOAR) tools, enabling active mitigation measures such as disabling accounts, isolating network segments, deactivating resources, and activating backup and fast recovery systems.

Gaining an exhaustive view of the attack surface in CI/CD systems requires continuous effort, increasing with the number of pipelines and the complexity of each. Therefore, mapping the aforementioned threats to the MITRE ATT&CK framework and their corresponding mitigation measures to the MITRE D3FEND framework is highly effective for threat management. These mappings can be further extended with CVE and CWE catalogs for in-depth analysis, as well as threat intelligence activities to stay ahead of emerging threats.

The objectives of the attack and defense techniques outlined by MITRE can be summarized in the following figure.

Figure 1.9: overview CI/CD attack vectors mapped to ATT&CK techniques and D3FEND countermeasures [4]

Initial Access: Initial access involves establishing a foothold within the target network, utilizing various techniques. These techniques align with the previously discussed threats, such as insufficient flow control mechanisms, dependency chain abuse, and inadequate identity and access management

ATT&CK			D3FEND		
Tattica	Tecnica	Procedura	Mitigazione	Tecnica	Contromisura
Initial Access	Compromise Software Supply Chain [T1195.002]	CVE-2019-3396(CWE-22) : Server Side Template Injection through widget on Atlassian Confluence CVE-2011-0611(CWE-843) : Remote Code Execution through object type incompatibility on Adobe Flash Player(C++)	Vulnerability Scanning[M1016]	Automatic Static and Dynamic Code Analysis	Add multiple SCA steps in the pipeline, robust one after pull from the SCM Deploy artifact to test environment for DCA, ensure coverage of border scenarios
Initial Access	Compromise Software Dependencies and Development Tool [T1195.001]	CVE-2021-30713(CWE-20) : Local Code inclusion in Xcode MacOS IDE that lead to remote code execution in various hosts where projects were used - XCSSET backdoor	Limit Software Installation[M1033]	Executable Allowlisting[D3-EAL] Executable Denylisting[D3-EDL]	Enforce restriction to pull/clone/fetch code solely from internal repositories with pre-verified code Compare checksum and signature with official ones, keep updated trusted CA certificates
Initial Access	Valid Accounts[T1078]	Spear-phishing with strong social engineering, that lead to execution of malicious code. Mainly involves fingerprinting payload	Account Use Policies[M1036]	Authentication Cache Invalidation[D3-ANCI] Authentication Event Thresholding[D3-ANET]	Context-aware access control: activity baseline created with authentication event. Manual(static) or statistical analysis based(dynamic) threshold definition. Reduce session caching window, both of credentials and connections

Figure 1.10: Initial Access ATT&CK TTPs and D3FEND countermeasures

Execution: Execution refers to techniques that lead to the execution of adversary-controlled code on a target system (blue space). A Malicious Cyber Actor (MCA) can exploit CI/CD systems in the cloud

using the following MITRE ATT&CK TTPs, and MITRE enumerated the corresponding countermeasures in D3FEND

ATT&CK			D3FEND		
Tattica	Tecnica	Procedura	Mitigazione	Tecnica	Contromisura
Execution	Container Administration Command [T1609]	CVE-2019-5736(CWE-78) : OS command injection through low-level binary runc underlying Docker, cri-o, containerd, Kubernetes	Execution Prevention[M1038]	System Call Filtering[D3-SCF] Application Configuration Hardening[D3-ACH]	Use lightweight read-only images and read-only filesystem. Use application control and software restriction tools to restrict access to files, processes, and system calls in containers.[8]
Execution	Command and Scripting Interpreter[T1059]	CVE-2017-0199 : remote code execution via RTF and XLSM files in some windows version via HTA handler vulnerability	Execution Prevention[M1038]	Process Segment Execution Prevention[D3-PSEP] Application Configuration Hardening[D3-ACH]	Detect faulty entry point, preventing execution of any segment besides text segment(code). Force application restriction, like PowerShell Constrained Language mode can be used to restrict access to dangerous language elements such as those used to execute arbitrary Windows APIs

Figure 1.11: Execution ATT&CK TTPs and D3FEND countermeasures

Persistence: Persistence involves techniques adversaries use to maintain long-term access to systems, even after reboots, credential changes, or other disruptions that might otherwise terminate their access

ATT&CK			D3FEND		
Tactic	Technique	Procedure	Mitigation	Technique	Countermeasure
Persistence	Additional Cloud Credentials[T1098.001]	CVE-2020-10148(CWE-287) : Orion SolarWind API authentication bypass enabling X509 keys and passwords addition	Multi-factor Authentication[M1032]	Multi-factor Authentication[D3-MFA]	Force presentation of two or more credentials, something you know, something you have and/or something you are
Persistence	Add SSH Authorized keys[T1098.004]	Edit of ssh control configuration files, authorized_keys with trusted public ssh keys and sshd_config to allow authentication with public key and RSA	Restrict File and Directive Permissions[M1022]	Local File Permissions[D3-LFP]	Restrict access to files. Create sensitive files with a purposefully crafted user and ensure they can only be written by him setting permission bits to 600, 400 or even 000 for fixed content.
Persistence	Event Triggered Execution[T1546]	AWS exposes lambda functions, custom action triggered by declared events. Creation of Lambda function that reacts on user creation and post his disaster recovery key to an arbitrary location	Account Management[M1018]	System Configuration Permissions[D3-SCP]	Ensure Least Privilege Principle at account level. Do not grant permission to low privilege users to edit its and others account configuration

Figure 1.12: Persistence ATT&CK TTPs and D3FEND countermeasures

Privilege Escalation: Privilege escalation consists of techniques adversaries use to gain higher-level permissions on a system or network. While adversaries often begin with limited access, they require elevated privileges to achieve their objectives

ATT&CK			D3FEND		
Tactic	Technique	Procedure	Mitigation	Technique	Countermeasure
Privilege Escalation	Cloud Accounts[T1078.004]	Cloud accounts are typically federated with Identity management systems, hence they grant access to multiple segments of a perimeter. ROADRecon provides a framework to pen test Azure AD API	Active Directory Configuration[M1015]	User Account Permissions[D3-UAP] Multi-factor Authentication[D3-MFA]	Restrict access method to credentials with MFA, and ensure LPP is guaranteed at account level

Figure 1.13: Privilege Escalation ATT&CK TTPs and D3FEND countermeasures

Defense Evasion: Defense evasion encompasses techniques adversaries use to avoid detection during the compromise process. These techniques include uninstalling or disabling security software, obfuscating or encrypting data and scripts, exploiting trusted processes to mask malicious code.

ATT&CK			D3FEND		
Tactic	Technique	Procedure	Mitigation	Technique	Countermeasure
Defence Evasion	Exploitation for Defense Evasion[T1211]	CVE-2021-3849(CWE-787) : Through the Sophos XG firewall arbitrary code execution was performed exploiting the eBPF vulnerability to not check for writes smaller than buffer size[9]	Application Isolation and Sandboxing[M1048]	Dynamic Analysis[D3-DA]	Executing or opening a file in a synthetic "sandbox" environment(container, virtual machine, simulator) to analyze the natural behaviour of the code without requiring the code to be disassembled.
Defence Evasion	Impair Defences[T1562]	Windows offers the set-mp-preferences utility to configure windows defender behaviour. MCA can impair wvd disabling behaviour and real-time monitoring and excluding arbitrary paths from control[10]	Audit[M1047]	System File Analysis[D3-SFA]	Monitoring system files such as authentication databases, configuration files, system logs, and system executables for modification or tampering.
Defence Evasion	Deploy Container[T1610]	Containerized applications can be purposefully built from images created on the host, being isolated they can evade weak audit checks	Audit[M1047]	Static Code Analysis	Scan images before deployment. In Kubernetes environments, the admission controller can be used to validate images after a container deployment request is authenticated but before the container is deployed[11]

Figure 1.14: Defence Evasion ATT&CK TTPs and D3FEND countermeasures

Credential Access: Credential access involves techniques for stealing credentials, such as keys and passwords, which enable adversaries to perform lateral movement. The adoption of cloud infrastructures has made credential access a highly prevalent tactic among adversaries.

ATT&CK			D3FEND		
Tattica	Tecnica	Procedura	Mitigazione	Tecnica	Contromisura
Credential Access	Forge SAML Tokens[T1606/002.C56]	In the context of federated cloud system, an adversary with access to token-signing private key and public key certificate of the IdP can forge arbitrary SAMLResponse and compromise users across all system environments[12]	Active Directory Configuration[M1015]	Application Configuration Hardening[D3-ACH]	Rotate the token-signing AD FS certificate in rapid succession twice, which will invalidate any tokens generated using the previous certificate
Credential Access	Unsecured private keys[T1552.004]	Besides looking for typical keys file extensions and in common key directories of device communication protocols(ssh), also device and transport keys used in federated systems could be exported if the device is compromised[14]	Encrypt Sensitive Information[M1041]	Disk Encryption[D3-DENCR]	Store keys on separate cryptographic hardware instead of the local system. Windows offers TPM to secure keys and other sensitive credential material.[15]

Figure 1.15: Credential Access ATT&CK TTPs and D3FEND countermeasures

Lateral Movement: Lateral movement refers to techniques adversaries use to exploit and control additional remote systems on a network, starting from an already compromised system. Achieving their primary objectives often requires exploring the network to identify and access targets.

ATT&CK			D3FEND		
Tactic	Technique	Procedure	Mitigation	Technique	Countermeasure
Lateral Movement	Taint Shared Content[T1080]	Shared content can be tampered with malicious code triggered when any user in the network access it, therefore compromising its system. A widespread pivot of this technique is directly tampering links to shared directories in the sharing server.[16]	Exploit Protection[M1050]	Shadow Stack Comparisons[D3-SSC]	Comparing a call stack in system memory with a shadow call stack maintained by the processor to determine unauthorized shellcode activity.
Lateral Movement	SMB/Windows Admin Shares Exploit[T1021.002]	SMB can be exploited to interact with networked systems using remote procedure calls (RPCs), transfer files, and run transferred binaries through remote execution. A pivot of this technique is the access of administrator shares with NTLM password hashes.	Filter Network Traffic[M1037]	Network Traffic Filtering[D3-NTF]	Consider using the host firewall to restrict file sharing communications such as SMB
Lateral Movement	SSH Session Hijacking[T1563.001]	Active SSH sessions, especially with public key authentication and agent forwarding enabled, can be exploited by hijacking an existing connection to another system. This can involve the compromise of the SSH agent itself or by having access to the agent's socket.[17]	Disable or Remove Feature or Program[M1042]	Application Configuration Hardening[D3-ACH]	Ensure that agent forwarding is disabled on systems that do not explicitly require this feature to prevent misuse.

Figure 1.16: Lateral movement ATT&CK TTPs and D3FEND countermeasures

Exfiltration: Exfiltration involves techniques adversaries use to steal data from the network. Once collected, data is often packaged and encoded according to system standards to avoid detection during transfer to adversary-controlled systems

ATT&CK			D3FEND		
Tattica	Tecnica	Procedura	Mitigazione	Tecnica	Contromisura
Exfiltration	Automated Exfiltration: Traffic Duplication[T1020.001]	Traffic mirroring, such as to network analyzer, can be leveraged to duplicate traffic to attacker controlled host by editing maliciously host configuration[18]	Encrypt Sensitive Information[M1041]	Encrypted Tunnels[D3-ET]	Encrypted encapsulation of routable network traffic, forcing strong protocols such as mTLS
Exfiltration	Exfiltration Over C2 Channel[T1041]	Stolen data is commonly exfiltrated to the attacker over the command and control channel.	Behavior Prevention on Endpoint[M1040]	User Data Transfer Analysis[D3-UDTA]	Employ network traffic monitoring tools(SIEM) to detect suspicious data transfers by a user

Figure 1.17: Exfiltration ATT&CK TTPs and D3FEND countermeasures

It is important to specify that only a subset of mitigation tactics has been provided for illustrative purposes. Multiple mitigation strategies can be identified depending on the specific context. Additionally, both the MITRE ATT&CK and D3FEND frameworks are continuously evolving to address emerging threats and techniques.

1.2 Hybrid Multi-Cloud Infrastructure

Nowadays, cloud computing is a prominent paradigm for enabling new business models and economies to scale their applications based on automatic on-demand provisioning of IT resources (both hardware and software) over a network as metered services, where consumers are billed only for what they consume.

Cloud services providers offer a wide spectrum of services, all roughly share the same set of services and each offers an experience better tailored for specific use cases, furthermore several organizations are interested by heterogeneous workload requirements, increasingly restricting regulations and vendor lock-in boundaries. Therefore, especially when it comes to general purpose applications, a multi cloud approach is the best suited for performance, cost, flexibility and reliability enhancement. All widespread CSPs(Azure, AWS, GCP) are well-known for a different specialization: Azure for enterprise integration with the microsoft ecosystem, AWS for scalability and serverless infrastructure implementation and GCP for advanced data analytics, machine learning and container orchestration. These specializations can be leveraged simultaneously, in several synergic real-world use cases. The most common use case is a meticulously designed data analytics pipeline: GCP's BigQuery for real-time data processing, AWS's S3 for scalable data storage, and Azure Synapse Analytics for seamless integration with its Microsoft-powered enterprise applications.

Even though cloud computing come with massive benefits, a pure cloud based infrastructure presents some drawbacks that must not be overlooked in the design or migration phase. The foremost concern is a single data point of failure, full reliance to a single cloud provider for data retention, following a impairment can lead to the exfiltration of all the sensitive data and intellectual property, before being eventually encrypted or even worse, wiped. A partial remediation to this would be the replication of such sets of sensitive data across multiple locations or even providers with automated workflows, but this isn't always possible due to hosting country data retention policies. Similarly, an infrastructure with full cloud reliance comes with low fault-tolerance, an interruption of a core component of one provider can impact directly the business continuity, leaving the consumer with no choice than waiting for service recovery. Next, adhering to stringent regulatory requirements (e.g., GDPR, HIPAA) might result demanding with heterogeneous data and wide product distribution. Such challenges are just some of the peculiarities of cloud adoption, depending on the context several more can be identified. Hence, an infrastructure solution distinguished by multiple providers and distribution of resources between on-premises private and

public domains represents a compelling solution, also known as multi-hybrid cloud infrastructure. This model embodies adaptability, resilience and optimization as main features and allows consumers to navigate the complexities of always evolving digital ecosystem.

1.2.1 Cloud Security Challenges

Nevertheless, enterprises consider security as the #1 inhibitor to cloud adoptions (Fortinet 2024 Cloud Security Report). Especially SMEs are reluctant to the adoption of cloud computing due to the difficulty in evaluating the trade-off between cloud benefits and the additional security risks and privacy issues that may arise. Most concerns are related to data protection, regulations compliance and other issues related to the lack of know-how regarding controls and governance processes in the outsourcing of data and applications: data confidentiality, trust on aggregators, control over data and/or code location, and resource assignment in multi-tenancy. The most challenging applications in heterogeneous cloud ecosystems are those that are able to maximise the benefits of the combination of the cloud resources in use. Such applications have a Microservice architecture with components deployed across different resources and each interested by a single CI/CD pipeline, these are also known as multi-cloud applications. Hence, for the context of this paper, a multi-cloud application is conceived as a distributed application over heterogeneous cloud resources whose components are deployed in different cloud service providers and still they all work in an integrated way and transparently for the end-user. Multi-cloud application solutions have to deal with the security of the individual components as well as with the overall application security including the communications and the data flow between the components. Even if each of the cloud service providers offered its own security controls, the multi-cloud application has to ensure an integrated security across the whole composition. Therefore, the overall security depends on the security properties of the application components, which in turn depend on the security properties offered by the cloud resources they exploit. For instance, the database component in charge of storing sensitive data cannot ensure a high confidentiality if the cloud storage resource in which it is deployed does not use strong encryption algorithms. Consequently, the whole multi-cloud application may be not sufficiently safe. The threats landscape is wide and therefore cloud security is itself a broad term, though some major areas of concerns can be addressed in IAM, data at rest and in transit, ingress and egress traffic, architecture framework and threat management.

Federated IAM

Identity and Access Management is the beating heart of a strategy aimed to safeguard a cloud based infrastructure. Each cloud platform often has its own access control methods, user directories, and authentication protocols. This lack of native integration features and centralized control makes it difficult for organizations to enforce consistent security policies and ensure uniform access management across multiple clouds. It may lead to security flaws, ineffective access rights enforcement, and challenges in auditing and observing access events. Uniformed and centralized management is obtained with a federated paradigm, where all domains have multiple service providers whose access is granted with the domain Identity Provider, and a trust relationship is established between these different IdPs. A trust relationship involves establishing shared traffic layer protocol(mTLS), users data structures, authorization policies, authentication mechanism(OAuth, OIDC), and more details based on the context. A strong federated approach enables a seamless authentication and authorization to access resources across different domains, privacy and compliance with governments regulations. Federated access control relies on the concepts of single sign-on (SSO), security tokens, role-based access control(RBAC), attribute-based access control (ABAC), and the federated protocols like the security assertion markup language (SAML), OAuth, and OpenID Connect (OIDC) to provide its functionalities.

An hybrid multi cloud infrastructure is highly synergic with Data Loss Prevention strategies adoption. Data loss prevention (DLP) is a strategy to ensure that sensitive or confidential data are not lost, stolen, or accidentally leaked. It can control access to data, monitor for unauthorized access, and encrypt data at rest or in transit. DLP can also refer to the software and hardware used to implement these security controls. IAM is a process for managing who has access to which data and resources in an organization. These security controls include policies and procedures for authenticating and authorizing users to access data and resources, thereby bolstering the DLP strategy. DLP and IAM are thus interlinked and are important tools for protecting sensitive data. DLP can help prevent loss by encrypting data and controlling access. IAM can help prevent unauthorized data access by authenticating and authorizing users.

Data Protection

To ensure robust cloud data security, three critical aspects must be addressed: data at rest, data in transit, and intrinsically encryption.

Data at rest, stored on physical storage devices like hard drives or SSDs, can be protected through encryption tools such as BitLocker for Windows and FileVault for macOS. These tools employ the Advanced Encryption Standard

(AES) to scramble data, ensuring only authorized users with the appropriate keys can access it. Both tools offer flexibility to encrypt entire drives, startup disks, or specific partitions, enabling enhanced security against unauthorized access even if a device is physically compromised. A recommended practice for critical environments is to use separate partitions or isolated storage, ensuring sensitive data remains segregated and reducing the risk of cross-contamination in case of breaches.

Data in transit, moving between endpoints such as servers and user devices, is safeguarded using encryption protocols. Communication can leverage secure transport layers like SSL/TLS, forming the backbone of many encrypted tunnels. Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) add an additional layer of security by creating isolated communication channels. Modern VPN implementations, such as OpenVPN, rely on the OpenSSL library to ensure that traffic adheres to robust SSL/TLS standards. This combination not only prevents eavesdropping but also ensures that even if data packets are intercepted, their contents remain inaccessible without the necessary decryption keys.

Beyond conventional methods, homomorphic encryption introduces a revolutionary approach to data security. Unlike traditional encryption, which requires data to be decrypted before processing, homomorphic encryption allows computations directly on encrypted data. This ensures data remains secure even during analysis, significantly enhancing privacy in scenarios involving sensitive information like healthcare or financial data. Its ability to maintain encryption throughout the data lifecycle addresses both performance concerns and the risk of exposure during processing.

To manage encryption effectively, cloud providers offer robust key management services (KMS), such as AWS KMS, Azure Key Vault, and Google Cloud KMS. These services handle the secure storage, distribution, and rotation of cryptographic keys, simplifying encryption for both data at rest and in transit. Regular key rotation further mitigates risks by limiting the exposure window for compromised keys.

Network Traffic Control

Besides designing the perimeter in micro-segments, egress and ingress network traffic filtering is fundamental, both within each segment and in the whole infrastructure.

Egress traffic refers to data that leave the cloud environment, whereas ingress traffic is data that enter the cloud. One of the most serious risks with egress traffic is data leakage, which can occur if data are not properly encrypted or there are gaps in the security barrier. To tackle this threat, the employment of a robust security perimeter barrier, with multiple layers of security, is necessary. Ingress traffic can also be a security concern, allowing mali-

cious actors to access the cloud environment. To prevent this, multi-cloud providers must have strong firewall rules, coordinated with intrusion detection and prevention systems. A robust firewall, besides applying a dynamic filtering with a context-aware approach, it performs a deep packet inspection enabling the analysis of the application layer of packets, detecting also malicious payloads even if encrypted by checking for known encrypted exploits, such firewall solutions go by the name of Next Generation Firewalls(NGFW).

Architecture Model

Several architectural patterns can be outlined in hybrid multi-cloud systems that allow to address complexities, leverage all cloud possibilities and ensure safety, across different layers. In terms of policies management, the recommendation is a federated governance pattern where there is an highly protected centralized governance portal for system-wide or cross environments operations, while allowing autonomy in each environment for local decisions. For cross-provider communication the suggested paradigm is a service mesh for a secure and reliable management, especially in microservices architectures. Similarly create a unified data layer that abstracts and integrates data storage and access across on-premises and cloud environments. The operational model to handle high work loads should apply a cloud bursting, that employs an execution on premises during normal workloads and burst into fallback cloud environments during peak demands, through a properly configured load balancer. Even though not directly correlated to architecture, to ensure application portability and seamless orchestration including version alignment, workload mobility and disaster recovery, employ as much as possible containerization (e.g., Docker) and related automated orchestration services(e.g Kubernetes). Asynchronous communications is tough argument to handle and in event-driven systems, the employment of message brokers like Kafka or AWS EverBridge can reduce the overhead and reduce consumption. Finally in order to guarantee business resilience to cyber threats, cross-cloud redundancy with back-ups is widely applied, such backups are constantly updated with properly created workflows to ensure a close to none discrepancy with production data.

Threat Management

Threat management in hybrid multi-cloud systems relies heavily on effective event logging and active countermeasures to ensure visibility, detect anomalies, and mitigate risks. The fragmented nature of these environments presents challenges, including dispersed logs, high data volumes, and compliance requirements. Centralized log aggregation using tools like Splunk, Elastic Stack, or cloud-native services (e.g., AWS CloudWatch, Azure Mon-

itor) is essential to consolidate and correlate data across platforms. Granular and highly detailed information logging must be employed, using native logging tools offered by CSPs like AWS CloudWatch, Azure Monitor. Aggregating their data, previously parsed correctly by a custom middleware given the likely different formats(e.g. JSON, XML, YAML), in a central environment enables a correlated analysis. A distributed and well orchestrated SIEM architecture employes a thorough threat detection and if properly integrated with SOAR solutions, active countermeasure practices.

To bolster security, organizations increasingly adopt Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response (SOAR) solutions. SOAR platforms like Palo Alto Cortex XSOAR, Splunk Phantom, or IBM Resilient automate threat detection and response workflows. These solutions actively analyze logs, correlate data, and trigger automated playbooks to respond to incidents in real time. For example, a SOAR system can isolate compromised workloads, block malicious IPs, or enforce stricter access controls during a suspected breach, all without human intervention. Best practices include log normalization, real-time monitoring with SIEM/XDR tools (e.g., Microsoft Sentinel, IBM QRadar), and integrating external threat intelligence for identifying indicators of compromise. Retention policies and scalable storage solutions like AWS S3 ensure compliance and forensic readiness

1.3 Data Crucial Role

As pointed out multiple times in former chapters, testing is a critical cornerstone in DevSecOps processes. Automated quality validation and security lay the foundation of a CI/CD pipeline, therefore an exhaustive, seamless and accurate testing is the core joint of development, security and operation integration. Besides, its role transcends mere flaw detection, whether of security or efficiency, it ensures the delivery of robust, scalable, and secure applications in increasingly complex systems such as hybrid multi-cloud ones. Accounting this, in a well designed software delivery life cycle there are multiple testing phases, with heterogeneous goals. It can figure as a continuous testing paradigm, that other than being automated it guarantees full coverage of different nature(code, requirement, risk, environment) and especially a comprehensive validation strategy that includes static, dynamic, functional, non-functional, regressive, exploratory and random methods.

This escalated paradigm involves the introduction of several challenges that, as in every system, should be tackled as early as possible in the design phase. The common denominator of all these challenges is testing data, inevitably representing the main catalyst for testing success.

Data Bottleneck: traditional approaches to test data provisioning often represent a significant bottleneck, impeding the pace of software delivery. This challenge is particularly pronounced when provisioning involves extraction, copying, and movement from production systems to test environments, that require manual intervention. Inefficient data provisioning directly impacts the speed of testing, leading to longer development cycles and slower time-to-market. Ensuring data completeness while maintaining its structure and interdependencies significantly increases the time and effort required for provisioning. Overall slow data delivery undermines DevOps core principles of agility and rapid iteration.

Innovated privacy trade-off: Non-production environments are particularly vulnerable to data breaches due to weaker security controls compared to production systems. The presence of sensitive information, including personally identifiable information (PII), magnifies these risks. Manual and resource-intensive processes for identifying and protecting sensitive data—such as data masking or anonymization—further exacerbate delays and increase the likelihood of errors or not faithful data. Additionally, regulatory legislations like GDPR or HIPAA impose stringent requirements on how organizations handle sensitive data, regardless of whether it resides in production or non-production environments. Failure to meet these requirements can result in significant financial and reputational consequences.

Synchronized Data Delivery: in current DevOps workflows, cloud environments and virtual machines can now be provisioned in minutes, thanks to advancements in infrastructure automation. However, the delivery of corresponding test data often lags behind. Data delivery workflows remain heavily reliant on manual tasks, including data extraction, anonymization, and transfer. - Heterogeneous Data Landscape : Enterprises often maintain a mix of legacy and modern systems, including relational databases, NoSQL stores, and cloud-native data solutions. The coexistence of disparate architectures creates challenges in extracting, normalizing, and provisioning data for DevOps purposes. Moreover, technologies bound siloed environments worsen the integration of data across systems. These siloes lead to isolated data repositories, hindering efforts to create unified and consistent test environments

Data Fidelity: The use of subsetted data, often employed to reduce provisioning time, typically lacks the diversity and coverage necessary to

simulate real-world scenarios. This limitation can lead to inadequate test coverage, leaving critical edge cases unaddressed. Likewise, synthetic data generation, while useful for specific testing needs, may fail to capture the nuanced relationships and dependencies inherent in production datasets, reducing the fidelity of test environments. The infrequency of data refreshes, sometimes spanning months or years, compounds this issue, creating environments that are disconnected from real-world application usage patterns.

Data Access: Complex data provisioning tasks often require multiple hand-offs between operations, database administrators, and development teams. This reliance on inter-team coordination creates bottlenecks and prolongs the time required to prepare test environments.

1.3.1 DataOps

Facing these challenges can be sophisticated, it requires a cultural shift to a dynamic approach to data related activities, that involves technology and protocol agnostic solutions paired with continuous integration, core principles of DataOps.

There are several *-ops paradigms in the whole IT sector, among others DevOps and DataOps are definitely the most established, given the perks they bring to production contexts. DataOps is an approach to data operations that draw from the principles of DevOps (being born and adopted before) to emphasize automation, synchronization, continuous integration and improvement of data and its workflows. Therefore it aims to push the boundaries of siloed data operations like data engineering, data management and data science; in order to integrate them along with IT operations.

Similarly to DevOps, DataOps beating heart are data pipeline, however, unlike CI/CD pipeline, data pipelines manage the continuous integration and delivery of data, ensuring that data flows efficiently, reliably, and in real-time across various stages of data processing, from ingestion to transformation and delivery for consumption by machine learning models, analytics, and other applications. A core concept of DataOps is the automation of extraction, transformation, and delivery of data, ensuring that i.e. ML models are fed with consistent, high-quality data.

Extraction: Data extraction is the initial crucial phase that involves the collection of data robustly across all required environments, this phase must apply a technology and structure agnostic approach, that anyways in most cases requires a meticulous configuration. Two macro methods can be distinguished, batch and stream extractions. While the former is

simpler and less resource-intensive being scheduled and having a fixed size, the latter ensure up-to-the-minute real data required where low-latency is critical, such as with consumers like ML prediction algorithms or live events streaming.

Transformation: where raw data is processed and converted into a more structured, usable format, conceptually it involves the abstraction of its value from diverse frameworks, structures to a uniformed structure organized in a meaningful hierarchical topology. It ensures that the data is clean, normalized, enriched, and properly formatted to meet the needs of downstream processes and decision-making systems

Validation: a control step is required to ensure that the data being processed is accurate, complete, consistent, and adheres to the expected structure and quality standards. It acts as a quality gate, identifying errors, inconsistencies, and anomalies early in the pipeline. Some of the key controls performed are schema, data type and format validation, range boundaries check, uniqueness keys and referential constraints and statistical analysis verification.

Delivery: delivery is the last step, during which transformed and validated data is made available to consumers in target destinations. This step must ensure data integrity, confidentiality and adherence to target destination structure, therefore just like in extraction, the approach applied should be technology and protocol agnostic. Similarly to the extraction phase, few macro provision methods can be distinguished : batched, streamed or event-driven; with the least being triggered by a given configured event, therefore asynchronous, contrarily to batched where it's scheduled, implicating a more complex handling with message brokers.

1.3.2 Programmable Data Infrastructure

Data pipelines are inserted in the wider context of a programmable data infrastructure, being the core component often platform engineering teams or who in charge of the engineering of such systems often overlooks the infrastructure framework being adopted and proceed directly to the engineering of data pipelines, neglecting critical aspects like the infrastructure scalability, interoperability, active monitoring and modification.

Especially in modern data-driven environments where agility, scalability and integration are in high demand, such as when the data consumers are machine learning or big data analytics algorithms, the overall infrastructure

framework plays a vital role. In the design phase, efforts should be made to deploy an infrastructure that enables dynamic, flexible, and automated control over data processing and movement across distributed systems, also known as Programmable Data Infrastructure. PDIs provide a level of abstraction to infrastructure components leveraging software defined principles and programmable interfaces that create a data layer completely independent of underneath technologies to extend control and automation to various components of a data infrastructure, including storage systems, network interfaces, data processing pipelines, and cloud environments. Therefore, A PDI abstracts the complexity of integrating, processing, validating, and delivering data by employing a unified layer of APIs, event-driven workflows, and scalable orchestration. It ensures interoperability, consistency, and real-time responsiveness, making it an essential backbone.

The key characteristic of a PDI is its programmability. With programmability is meant the ability to dictate the behaviour of network devices, such as switches, hubs, routers, NICs(Network Interface Cards) according to the system scenario and circumstances; the custom logic implemented in the technology stack of such devices, goes beyond just the analysis of packet control layer and process the data layer, creating what is an evolution of Software Defined Networking(SDN); SDN delineates a clear separation between the control plane and the data plane, and consolidates the control plane so that a single centralized controller can manage remotely multiple data layers through their APIs with protocols such as OpenFlow[10], nevertheless networking logic is still strictly bound to legacy vendors-bound mechanisms. PDI is new paradigm underpinned by a DSL(Domain Specific Language) like P4(Programming Protocol-independent Packet Processors) that enables an action-match approach to packet processing. The illustration of P4 goes outside the scope of this thesis but it can be conceived as a language used to implement custom packets data layer processing logic. Which, allows engineers to design systems architectures fully adaptable to several contexts, like the Protocol Independent Switch Architecture(PISA) depicted below.

Architecting an infrastructure to fully respects these principles requires a strong commitment, therefore what we can witness in real-world systems is still a SDN with PDIs flavoured components. PDIs became de facto standard mainly in dynamic QoS(Quality of Services) policies in telecom networks, where most of data load is dedicated to monitoring. The main core outcomes of the PDI paradigm adoption or even a well designed SDN are :

Dynamic configuration - scalability: ability to adapt to changing demands, both in terms of workload and nature of requests. System can scale, reconfigure, and optimize itself based on real-time workload patterns, ensuring consistent performance and efficient resource utilization. Two symmetric approach to scaling can be distinguished, horizontal with the allocation of additional nodes or vertical with the increase of resources(CPU, memory) in current instances. A widespread solution to the former is Kubernetes Horizontal Pod Autoscaler(HPA), that monitors metrics like CPU or memory usage and automatically

add pods to handle increased traffic. Another feature, fundamental when it comes to data, is dynamic data partitioning, that ensures intelligent data processing and partitioning in different datasets based on usage patterns, to guarantee a low overhead during high demand events.

Integration: may sound redundant, but integration is intrinsically a feature of such a technology, protocol and data structures agnostic infrastructure, interoperability at all layers.

Automation: as stated formerly, automation is a core concept of data pipelines and PDIs enable a dynamic automation; providing the framework for a constant improvement revealing insights by analysing data patterns, discrepancies, schemas and performance of infrastructure nodes.

1.3.3 Ransomware

As explained broadly formerly, data represents a critical asset in testing environments, especially it's fidelity to production contexts. Therefore, to assure quality of testing, systems are often designed to provision in testing environments masked data directly from production data repositories, rarely not even masked. This continuous integration between production and often several testing environments in different perimeter segments must undergo a thoroughly engineered protection process, that besides guaranteeing integrity, confidentiality and legitimation of data must block lateral movements in production once a testing environments is compromised, which often are by design exposed to several threats and can't be secured further without damaging efficiency and quality. Bringing sensitive data in such environments, enlarge the attacks target surface with an highly valuable asset for attackers. The threats landscape for such target is wide with ransomware being the threat that pose the most risk.

CISA defines ransomware as an ever-evolving form of malware designed to encrypt files on a device at the hardware level, rendering any files or systems that rely on them unusable. Then the attack involves the demand of a ransom payment through decentralized means like cryptocurrencies, in exchange of decryption key. To understand ransomware fully, it must be situated in a wider cybersecurity context and provide a more technical outlook, which is done by analysing it within established threat models and taxonomies that help categorize and contextualize its tactics, techniques and procedures(TTPs) . Hence, a brief overview of attack patterns TTPs tied to ransomware is illustrated below. As described before for CI/CD threats, an

attack is composed of some macro phases defined as tactics, tactics definition and example techniques can be referred to CI/CD threats. When it comes to ransomware typically the tactics involved are Initial Access, Privilege Escalation, Defence Evasion, Credential Access, Discovery, Lateral Movement and Impact. Initial access can be accomplished by several techniques among which spear phishing(T1566) through medias like mail and sms, exploit public-facing applications(T1190) like xss and csrf; External Remote Services(T1133) using unsecured RDP, SSH or VPN bound services. Proceeding privilege escalation is performed by Process Injection(T1055) that inject malicious payloads in legitimate code in order to mask it as a part of legitimate process. Moving on, usually defence evasion is performed through techniques like Impair Defenses(T1562) by disabling or modifying controls of security detection tools. Disabling such tools, attackers can perform harmful operation, by standard monitored, undetected, like accessing sensitive information stores and this leads us to Credential Access employed by OS Credential Dumping(T1003) or Credential from Password Stores(T1555). Then attackers proceed with a recognition phase aimed at the discovery of further files or directories hidden or underpinned through links(T1083), locally; and additional valuable targets in the network(T1016) where previously found credentials can be leveraged to perform malicious activities, such tactic is called Discovery. All previous activities are aimed at the creation of an ideal context for the access of additional environments in different segments of the perimeter, that likely store more sensitive data, such tactic is known as Lateral Movement and it is commonly applied leveraging Remote Services(T1021) like RDP, SSH, SMB; or hijacking sessions(T1563) of such services stealing session tokens and impersonating the legitimate host. Finally compromised systems are subject to the encryption of their data and deletion of optional back-up archives, which constitute the final Impact of the attack, some techniques mapped in ATT&CK obviously are Data Encrypted for Impact(T1486), Inhibit System Recovery(T1490), Service Stop(T1489) which consist in the termination of archivation systems like databases or backups to ensure encryption success.

The ransomware threats target landscape is wide and scattered across multiple nations and sectors, this is just one of the main reasons, along with the missing reporting of incidents, why ransomware data articles from leading research organizations report similar but not identical results. Anyways, the direction is clear : ransomware is the preferred monetization method by attackers, its widespread is growing year-over-year and likewise its financial impact. As covered by a thorough research realized by Sophos on 5,000 cyber/IT organizations leaders[24] across all macro industries and 14 countries in 2024, 59% were affected by a ransomware attack with an av-

average ransom of 2.73\$ million, of which 57% attempts to access back-ups were successful. Even though, the sample is small, central/federated governments reported the highest attack hit rate of 69%, with other notable rates being in healthcare, both lower and higher education; with the latter having also one of the highest rate of back-up compromise success with 71%. Back-ups compromise is noteworthy since it results in on average doubling of the ransom demand, correlated by a higher probability of ransom payment. Additionally, it is severe to mention some medium-big organizations that filed for bankruptcy or insolvency following a ransomware attack, like the 150-year long thriving KNP Logistic Group in 2023, one of the UK's largest privately owned logistics firms, that led to the loss of 730 jobs[25]. One of the most interesting insights of the previously cited report, is that 93% of ransomware tied malwares are Windows based executables, this is largely due to the fact that most enterprise and personal devices host Windows OS and one of the most widespread storage technologies across enterprise contexts is Microsoft's Active Directory. Moreover, often these technologies have legacy versions, with several vulnerabilities unpatched. Therefore, heterogeneous attack vectors mentioned formerly can be leveraged to exploit a wide range of vulnerabilities, ensuring that no single sector or organization type is immune. A core ransomware concept is the targeting of an asset that fuels organizations of all kinds, data. Hence, in the target recognition phase attackers evaluate if the potentially in scope data is critical for the target business operations, or highly sensitive whether they are customer records, intellectual property or financial data. Given critically valuable data, the analysis proceeds with the value estimation that paired with an evaluation of the target ability to afford the ransom lead to create a proper ransom proposal. Another core ransomware concept is its universal operational impact, as it affects three business operations that mark all organizations: data encryption, financial strain, reputation damage. These characteristics of the ransomware threat target landscape and intrinsically of the attack itself, make it a threat that transcends from industry sector, therefore is also known as cross-business threat.

An operational approach that is taking over the ransomware widespread is Ransomware as a Service (RaaS). From a business outlook, RaaS is a subscription-based business model that enables hackers to use pre-developed ransomware kind exploitation code, phishing tools, as well as all payment gateways. Much like legitimate Software-as-a-Service offerings, this service provides everything needed to launch and manage ransomware attacks without requiring extensive technical expertise. In essence, it allows cybercriminals to rent the malware infrastructure created by experienced developers, who typically receive a cut of any successful ransoms collected. RaaS recog-

nized an extraordinary success in the recent years, to the extent that nowadays service providers scaled their offering with fully self-managed platforms that follow the serverless paradigm offered through a web portal, where consumers(or affiliates according to the business model) can start tailored phishing campaigns, see the status of infections, total payments, total files encrypted and other information about their targets. An affiliate can simply log into the RaaS portal, create an account, pay with Bitcoin, enters details on the type of malware and execute the attack. Subscribers may have access to support, communities, documentation, feature updates, and other benefits identical to those received by subscribers to legitimate SaaS products. Proliferation of this service-oriented approach has profound implications for the cybersecurity landscape, as it lowers barriers to entry and enables even those without sophisticated technical know-how to launch ransom attacks. Mainly due to this shit in the approach ransomware has rapidly evolved from a mere cybersecurity threat into a full-fledged industry. Several types of ransomware attacks can be classified according to their attack kill chain and intended final impact. The following is a basic comprehensive list of macro ransomware types:

- File Encrypting : Ryuk
- Locker : LockBit
- Double Extortion : Maze
- Wiper : figure as a ransomware but disrupt business operations by forcing deletion of data from disks

Preventing a ransomware attack involves applying defense mechanisms to detect and inhibit, briefly mentioned previously, attack techniques that fall in Initial Access tactic. Some have already been covered with CI/CD threats, but when it comes to ransoms some attack techniques are more accentuated, which means that they appear in IOCs of several known ransomware malwares, than others, therefore likewise determined defense best practices must be enforced strongly. Prevention best practices are grouped by common initial access vectors of ransomware and data extortion actors :

Internet-Facing Vulnerabilities and Misconfigurations: besides standard best practices like regularly patching softwares and underlying OS, conduct routine vulnerability scans and implement a robust logging of internet-facing services, further practices regarding mainly exploited protocols in ransomware contexts(RDP, SSH) are :

Limit Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP) Exposure: avoid exposing RDP on the web. If required, enforce public key based authentication and compensate with controls like multi-factor authentication (MFA) and account lockouts. Regularly audit and close unused RDP ports (TCP 3389)

Harden SMB protocols: Update SMB to his minimum secure standard version(3.1+), and enable message encryption or signing. Block external SMB access at firewalls (e.g., TCP port 445) and limit internal traffic to essential systems. The best configuration requires the use of SMB over QUIC, which employs always Transport Layer Security (TLS) 1.3 encryption and use of certificate authentication to encapsulate all SMB traffic inside a VPN-like transport. Additionally, always require Kerberos-based IPsec handshake for lateral SMB communications(ZTA)[16].

Compromised Credentials: strictly related to the management of identities access, as well as credentials and secrets :

Implement multi-factor authentication (MFA): Deploy phishing-resistant MFA for critical services like email, VPNs, and sensitive accounts , and consider password-less MFA methods(e.g., fingerprints, facial recognition, cryptographic keys).

Credential management and monitoring: Subscribe to credential monitoring services to detect compromised credentials on the dark web. Where possible, use password managers, securing them with MFA and all available protections.

Phishing: involves sending messages through main communication medias (email, sms, social medias) with malicious payload to gain access to the victim's system. Often, employe social engineering tactics, with a context-aware approach, in such cases it's also referred as spear-phishing :

Flagging and filtering: application of email gateway filtering that block emails with external domain, suspicious IPs and overall known indicators of compromise(IOCs). Filtering is also applied at attachment level, blocking emails attachments with common malware file type; in this regard, attention should be brought to password-protected archives that often evade widespread email filters. Likewise, for Microsoft Office files disabling of macro scripts should be enforced.

Domain-based email verification: implement Domain-based Message Authentication, Reporting, and Conformance (DMARC) policies to minimize spoofed or modified emails. DMARC builds on the widely deployed Sender Policy Framework (SPF) and Domain Keys Identified Mail (DKIM) protocols, adding a reporting function that allows senders and receivers to improve and monitor protection of the domain from fraudulent email[11]

Once a malicious actor got a foothold in the target system, compromising one or more of the previously mentioned prevention tactics; detection, mitigation and response practices must be employed in order to minimize the magnitude of the impact and therefore guarantee business resilience. Such practices must be implemented through industry standard tools, whose priority is continuous update and integration to the latest IOCs and attack patterns. The core practice are controls, requests of all kinds, related logs, resources usage, local command executions. A control system can reach high levels of complexity, that often force attackers to discover cutting-edge vulnerabilities, also know as zero-day, to achieve their goal.

Nevertheless, ransomware, for the nature of the attack goal, is distinguished by several different paths of attack execution, very few of the current control infrastructure available in the market, if configured thoroughly and continuously reviewed, mitigate ransomware attacks promptly. As a matter of fact, previous ransomware attacks, that fall in the categories previously mentioned, besides being resilient to intrusion detection(defense evasion) have as a key feature a high speed of encryption, eluding automated data integrity controls and mass modification threshold. Such ransomware defenses, which can be applied widely to other threats, require a combination of practices, technical tools, and a focus on speed and frequency to ensure an active response before significant damage occurs. This involves a multi-layered, behavioural based defense approach, with a variety of tools synchronised together among which IDS, XDR, SIEM and SOAR play a crucial role. When it comes to mitigation after a successful foothold in the system perimeter, high attention must be placed on IDS controls. First of all, two macro levels of intrusion detection can be distinguished, network-based and host-based, with the former focusing on unusual network traffic indicative of ransomware(C2 servers, exfiltration, spike in suspicious type of traffic) and the latter monitoring endpoint behaviours (mass file modification, unrecognized edit patterns, known malware file hashes). Focusing on endpoint behaviours, three main challenges, also mentioned briefly, encounter IDS :

- Control robustness : integrity controls are still bound to traditional approaches, often limited to signature and hash or deviation from nor-

mal execution patterns, which modern ransoms can evade respectively by replicating file-system signature mechanism, manipulating data completeness and masking itself as a legitimate administrative process.

Lack of granular context tracking is another major factor that contribute to this weakness, without considering data modification trends scheduled legitimate jobs often get blocked.

- Control speed : most modern ransomware employ cutting-edge encryption techniques, also known as zero-day, that encrypt whole file systems in minutes, data integrity monitoring mechanisms isn't often equally fast. This is simply due to the nature of operations and fundamental differences in computational efficiency. Encryption can be reduced to a one computational cycle operation, leveraging on-the-fly encryption as it is directly written and modern encryption algorithms such as Advanced Encryption Standard with hardware acceleration(AES-NI) designed for gigabit-per-second throughput. Conversely, integrity control require at least three computation cycles : reading expected, reading effective and comparison; and often all the data in scope must be verified before eventually triggering response mechanisms. Of course, it may looks obvious that this encryption outpacing concern can be resolved by comparing the hash of data, but this comes with several drawbacks and complexities that will be illustrated later.

On the other hand, some ransoms employ a slow and steady encryption, which is below data modification threshold, therefore looking harmless.

- Control frequency : data integrity controls are often scheduled with a frequency directly correlated with data sensibility, size and resources availability, and usually spans from few days to minutes. From a security point of view, the shorter the control cycle the better it is, but highly frequent controls come with few drawbacks such as an overhead to other processes using the controlled data and high resource consumption. The perfect trade-off would be an event-driven control, which require a real-time monitoring of data. Though, as cited multiple times a correct malicious modification detection can be highly complex

Once a ransomware attack has been detected, further tools are used to perform an attack response in order to reduce attack impact. This involves the integration of IDS with SOAR. In most scenarios, SOAR playbooks include :

- Isolation : the first priority is to contain the infection to prevent lateral movement across the network. By applying further VLAN segmentation, disabling network interfaces, updating firewalls, especially WAF to block attacker controlled domains and IPs. If possible, would be even better to switch them off before acquiring snapshots.
- Terminate malicious processes and remove all its artifacts : all malware related processes, associated files, registry keys, scheduled tasks are terminated or removed. Usually, before a snapshot of volatile memory is acquired to extract IOCs.
- Disable compromised accounts : compromised accounts leveraged for initial access or lateral movement are disabled and completely reset.
- Mount clean back-up in production : pre-verified, secure, and malware-free golden image is mounted in production environment to replace compromised system. Likewise, for database technologies clean back-ups are deployed in production environments.

Besides these automated operations, following operations to reduce security gaps are : threat intelligence, forensic analysis, notification of all stakeholders and with results edit of security posture of the system : which can include new perimeter segmentation, additional enhanced firewall rules, accounts permissions downgrades.

The aforementioned challenges in ransomware mitigation highlight the need for a solution that emphasizes efficiency, granularity, accuracy and guarantees an high degree of operational resilience. The solution presented in the next chapters seek to satisfy these requirements by leverage the features of a PDI(Delphix Data Platform) not in its native settings. The proposed approach aims to execute a control on relation data structures with single cell granularity, on virtualised version of data, allowing to witness mismatches, data versioning and finally trigger an attack response that notifies all stakeholders and following a manual confirmation loads the latest clean version in production.

1.4 Delphix - DevOps Data Platform

As defined by Perforce, the organisation behind Delphix, Delphix is a data platform that enables organizations to manage, secure, and deliver data efficiently across hybrid and multi-cloud environments. It provides automated data virtualization, masking, and compliance capabilities to accelerate application development, cloud migrations, and AI/ML initiatives while ensuring

data security and regulatory compliance. By integrating Continuous Data, Continuous Compliance, and centralized orchestration, Delphix allows teams to rapidly provision, refresh, and version data, reducing bottlenecks in software delivery and enhancing data governance.

Figure 1.18: Delphix data platform overview [9]

It's fundamental to assess that it is offered via SaaS, hence Delphix engines are delivered and maintained as a closed virtual software appliance. Like all virtual appliances, these engines are a tightly integrated combination of a special-purpose operating system and business logic; their usage directions specify that the Continuous Data Engine can be solely configured for data virtualization, while the Continuous Compliance Engine for data masking. Additionally, obviously conforming to the SaaS paradigm, consumers do not have any administrative permission on the underlying operating system and software dependencies, including installing custom software or perform any kind of analysis.

Delphix provide a level of abstraction that allows the creation of a purely data plane infrastructure. This data plane infrastructure is highly flexible, scalable, observable and above all efficient; enabling a data management completely independent of underneath technologies, data entities and architectural context. Till a certain extent, Delphix could be exposed as a previously illustrated Programmable Data Infrastructure(PDI), as it employs the paradigm concept of abstracting or facilitate the complexities of integration, processing, validation, and delivery of data. Nevertheless, there is a noteworthy gap between the abstraction provided by the Programmable Data Infrastructure depicted before and Delphix, actually they are symmetric. A PDI regards the low level, resolving directly around network devices(i.e. switches, hubs, routers) implementing a custom logic in their technology stack, underpinned by a specifically crafted DSL; whereas Delphix data platform operate an abstraction toward an high level, its software components are designed

and developed to be extremely technology agnostics, transcend from data structures and allow an high degree of customisation.

Figure 1.19: Delphix infrastructure agnosticism [9]

Figure 1.20: Delphix technology agnosticism [9]

Furthermore, Delphix engines are built with a strong emphasis on API-first design, which allows full automation and integration with modern Infrastructure-as-Code(IaC) based workflows. Its highly widespread use case to date is the automation of test environments provisioning. Further main use-case are cloud data migration and disaster recovery, all of these usage scenario are combined in this control solution.

Another key application of Delphix data platform is to secure of data, both in terms of privacy and compliance, as well as protection from exfiltrations. Once data management is abstracted to a data plane infrastructure, operations on it are significantly easier. Delphix’s data privacy and compliance capabilities abstract the core data management paradigm functionalities such as data governance, data security, data protection, data integrity, and data optimization. These functions together form a comprehensive strategy for ensuring that data is protected, compliant, and accessible while minimising risk, optimising usage, and adhering to regulatory standards. Through data masking, data subsetting, and data redaction, Delphix ensures that production data is obfuscated or minimized in non-production environments, preserving privacy without compromising data utility for testing and development. The platform also offers audit trails and access controls to track and manage data usage, ensuring accountability and transparency. Additionally, Delphix supports compliance reporting, enabling organisations to demonstrate alignment with regulatory requirements like GDPR, HIPAA, and CCPA, ultimately ensuring secure, compliant, and efficient data management practices .

Hence, features offered by the Delphix DevOps Data Platform can be aggre-

gated within 4 main services, each of which plays a very important part in delivering fresh secure data to anybody that needs it :

Virtualize: Delphix compresses the data that it gathers, often to one-third or more of the original size. From that compressed data footprint, Delphix virtualizes the data and allows operators to create lightweight, virtual data copies. Virtual copies are fully readable/writable and independent. They can be spun up or torn down in just minutes. And they take up a fraction of the storage space of physical copies – 10 virtual copies can fit into the space of one physical copy.

Identify and secure: The Delphix platform continuously protects sensitive information with integrated data masking. Masking secures confidential data – names, email addresses, patient records, SSNs – by replacing sensitive values with fictitious, yet realistic equivalents. Delphix automatically identifies sensitive values and then applies custom or predefined masking algorithms. By seamlessly integrating data masking and provisioning into a single platform, Delphix ensures that secure data delivery is effortless and repeatable.

Manage: Data operators can now quickly provision secure data copies – in minutes – to users in their target environments. The Delphix platform serves as a single point of control to manage those copies. Data operators maintain full control and visibility into downstream environments. They can easily audit, monitor, and report against access and usage.

Self-service: Provides developers, testers, analysts, data scientists, or other users with controls to manipulate data at will. Users can refresh data to reflect the latest state of production, rewind environments to a prior point in time, bookmark data copies for later use, branch data copies to work across multiple releases, or easily share data with other users.

With that being asserted, two core components components in the software suite can be distinguished and contribute more broadly to provide the aforementioned services. They are interconnected by design and therefore constantly collaborate : Continuous Data Engine and Continuous Compliance Engine

1.4.1 Continuous Data Engine : Technical Overview

The Delphix Continuous Data Engine is a sophisticated programmable data infrastructure designed to integrate with diverse data sources, including relational database management systems (RDBMSs), no-SQL, JSON, YAML,

XML files. The platform leverages advanced data ingestion and virtualisation techniques to optimise storage, enhance compliance, and facilitate efficient data provisioning.

The Continuous Data engine connects to your source database(s) to take in a full readable, writable copy of your data. When it does this, the data is compressed (usually to about 1/3 the size). After the initial data ingestion, the Delphix Continuous Data Engine stays connected to your source environment. Each time the data from your source environment changes, the Continuous Data engine ingests only the new data blocks rather than an entire 1:1 copy. This collection of source data blocks is referred to as a dSource. The Delphix Continuous Data Engine maintains synchronization either by using product native replication such as Dataguard, SQL Server log shipping, and Postgres replication, or via product native incremental backups. User defined policies dictate the frequency of synchronization. Delphix maintains a Timeflow of the source database; a record of snapshots and log changes. Virtual copies of your database (VDBs) can then be provisioned from dSource (or VDB) snapshots, from any point in time in a timeflow. VDBs are read-write virtual databases, and changes made to the VDB are written to new, compressed blocks in Delphix storage. The data within the VDB can be refreshed as needed, to any point in time along its source's timeline.

Figure 1.21: continuous data engine web dashboard

Data Ingestion and Virtualisation

The data ingestion process within the Delphix Continuous Data Engine is

performed through SnapSync, a mechanism that copies and compresses data to approximately one-third of its original size. The resulting copy, known as a dSource, is fundamentally a collection of metadata regarding original data on connected database, along with its incremental updates. It serves to provision virtual representation of data.

Delphix remains continuously connected to the source environment, ensuring that every modification in the original dataset is reflected in the dSource. Notably, SnapSync is optimized for efficiency as it only captures newly modified blocks from the source environment rather than duplicating entire datasets. Since a dSource is a virtual entity, it cannot be directly manipulated using traditional database tools. Instead, Delphix generates snapshots — instantaneous copies of the data state — organized in a timeflow. From these snapshots, virtual databases (VDBs) can be provisioned, allowing users to work with lightweight, fully functional clones of their databases. Snapshots are created during specific events, the most common ones are dSource creation and virtual database refresh operations. Each VDB also maintains its own timeflow, recording the snapshots from which additional VDBs can be generated.

Figure 1.22: conceptual VDB provisioning [8]

Figure 1.23: conceptual VDB timeflow [8]

Storage Efficiency and Block Sharing Mechanism

During the initial data ingestion process, a backup of the source data is required to create the first snapshot of the dSource. The Continuous Data Engine employs block sharing across snapshots to ensure that only new data blocks are written when changes occur. Within the engine memory a shared snapshot space is stored, where data blocks shared between multiple snapshot of the same data set reside. Furthermore, data with different entities can share the same data blocks as well, in the most common scenario VDB and dSource snapshots, this setting is particularly capacity efficient with the initial VDB snapshot, which typically requires zero additional storage. The

VDB file system is cloned from a dSource snapshot, and the only additional data stored during provisioning consists of transaction logs applied during the process.

Figure 1.24: dSource management web dashboard

LogSync: Granular Data Ingestion and Versioning

An alternative data ingestion method highly widespread is LogSync, which captures database transaction logs rather than entire data blocks. LogSync provides more granular control, enabling provisioning of a VDB from any point in time between snapshot endpoints and refreshing or rewinding a VDB to a previous transaction state. When both LogSync and SnapSync are set up, LogSync operates independently of SnapSync, maintaining a separate connection to the source environment and retrieving transaction logs. It is particularly effective for databases that rely heavily on transactional consistency.

Policy-Driven Data Management

To automate data operations within the engine, Delphix employs a policy-based management system that governs system operations such as : snapshot frequency for dSources and VDBs (default: daily); retention policies for snapshots, ensuring compliance with security standards; and continuous VDB refresh rates. Retention policies are particularly critical for financial, health, public services organisations adhering to regulatory compliance and long-term data preservation requirements.

Virtual-to-Physical (V2P) Export

For scenarios requiring physical database restoration, Delphix provides a Virtual-to-Physical (V2P) process that exports data from a VDB or dSource

into a target physical storage environment, such as a classic database. This process creates physical database directories that besides containing raw database files contain all metadata object like transaction logs and deployment scripts. V2P is commonly utilised for migrating production data to cloud environments in order to have an identical copy with the same settings whose main use case is back-up; or following an significant incident to reconstruct physical databases from virtual copies.

Data Replication and Multi-Engine Environments

Delphix supports data replication across multiple engines, allowing organizations to copy dSources and VDBs from a source engine to a target engine (also known as a namespace). Replication process plays a key role in the following scenarios :

- Disaster Recovery (DR) : having a backup copy of critical data to restore operations following a system failure or unauthorised data modification that compromised definitively all the data. Replication can be scheduled or asynchronous, with target engines initially disabled in a passive state. In the event of a catastrophic failure, a failover process promotes the target engine to replace the failed source engine. However, the replication mechanism does not guarantee high availability, as some data loss may occur between the last synchronization and the disaster event. Failover is not automated and often requires manual intervention for configuration adjustments.
- Geographically Distributed Development : replication allows organisations to replicate data to one or multiple cloud-based engine with ease. I.e. for global development teams, this seamless replication process allows developers in different locations to provision VDBs from remotely accessible dSources without direct access to the original source environment.
- Cloud Migration : one of the most widespread refactoring that interested organisations at the architectural level in the past years. Replication ease the process with its incremental approach and data transfer optimised network transfer protocols, additionally data being also compressed to one third of its original size allows lower bandwidth requirements and therefore multiple parallel transfers.

1.4.2 Continuous Compliance Engine : Technical Overview

In general settings, once data has been ingested into the Delphix Continuous Data Engine, and a dSource has been linked, the other core component of

the suite enters in action : the Delphix Continuous Compliance Engine. It is used to secure sensitive data through the process of masking .

The Delphix Continuous Compliance Engine is a data profiling and masking solution designed to help organizations protect sensitive information across diverse data environments. By automating the discovery and obfuscation of confidential data, it ensures compliance with various regulatory standards and reduces the risk of data breaches. This engine is particularly adept at handling data from mainframes to modern cloud platforms, providing a unified approach to data security.

In today's data-driven landscape, enterprises manage vast amounts of information, including personally identifiable information (PII), financial records, and health data. Ensuring the privacy and security of this data is paramount, especially with stringent regulations like GDPR, CCPA, HIPAA, and PCI DSS. The Delphix Continuous Compliance Engine addresses these challenges by:

- **Identifying Sensitive Data:** automatically discovering sensitive information, such as names, email addresses, and credit card numbers, across a broad range of data sources.
- **Masking or Tokenising Data:** replacing sensitive data with fictitious yet realistic data while maintaining referential integrity, ensuring that masked data remains functional for development and testing purposes.

Unlike encryption measures that can be bypassed through schemes to obtain user credentials, masking irreversibly protects data in downstream environments. Consistent masking of data while maintaining referential integrity across heterogeneous data sources enables Delphix masking to provide superior coverage compared to other solutions—all without the need for programming expertise. Moreover, the Delphix DevOps Data Platform seamlessly integrates masking with data delivery capabilities, ensuring the security of sensitive data before it is made available for development and testing, or sent to an offsite data center or the public cloud.

Environment	Job Name	Status	Progress	Submit Time	Start Time	Type	Actions
env_W3486FEU	prof_1MVP92EA	SUCCEEDED	5 of 5 - Profiling Complete	31 May 2024 11:48 IST	31 May 2024 11:48 IST	PROFILE	
env_QHDTVP69	prof_VM8CB186	CANCELLED	5 of 5 - Profiling Complete	31 May 2024 11:47 IST	31 May 2024 11:47 IST	PROFILE	
env_XH3M04HZ	prof_2W27C80H	SUCCEEDED	5 of 5 - Profiling Complete	31 May 2024 11:46 IST	31 May 2024 11:46 IST	PROFILE	
env_OA566DDP	prof_LFC54WA8	FAILED	5 of 5 - Profiling Complete	31 May 2024 11:44 IST	31 May 2024 11:44 IST	PROFILE	
env_QaXIN8R	prof_47GTREJ	SUCCEEDED	5 of 5 - Profiling Complete	31 May 2024 11:43 IST	31 May 2024 11:43 IST	PROFILE	
env_UINIG02X	mask_TLY9JLX	CANCELLED	10 of 10 - Job Completed	31 May 2024 11:39 IST	31 May 2024 11:39 IST	MASK	
env_QH2F7534	mask_XH854T4U	FAILED	10 of 10 - Job Completed	31 May 2024 11:38 IST	31 May 2024 11:38 IST	MASK	
env_XL8L6VSR	mask_HSNW6TOB	WARNING	10 of 10 - Job Completed	31 May 2024 11:36 IST	31 May 2024 11:36 IST	MASK	
env_YH2M983L	reidentify_F1YYS	SUCCEEDED	10 of 10 - Job Completed	31 May 2024 11:34 IST	31 May 2024 11:34 IST	RE-IDENTIFY	
env_YH2M983L	tokenize_JH6NSM	SUCCEEDED	10 of 10 - Job Completed	31 May 2024 11:33 IST	31 May 2024 11:33 IST	TOKENIZE	
env_NAM8F24V	tokenize_A4E1C	SUCCEEDED	10 of 10 - Job Completed	31 May 2024 11:31 IST	31 May 2024 11:31 IST	TOKENIZE	
env_HNFJNEH	mask_2TR94XA1	CANCELLED	10 of 10 - Job Completed	31 May 2024 00:06 IST	31 May 2024 00:06 IST	MASK	
env_HLEKYFPS	mask_310X9VYV	FAILED	10 of 10 - Job Completed	31 May 2024 00:04 IST	31 May 2024 00:04 IST	MASK	

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Figure 1.25: continuous compliance web dashboard

Delphix Masking is a multi-user, browser-based web application that provides complete, secure, and scalable software for your sensitive data discovery, masking, and tokenization needs while meeting enterprise-class infrastructure requirements. The Delphix DevOps Data Platform has several key characteristics to enable your organization to successfully protect sensitive data across the enterprise :

- End-to-End masking : The Delphix platform automatically detects confidential information, irreversibly masks data values, then generates reports and email notifications to confirm that all sensitive data has been masked.
- Realistic data : Data masked with the Delphix platform is production-like in quality. Masked application data in non-production environments remain fully functional and realistic, enabling the development of higher-quality code.
- Masking integrated with Virtualization : Most masking solutions fail due to the need for repeated, lengthy batch jobs for extracting and masking data and a lack delivery capabilities for downstream environments. The Delphix DevOps Data Platform seamlessly integrates data masking with data virtualization, allowing teams to quickly deliver masked, virtual data copies on-premises or into private, public, and hybrid cloud environments.
- Referential integrity : Delphix masks consistently across heterogeneous data sources. To do so, metadata and data are scanned to identify and

preserve the primary/foreign key relationships between elements so that data is masked the same way across different tables and databases.

- Algorithms/Frameworks : Eighteen algorithm frameworks allow users to create and configure algorithms to match specific security policies. Over twenty-five out-of-the-box, preconfigured algorithms help businesses mask everything from names and addresses to credit card numbers and text fields. Moreover, the Delphix platform includes prepackaged profiling sets for healthcare and financial information, as well as the ability to perform tokenization: a process that can be used to obfuscate data sent for processing, then reversed when the processed data set is returned.
- Ease of use : With a single solution, Delphix customers can mask data across a variety of platforms. Moreover, businesses are not required to program their own masking algorithms or rely on extensive administrator involvement. Our web-based UI enables masking with a few mouse clicks and little training.
- Automated discovery of sensitive data : The Delphix Profiler automatically identifies sensitive data across databases and files, and the time-consuming work associated with a data masking project is reduced significantly.

Data Identification and Profiling

Sensitive data identification is done using two different methods, column-level profiling, and data-level profiling :

- Column-level profiling : column-level profiling uses regular expressions to scan the column names (metadata) of the selected data sources. There are several dozen pre-configured classifiers designed to identify common sensitive data types (SSN, Name, Addresses, etc). You also have the ability to write/import your own classifiers.
- Data-level profiling : Data level profiling also uses regular expressions, but to scan the actual data instead of the metadata. Similar to column-level profiling, there are several dozen pre-configured classifiers and you can write/import your own.

For both column and data level profiling, when data is identified as sensitive, Delphix recommends/assigns particular algorithms to be used when securing the data. The platform comes with several dozen pre-configured algorithms which are recommended when the profiler finds certain sensitive data.

To comprehend thoroughly sensitive data discovery process, some objects and concepts the masking mechanism is built upon must be clarified :

Rule Set: a collection of database tables or flat files within a specific data source that users designate for profiling, masking, or tokenization operations. By organizing related data structures into rule sets, the Masking Engine streamlines the process of identifying and securing sensitive information across various environments. Each rule set is associated with a specific environment and utilizes a connector to define the connection parameters to the data source. This association ensures that masking operations are accurately targeted and executed within the intended context.

The screenshot shows the 'Rule Sets' page in the Continuous Compliance web interface. The page title is 'Demo_Environment' and it includes a '+ Rule Set' button. Below the title, there are tabs for 'Jobs', 'Rule Sets', and 'Connectors'. The main content is a table listing various rule sets.

Rule Set ID	Name	Connector Name	Source Type	Metadata	Refresh/Save	Actions
23	MysqlRuleset	MysqlDBConnector	Database	mysql	✓	...
24	HanaRuleset	HanaConnector	Database	extended	✓	...
25	PostgresRuleset	PostgresDBConnector	Database	POSTGRESQL	✓	...
26	LocalPostgresRuleset	LocalhostPostgresDB	Database	POSTGRESQL	✓	...
27	OracleRuleset	OracleConnector	Database	oracle	✓	...
28	WholeFileRs	WholeFileConnector	Fixed Width	File	N/A	...
29	JSONFileRs	JSONFileConnector	JSON	File	N/A	...
30	FixedFileRs	FixedFileConnector	Fixed Width	File	N/A	...
31	XMLFileRs	XMLFileConnector	XML	File	N/A	...
32	DelimitedFileRs	DelimitedFileConnector	Delimited	File	N/A	...
33	MainFrameFileRuleSet	MainFrameFileConnector	DataSet	Mainframe	N/A	...

Figure 1.26: rule sets web interface

Profile Set: defines the logic that will be used to determine which columns or fields in the rule set contain sensitive information. A profile set contains a set of classifiers, that define the recognition logic for the ASDD profiler. As each classifier is associated with a domain, the composition of the profile set determines which types of sensitive data may be detected by a profiling job using a particular profile set.

Name	Description	ASDD	Owner	Created	Actions
set_B6DLFHB3	IL4T92EC	No	admin	2 Apr 2024 11:22 IST	...
set_4U7ZIRRB	YYQY6GIE	No	admin	2 Apr 2024 10:05 IST	...
set_PEP4SRXN	4IOIRD8G	No	admin	2 Apr 2024 10:03 IST	...
ASDD Standard		Yes	admin	16 Jun 2023 01:27 IST	...
Standard		No	admin	16 Jun 2023 01:27 IST	...
Financial - Legacy		No	admin	15 Jun 2023 05:30 IST	...
HIPAA - Legacy		No	admin	15 Jun 2023 05:30 IST	...

Displaying 1 to 7 of 7

Figure 1.27: profile sets web interface

Domain: represents a particular type of sensitive information, such as first name or tax ID number. Based on the detection logic in the profile set, a profile job may assign a domain to a particular field or column in the rule set; when this occurs, the default masking algorithm defined for that domain will also be assigned. The domain mechanism helps to ensure that the same masking algorithm is applied consistently across rule sets whenever a particular type of sensitive data is discovered.

Name	Owner	Masking Method	Tokenization Method	Actions
ACCOUNT_NO	System	dipx-core:CM Alpha-Numeric		...
ACCOUNT_TK	System	NullValueLookup	AccountTK	...
ADDRESS	System	AddrLookup		...
ADDRESS_LINE2	System	AddrLine2Lookup		...
AGE	System	dipx-core:Age SL		...
BANK_ACCOUNT_NO	System	dipx-core:CM Numeric		...
BENEFICIARY_NO	System	dipx-core:CM Alpha-Numeric		...
BIOMETRIC	System	NullValueLookup		...
BLOOD_TYPE	System	dipx-core:BloodType SL		...
CERTIFICATE_NO	System	dipx-core:CM Alpha-Numeric		...

Displaying 1 to 10 of 69

Figure 1.28: domains web interface

Classifier: defines a specific piece of logic for recognizing sensitive data. Classifiers may only be used with the ASDD profiler. Classifiers use a framework and instance model, similar to algorithms. A framework represents a particular software module for detecting sensitive infor-

mation, while an instance provides the configuration for a framework and associates it with a particular domain. The following classifier frameworks are available by default :

- **PATH** : examines the path to the data in question and applies regular expression and/or exact match logic to match domains. For databases, the path includes the table and column name.
- **TYPE** : uses the data type and length of a field or column to detect possible domain matches. Supported types are String, Number, Date and Binary.
- **REGEX** : matches the data itself using regular expressions to match or reject domains.
- **LIST** : checks whether data values are present in a list of value to match or reject domains.

Name ↑	Domain	Owner	Type	Description	Actions
Credit Card Number - Regex	CREDIT_CARD	System	REGEX		...
Credit Card Number - Type	CREDIT_CARD	System	TYPE		...
Customer Number - Path	CUSTOMER_NO	System	PATH		...
Customer Number - Type	CUSTOMER_NO	System	TYPE		...
Data Classifier - Email	EMAIL	admin	REGEX	UMR9L97B	...
Data Classifier - Telephone...	TELEPHONE_NO	admin	REGEX	541T7XLB	...
Data Classifier - Zip Code	ZIP	admin	REGEX	6H677W88	...
Date of Birth - Path	DOB	System	PATH		...
Date of Birth - Type	DOB	System	TYPE		...
Department - List	DEPARTMENT	System	LIST		...
Department - Path	DEPARTMENT	System	PATH		...
Department - Type	DEPARTMENT	System	TYPE		...

Displaying 36 to 48 of 165

Figure 1.29: classifiers web interface

Hence, fundamentally the sensitive data discovery process involves the creation of a rule set, then the rule set is profiled by a specifically crafted profiling job. This profiling job examines the metadata, such as column names and types, and potentially the data itself, based on the configured classifier, to determine which columns or fields contain sensitive information. Upon determining that a data item is sensitive, the profiler assigns the matching domain and associated masking algorithm to the column or field. Being fully automated, this process is known as Automated Sensitive Data Discovery (ASDD) and requires a specific profiler.

Securing Data

Data masking is a comprehensive solution designed to safeguard sensitive information across diverse data environments. By replacing original data with fictitious yet realistic equivalents, it ensures data privacy while maintaining the functional integrity necessary for development, testing, and analytical processes. Masking is characterised by two methods and two architectural modality. Therefore, four different masking implementation can be distinguished.

The two secure methods Delphix currently supports are masking (anonymization) and tokenization (pseudonymization), depending on your need :

Masking: masking secure data by replacing values with realistic yet fictitious data. Seven out-of-the-box algorithm frameworks are provided to ease the definition of tailored precise algorithms, which can mask everything from names to social security numbers to images and plain, structured text.

Before Masking	After Masking
Elon Musk	Jeff Bezos

Figure 1.30: masking example [8]

Tokenisation: contrarily, tokenisation employs reversible algorithms so that data can be returned to its original state. Tokenisation is a form of encryption where the actual original data is converted into tokens that do not convey any meaning.

Before Tokenizing	After Tokenizing
226-74-3756	asdfkajsfdaja

Figure 1.31: tokenisation example [8]

In addition, as introduced, two flow of data masking can be distinguished :

In-Place masking: sensitive data is secured by overwriting it directly within the original data source. Involves reading the data from its current location, applying the necessary masking algorithms within the engine,

and then updating the same source with the masked data. As a result, the original sensitive information is overwritten, ensuring that the data remains protected within its initial environment. This approach is particularly beneficial when it's essential to maintain the existing data infrastructure without creating additional copies or moving data between environments. By transforming only the columns identified as containing sensitive information, in-place masking preserves the integrity of the remaining data, ensuring that non-sensitive information remains unaltered

On-the-Fly masking: this process instead reads sensitive data from a source environment, applies masking algorithms to obfuscate the data within the Delphix engine, and then writes the masked data to a separate target environment. This approach ensures that the original data remains unaltered, while the target environment receives the anonymized data, effectively maintaining data security and compliance across environments. This ETL-like (Extract, Transform, Load) workflow ensures that sensitive information is protected before it reaches less secure environments.

Figure 1.32: masking methods [8]

The key component of data masking is indeed the algorithm. In the context of data masking an algorithm refers to a defined method or procedure applied to data fields or columns to obfuscate sensitive information, ensuring that the original data cannot be reconstructed or retrieved. Algorithms are generally implemented on the structure of algorithm frameworks : foundational structures that define the general approach to masking. Delphix provides various algorithm frameworks, each suited to different data types and masking requirements. For instance, the Secure Lookup framework maps original data to masked values using a predefined list, ensuring consistent and irreversible masking. Key features of masking algorithms are :

- Irreversibility: Delphix masking algorithms are designed to be one-way functions, ensuring that masked data cannot be reverted to its original form. This is crucial for maintaining data security and compliance.
- Consistency: Certain algorithms, such as Secure Lookup, ensure that the same input value is consistently masked to the same output value across all instances. This feature is essential for preserving referential integrity within and across datasets.
- Customization: Users can create new algorithms or modify existing ones to meet specific requirements. This flexibility allows organizations to tailor masking processes to their unique data landscapes and compliance obligations.
- Multi-Column Support: Delphix supports multi-column algorithms, enabling coordinated masking across related data fields. This ensures that complex data relationships are maintained post-masking.

Chapter 2

Project Enterprise Recovery Vault (ERV)

Within the broader context of business continuity, the client has identified the implementation of an Enterprise Recovery Vault (ERV) as a critical requirement for a set of databases classified as mission-critical. These databases are simultaneously exposed across QA, test, and analytics environments, making them highly susceptible to elevated risk factors such as data corruption, unauthorized modifications, and operational disruptions.

Enterprise Recovery Vault solution, following the speed principle previously highlighted, must guarantee a data recovery strategy that minimise data loss and downtime. Which translate in the reduction of both Recovery Point Objective(RPO) and Recovery Time Objective(RTO). The functional and business requirements outlined a RTO and RPO respectively of 30 and 10 minutes, given that the application is not critical for the organization business but the loss of new data could lead to significant damage to the business. As mentioned briefly, a peculiar characteristic of this data is that its masked version is brought to three reliability, security and performance testing containerised environments within the wider context of multiple CI/CD pipelines, where single services of a core application are dynamically tested. Data provisioning and tests execution is orchestrated by ArgoCD which pulls subsets of masked data from a virtual database and delivers it to tailored structures in target environments on a time-based schedule and trigger tests once provisioning is completed. The provisioning mechanism and test execution is orchestrated by ArgoCD, leveraging Delphix as engine to fetch data from virtual databases and Kubernetes as deployment infrastructure, it is based on multiple parameters to guarantee maximum reliability, but goes beyond the scope of this work.

In order to comprehend the risk posed to data confidentiality and integrity, it

is fundamental to understand the perimeter segmentation and the authentication methods used by all the infrastructure components involved. Delphix, besides the execution of a password-based authentication at the production database where a copy of data is retrieved, authenticates with a password based approach at the target containerised testing databases to provision this data. Meanwhile, ArgoCD jobs must initially authenticate at Delphix and databases in test environments as well as to private repository where Kubernetes manifests are stored. Credentials are stored in Delphix and ArgoCD hosts, the security of these authentication processes is accomplished with encryption at rest and in transit, wrapping connections in mTLS tunnels. All databases involved in this perimeter expose a REST API for authentication, likewise Delphix engine. In the view of the infrastructure two segments can be distinguished, the production segment where the production database is hosted, and the testing segment where reside CI/CD pipelines nodes among which a Delphix data Engine, ArgoCD and three testing containers hosted on a single system

Figure 2.1: infrastructure ArgoCD managing 3 testing kubernetes pods with a delphix provisioned VDB

Furthermore, the target application has an architecture that follows a microservice paradigm and the infrastructure is strongly bound to heterogeneous cloud-based resources. What concerns the scope of this paper is the data flow from production storage to the database that undergoes integrity control. The application leverages cloud providers managed databases both for application usage log retention and production data, the latter is provisioned on a time-based schedule to an archive database cluster, which is the object of the control.

Deepening further in the application architecture and CI/CD structure is out of the scope of this thesis, but this brief overview and the previously illustrated CI/CD threats paired with cloud security challenges set the context to understand the reasons why the client pointed out the CI/CD pipeline as main attack vector that could eventually lead through some lateral movements and privilege escalation to the production database.

Similarly, the illustration of dataOps and PDI set the base context to comprehend the solution crafted to face malicious data encryption also known as ransomware. This solution leverages the data infrastructure abstraction provided by Delphix, a data virtualization and masking software offered via SaaS; a broad overview of Delphix is depicted in the following chapter.

2.1 Architecture

The infrastructure architecture of the crafted ERV solution is represented in the below picture

Figure 2.2: ERV solution architecture

At first glance, it's clear how the infrastructure is divided in two macro sites. Source site hosting the production data center, one Delphix data engine and

a recovery database. Whereas the control site features a database whose scope is to host virtualised data, provisioned from a data engine noted as vault and checked by a compliance engine noted as discovery engine, and finally results are evaluated by the orchestration component.

These two macro sites are separated with a robust firewall. With a deny by default approach, it's configured to apply a stateful control and strictly allow only traffic necessary for data replication and control of data engine. Since communications are encrypted the analysis of packets is limited up to the control layer. An IP/TCP session parameters filtering could already be strong enough but since the separation of these two sites is critical and communication between orchestration appliance and data engine uses HTTPS, which is often leveraged by C2 malwares, packet filtering is extended with detection of known malicious signatures and certificates, malicious encrypted payload patterns recognition, weak cipher suites, malicious SNI, self-signed or not trusted CA certificates during TLS handshake, finally there are some native behavioural based anomalies detection like packets frequency, size, replay. This firewall component is fundamental for attack detection, if the attacker is able to move laterally to the control site and access the orchestration component it could impair the control evaluation and inhibit discrepancies detection.

All the appliances are deployed on Azure cloud infrastructure, including Delphix engines and orchestration unit as well as all databases. Even though this aspect should't be overlooked, the solution transcend from underlying cloud provider, since it is technology agnostic and none of the native feature of Azure are really leveraged. Besides, the just mentioned firewalling solution, implemented with Azure native managed firewall, nevertheless its characteristics are replicable in any other cloud provider native firewall solution. When it comes to database technologies, on both database servers Oracle c19 database are deployed. Both databases are multi-tenant type with a container database model(CDB) which allows multiple full databases tenants within the same instance, also called Pluggable Databases(PDB).

The network topology diagram point out three different type of communications :

Data replication: these communications concern the provisioning of virtualised data to all required target environments. Virtualisation of production data, and its replication to a data engine in control site, testing environment and a fast recovery database and back-up data center

Ransomware DR: communications closely related to ransomware attack detection and response measures. Data integrity control, control results

evaluation, email alert notification, mounting of fast recovery database in production.

Engines orchestration: coordination of the flow of mission-critical data, controls execution and attack response. Besides triggering these actions, it monitors their execution to proceed to the next one

Overall, two different execution scenarios can be distinguished according to the control result :

- Amount of discrepancies revealed under a custom predefined threshold:
 1. Delphix data engine retrieve mission-critical data from the production database with a continuous synchronisation process called snapSync. This process besides copying the data to the host disks, compromise it to circa one third of its original dimension, with a virtualisation. One of data engines peculiar characteristic is the incremental approach to retrieval, also known as Change Data Capture(CDC), whereby it retrieves only changes to data on a scheduled frequency. This frequency is critical since it directly impact data loss and potential downtime during an attack, therefore to comply with formerly mentioned RTO and RPO, data engine has been configured to retrieve changes with 5 minutes interval. This interval has been identified, following an empirical evaluation, as a good trade-off between requirements compliance and overhead added to production
 2. Delphix data engine tagged as Vault replicate virtualised data to another data engine in the control site, which acts as vault. An identical copy of virtualised data, also called dSource in Delphix context, is recreated on the target engine. This process also establish a relationship between these two objects on different engines, which ensure that if the data snapshot is cancelled on the source it is cancelled also on the target,, therefore guaranteeing complete data disruption once infected data is discovered.
 3. Vault engine use the received virtualised data to provision a virtual database, contained in a database hosted on a purposefully created server. Virtual databases main perk, is that they are by fact fully functional copies of data sources that can be created and managed at a fraction of the storage and time that are typically required. To end-users, VDBs act and perform just like a standard database.

4. Delphix compliance engine labelled as Discovery, whose main functionality is to mask sensible data according to native or custom algorithms, execute a masking operation with a custom purposefully-built algorithm. This algorithm, instead of masking data, column by column cluster each cell with identical value, extract these clusters size, indexing them with a machine-friendly structure and insert them in a result table. This job leverages delphix intellectual property of data masking to parse data.
5. Orchestration unit matches results against expected values. Expected values are in a set of view tables, which are the outcome of a data elaboration algorithm embedded in the database and triggered on demand always by the orchestration unit after the previous control. Control mechanism is distilled more thoroughly in the following chapter
6. If the result control does not detect discrepancies, or a number of discrepancies lower than the predefined threshold, data is considered clean. Hence, data engine in source site is triggered to provision a fast recovery database with the latest virtualised data snapshot which has just been checked.

Figure 2.3: scenario discrepancies under alert threshold

- Amount of discrepancies revealed over a custom predefined threshold: Obviously up to the fifth step, execution is identical to the previous scenario
 1. If the result control detects a number of discrepancies higher than the predefined threshold, data is considered poisoned and a ransomware attack is ongoing or data could already be totally encrypted. The orchestration unit alert all defined stakeholders through email by default and if pre-configured by call or sms. Additionally it is connected with azure SIEM Microsoft Sentinel and raise an alert in the dashboard as well.
 2. The incident response team monitoring 24/7 the infrastructure or whoever is in charge to deal with potential attacks, should manually check the attachment received in the email and further evaluate the described discrepancies to decide if it's necessary to mount in production the fast recovery database properly provisioned with clean data copies in the previous control. In case it has been encrypted as well, Delphix data engine can provision again the latest clean data snapshot. If the data engine has been corrupted as well, vault engine in the control site, can replicate the latest clean data snapshot to the data engine in the source site.

Figure 2.4: scenario discrepancies over alert threshold

Further data flows depicted in the network topology are :

- Virtualised data replication to a data&compliance engine, which then provision the aforementioned testing environments within the CI/CD pipelines context. This replication is scheduled and combined aptly with the replication to the control site, in order not to obstruct each other.
- Provisioning of back-up database. A further copy of data is stored in a purposefully built datacenter, in order to enforce even more business resiliency. This provisioning is scheduled similarly to replication to testing segment, but with a weekly schedule. Following this provisions, virtualised data snapshots older than a week are erased from data engine in source and therefore due to synchronisation in the control site, to avoid server overload.

On a side note, the back-up strategy, even though out of the Enterprise Recovery Vault project scope, plays a vital role in the attack impact containment and therefore business resiliency, as illustrated formerly in ransomware chapter. The definition and implementation of this strategy was another project within the broader context of client's business continuity. Since they are inter-operational, the back-up strategy has been influenced by the ERV solution and vice versa. The strategy fol-

lows a 3-2-1-1-0 model. This mode is designed to ensure wide technology and location distribution. Add an air-gapped copy geographically located far from on-site archives, to ensure natural disaster resilience. Air-gap employs that the copy is stored offline, of any network, and if possible not loaded on any device. Here is a breakdown of the model approach :

- Three total copies of data, including one primary in production database.
- Two different storage medium, since the production storage server have a RDBMS, one of the backup copies is stored on a back-up optimized storage. Both actually have a disk as physical medium(SSD, HD) but data is structured differently.
- One must stay off on-premise site, this is already achieved with production database
- One offline and immutable, one of the copies is stored on WORM (Write Once Read Many) disks and it is properly managed by back-up managers to provision data manually, stay offline and far from on-premises site.
- Zero guarantees zero errors, all copies are continuously verified on a monthly frequency. Integrity verification includes hash check and constant lightweight snapshots

Figure 2.5: testing environments and back-up provisioning

2.2 Data Integrity Control Mechanism

Certainly, the core part of this data poisoning detection system is the actual control of the data itself. As depicted previously, once data is provisioned to the virtual database in the control site, the orchestration unit triggers the discovery engine to discover the values assumed by the data, and then it matches this data clustering results with expected values. In this chapter, an overview of the mechanism is depicted, deepening in involved tables and their characteristics.

Before illustrating the mechanism, without deepening in the entity of data, knowing some of its core characteristics could help the comprehension. It comes from final customers, from few customer-facing applications with different purposes, thus it is heterogeneous but there shouldn't be characters with diacritical marks or anyway belonging to Indo-European languages family; and data once written should change rarely, so it is suitable for this kind of integrity control. Assured this, discrepancies threshold can be changed arbitrary.

This mechanism leverages one native functionality of all database technologies, system catalog views. Views are ultimately queries stored in the database on material tables or other views. Two kinds of views can be distinguished, standard and materialised, the latter effectively persist and data is stored on

disks but it needs to be refreshed on demand to show updates from the underlying tables. Whereas catalogs, which are by fact static views, constitute a central repository that stores metadata about a database, acting as data dictionary, including tenants, tables, views, users, constraints, triggers and other objects, the core view, where all required data to execute the control is gathered, used in this mechanism within the virtual database are of this type.

On the discovery engine, a pre-configured job is loaded to perform a data masking on the provisioned virtual database according to a custom algorithm. This algorithm does not mask data, but queries it to extract each single value occurrences at a column level. Queries target are based on an aptly created table data, where columns interested of control are listed with indication of database tenant, table and column ID, this allows the client to exclude not critical columns from the control, the paper dives deeper in the algorithm in a dedicated chapter. These clustering results are written in the same aptly created table with a json format, in their corresponding column row. These columns are indexed by database, table and column ID retrieved from each object catalog, each row has an ID that will play a key role in the results evaluation and finally a timestamp of the execution is also reported. This table isn't provisioned from the source site, but native to this virtual database, so interested columns indexing can be inserted manually.

ID	DATABASE_ID	TABLE_ID	COLUMN_ID	RESULT	TIMESTAMP
1	10133	624	1122	5606 {"DONGO": "1", "FIUMICINO": "1", "ROMA": "1", "MILANO": "1"}	25-SET-24 12:56:54,717000000
2	10134	624	1122	5607 {"ROSSI": "1", "GOBBETTI": "2"}	25-SET-24 12:56:54,933000000
3	10135	624	1122	5608 {"COMO": "2"}	25-SET-24 12:56:55,105000000
4	10136	624	1122	5609 (null)	(null)
5	10137	624	1122	5610 {"FABIO": "2", "MARTINA": "1"}	25-SET-24 12:56:55,418000000

Figure 2.6: CHECK2 - data clustering results table

Likewise, the table reporting expected values is native to the control database, but values are populated automatically with specifically crafted SQL procedural code(PL/SQL). Executed on demand by the orchestration appliance, following a clean data detection. The expected results table exposes a column referred to the ID column of results table(that plays a crucial role in the control results evaluation), a value column which reports all distinct values in the column indexed by the database, table and column ID corresponding to the ID of the results table referenced and finally a column with occurrences of corresponding value, which by fact are expected results.

```

CHECK_2
Columns | Data | Model | Constraints | Grants | Statistics | Triggers | Flashback | Dependencies | Details | Partitions | Indexes | SQL
▼ Actions...
CREATE TABLE "C##CONTROL_USER"."CHECK_2"
(
  "ID" NUMBER(11,0) GENERATED BY DEFAULT ON NULL AS IDENTITY MINVALUE 1 MAXVALUE 9999999999 INCREMENT BY 1 START WITH 1 CACHE 20 NOORDER NOCYCLE NOKEEP NOSCALE NOT NULL ENABLE,
  "DATABASE_ID" NUMBER(1,0) NOT NULL ENABLE,
  "TABLE_ID" NUMBER(11,0) NOT NULL ENABLE,
  "COLUMN_ID" NUMBER(11,0) NOT NULL ENABLE,
  "RESULT" CLOB,
  "TIMESTAMP" TIMESTAMP (6) WITH TIME ZONE,
  PRIMARY KEY ("ID")
)
USING INDEX PCTFREE 10 INITRANS 2 MAXTRANS 255 COMPUTE STATISTICS
STORAGE(INITIAL 65536 NEXT 1048576 MINEXTENTS 1 MAXEXTENTS 2147483645
PCTINCRAS 0 FREELISTS 1 FREELIST GROUPS 1
BUFFER_POOL DEFAULT FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT CELL_FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT)
TABLESPACE "USERS" ENABLE,
CONSTRAINT "CHECK_DATABASE_TABLE_COL_UNIQUE_T" UNIQUE ("DATABASE_ID", "TABLE_ID", "COLUMN_ID")
USING INDEX PCTFREE 10 INITRANS 2 MAXTRANS 255 COMPUTE STATISTICS
STORAGE(INITIAL 65536 NEXT 1048576 MINEXTENTS 1 MAXEXTENTS 2147483645
PCTINCRAS 0 FREELISTS 1 FREELIST GROUPS 1
BUFFER_POOL DEFAULT FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT CELL_FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT)
TABLESPACE "USERS" ENABLE,
CONSTRAINT "CHECK_DATABASE_TABLE_PK_T" FOREIGN KEY ("DATABASE_ID")
REFERENCES "C##CONTROL_USER"."DATABASES" ("ID") DEFERRABLE INITIALLY DEFERRED ENABLE,
CONSTRAINT "CHECK_TABLE_COLUMN_FK" FOREIGN KEY ("TABLE_ID")
REFERENCES "C##CONTROL_USER"."TABLES" ("ID") DEFERRABLE INITIALLY DEFERRED ENABLE,
CONSTRAINT "CHECK_COLUMN_REF_FK" FOREIGN KEY ("COLUMN_ID")
REFERENCES "C##CONTROL_USER"."COLUMNS" ("ID") DEFERRABLE INITIALLY DEFERRED ENABLE
)
SEGMENT CREATION IMMEDIATE
PCTFREE 10 PCTUSRD 40 INITRANS 1 MAXTRANS 255
NOCOMPRESS LOGGING
STORAGE(INITIAL 65536 NEXT 1048576 MINEXTENTS 1 MAXEXTENTS 2147483645
PCTINCRAS 0 FREELISTS 1 FREELIST GROUPS 1
BUFFER_POOL DEFAULT FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT CELL_FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT)
TABLESPACE "USERS"
LOB ("RESULT") STORE AS SECUREFILE (
TABLESPACE "USERS" ENABLE STORAGE IN ROW CHUNK 8192
NOCACHE LOGGING NOCOMPRESS KEEP DUPLICATES
STORAGE(INITIAL 106496 NEXT 1048576 MINEXTENTS 1 MAXEXTENTS 2147483645
PCTINCRAS 0
BUFFER_POOL DEFAULT FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT CELL_FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT) );

```

Figure 2.7: results table DDL code

ID	CHECK_ID	VALUE	RES_EXPECTED
1	1	1 Diego	1
2	2	1 Fabio	1
3	3	1 Martina	2
4	5	2 Como	6
5	6	2 Milano	14

Figure 2.8: CHECKBASE - expected values table

Once data clustering results are elaborated and all rows in the results table are populated. The orchestration appliance proceed to evaluate the results. The evaluation of results involves a query that parse results, written in json format, and builds an ephemeral data structure specular to the expected results table(CHECK_BASE). Below an example table called for reference CHECK_RESULTS.

This data structure and CHECK_BASE are confronted based on its ID and CHECK_BASE check_id and both tables values(in the example table “chi-avi”), this ensures the correct matching of values across all column of all tables. The result of this comparison is a list of values with discrepant occurrences, actual from expected. This list size is checked against the threshold and accordingly to the check result the data snapshot is saved as golden copy


```

    count NUMBER
);

```

Whereas, the table type definition enables the processing of a collection of values with a given record type. In this settings, the record type is the one previously defined, therefore it allows the wrapper procedure to process a list of triple with values of type NUMBER, VARCHAR2 AND NUMBER.

```

CREATE OR REPLACE TYPE CheckBaseTableType AS TABLE OF CheckBaseRecType;

```

The core procedure (update_check_base) takes as input the mentioned triple of values which are respectively : id of the results table, value and its occurrences. Then a number variable defined to hold current expected occurrences of the current interested value in the table. The procedure implements a logic that basically checks if current and retrieved occurrences are the same, in such case it ends, otherwise checks if effectively only the occurrence is changed or the value or column are new, in the former case the corresponding row is identified and occurrences updated; in the latter a new row is created and populated with input parameters.

```

CREATE OR REPLACE PROCEDURE update_check_base (
    p_check_base_data IN CheckBaseTableType
)
IS
    CREATE GLOBAL TEMPORARY TABLE processed_check_base (
        check_id NUMBER,
        val VARCHAR2(4000)
    ) ON COMMIT PRESERVE ROWS;

BEGIN
    FOR i IN 1..p_check_base_data.COUNT LOOP
        MERGE INTO check_base tgt
        USING (
            SELECT p_check_base_data(i).check_id AS check_id,
                p_check_base_data(i).val AS val,
                p_check_base_data(i).count AS count FROM dual
        ) src
        ON (tgt.CHECK_ID = src.check_id AND tgt.VALUE = src.val)
        WHEN MATCHED THEN
            UPDATE SET tgt.RES_EXPECTED = src.count
    
```

```

    WHEN NOT MATCHED THEN
        INSERT (CHECK_ID, VALUE, RES_EXPECTED)
            VALUES (src.check_id, src.val, src.count);
        INSERT INTO processed_check_base (check_id, val)
            VALUES (p_check_base_data(i).check_id, p_check_base_data(i).val);
END LOOP;

COMMIT;

DELETE FROM check_base
WHERE NOT EXISTS (
    SELECT 1
    FROM processed_check_base
    WHERE check_base.CHECK_ID = processed_check_base.check_id AND
        check_base.VALUE = processed_check_base.val
);

COMMIT;

DROP TABLE processed_check_base;

END;

```

The retrieval of the current values occurrences which are the input to the procedure that updates expected results is realised with a combination of queries that will be illustrated in a dedicated chapter. For the sake of this chapter comprehension, first the results table is queried to obtain target columns, then such columns are queried in a loop. For each column, a list of distinct values and their occurrences are extracted, this pair of columns are joined with results table ID that index the corresponding values column. These queries leverages the whole database container(CDB) catalogs to index columns where values must be retrieved. Such CDB catalogs are a fundamental objects for the control mechanism. They are specifically built to facilitate the indexing in the CDB structure : Databases, Tables and Columns catalog tables abstract the complexities of underlying system views. In addition, a catalog view built upon these catalogs and the results table is defined to ease even further the control visibility.

Following a clean data evaluation, likewise CHECK_2 and CHECK_BASE, these catalog tables are refreshed on demand by the orchestration appliance to fetch potential new columns, tables and databases. In the following images, catalogs and relative DDL for tables definition and DML for data

update SQL code is depicted.

In the database catalog, all pluggable database tenants in the container are listed, with their system name and an ID that replicates the connection ID. Data is retrieved from the system view `cdb_pdb$seeds`, `connection_id` is used as ID since it is a unique number for each database instance and it's selection is always required when querying these system views. Only active connection are selected and the whole container database reference(ORCL) is hardcoded as it doesn't appear in `cdb_pdb$seeds`.

ID	DB_NAME
1	3 DGP
2	2 PDB\$SEED
3	1 ORCL

Figure 2.11: Databases catalogue example


```

CREATE TABLE "C##CONTROL_USER"."DATABASES"
(
  "ID" NUMBER(10,0),
  "DB_NAME" VARCHAR2(128 BYTE) NOT NULL ENABLE,
  PRIMARY KEY ("ID")
  USING INDEX PCTFREE 10 INITRANS 2 MAXTRANS 255 COMPUTE STATISTICS
  STORAGE(INITIAL 65536 NEXT 1048576 MINEXTENTS 1 MAXEXTENTS 2147483645
  PCTINCREASE 0 FREELISTS 1 FREELIST GROUPS 1
  BUFFER_POOL DEFAULT FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT CELL_FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT)
  TABLESPACE "USERS"  ENABLE
) SEGMENT CREATION IMMEDIATE
PCTFREE 10 PCTUSED 40 INITRANS 1 MAXTRANS 255
NOCOMPRESS LOGGING
STORAGE(INITIAL 65536 NEXT 1048576 MINEXTENTS 1 MAXEXTENTS 2147483645
PCTINCREASE 0 FREELISTS 1 FREELIST GROUPS 1
BUFFER_POOL DEFAULT FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT CELL_FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT)
TABLESPACE "USERS" ;

```

Figure 2.12: Databases catalogue table DDL code

```

INSERT INTO c##control_user.databases (ID, DB_NAME)
SELECT con_id, pdb_name
FROM cdb_pdb$seeds
WHERE status = 'NORMAL'
UNION ALL
SELECT 1, 'ORCL' FROM dual;

CREATE OR REPLACE PROCEDURE update_databases_catalog
IS
BEGIN
  MERGE INTO c##control_user.databases tgt
  USING (
    SELECT con_id, pdb_name
    FROM cdb_pdb$seeds
    WHERE status = 'NORMAL'
  ) src
  ON (tgt.DB_NAME = src.pdb_name)
  WHEN NOT MATCHED BY TARGET THEN -- in current values not in catalog
  INSERT (ID, DB_NAME) VALUES (src.con_id, src.pdb_name)

```



```

WHEN MATCHED THEN
    NULL
WHEN NOT MATCHED BY SOURCE THEN
    DELETE;
COMMIT;

```

Columns catalog exposes column name and relative table id from tables catalog. Data is therefore retrieved from the combination of tables catalog and system view `cdb_tab_columns` joined on tables schema and name. Reported tables aren't in system table spaces.

ID	COLUMN_NAME	TB_ID
94	DOC_NAME	62
95	DOC_TYPE_ID	62
96	ORACLE_INS...	62
97	CREATE_DATE	62
98	DOC_CONTENT	62
99	99_SI_FEATURE...	2
100	100_PID	37
101	101_POS	37
102	102_OPERAND	37
103	103_PSID	39
104	104_PARNAME	39
105	105_DOC_NAME	48
106	106_TABLE_NAME	48

Figure 2.15: Columns catalogue example

```

CREATE TABLE "C##CONTROL_USER"."COLUMNS"
(
  "ID" NUMBER(10,0) GENERATED BY DEFAULT AS IDENTITY MINVALUE 1 MAXVALUE 9999999999 INCREMENT BY 1 START WITH 1 CACHE 20 NOORDER NOCYCLE NOKEEP NOLOCAL NOT NULL ENABLE,
  "COLUMN_NAME" VARCHAR2(128 BYTE) NOT NULL ENABLE,
  "TB_ID" NUMBER(10,0) NOT NULL ENABLE,
  PRIMARY KEY ("ID")
) NOLOGGING NOCOMPRESS LOGGING
STORAGE(INITIAL 65536 NEXT 1048576 MINEXTENTS 1 MAXEXTENTS 2147483645
PCTINCREASE 0 FREELISTS 1 FREELIST GROUPS 1
BUFFER_POOL DEFAULT FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT CELL_FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT)
TABLESPACE "USERS" ENABLE
REFERENCES "C##CONTROL_USER"."TABLES" ("ID") ON DELETE CASCADE ENABLE
) NOLOGGING NOCOMPRESS LOGGING
STORAGE(INITIAL 65536 NEXT 1048576 MINEXTENTS 1 MAXEXTENTS 2147483645
PCTINCREASE 0 FREELISTS 1 FREELIST GROUPS 1
BUFFER_POOL DEFAULT FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT CELL_FLASH_CACHE DEFAULT)
TABLESPACE "USERS" ;

```

Figure 2.16: Columns catalogue table DDL code

```

INSERT INTO c##control_user.columns (COLUMN_NAME, TB_ID)
SELECT c.column_name, t.ID
FROM cdb_tab_columns c
JOIN c##control_user.tables t
    ON c.owner = t.TABLE_SCHEMA AND c.table_name = t.TABLE_NAME;

```

```

CREATE OR REPLACE PROCEDURE update_columns_catalog
IS
BEGIN
    MERGE INTO c##control_user.columns tgt
    USING (
        SELECT c.column_name, t.ID
        FROM cdb_tab_columns c
        JOIN c##control_user.tables t ON c.owner = t.TABLE_SCHEMA
        AND c.table_name = t.TABLE_NAME ) src
    ON (tgt.COLUMN_NAME = src.column_name AND tgt.TB_ID = src.ID)
    WHEN NOT MATCHED BY TARGET THEN
        INSERT (COLUMN_NAME, TB_ID) VALUES (src.column_name, src.ID)

```

```

WHEN MATCHED
  NULL
WHEN NOT MATCHED BY SOURCE THEN
  DELETE;
COMMIT;
END;

```

For all these catalogs, the procedure requires them to be populated initially with a standard insert query and in consequent control cycles data will be refreshed by a stored procedure that leverages the combination of the clauses MERGE INTO and WHEN NOT MATCHED. All procedures share the same executive template, current and newly retrieved data is matched against database name for databases, tables schema and names for tables and column name and table id for columns. Whenever there is match on both sides the entry remains the same, whereas all rows with only the current retrieved values result in an insertion in the catalog, on the opposite rows where only data from the catalog appear are deleted.

Upon these catalogs is defined a master view, that joins the catalogs and expand them with more intelligible information like actual databases, tables and columns name that will be retrieved from discovery engine and orchestration appliance to build queries strings dynamically. It is built upon results table(CHECK_2) so only columns interested of control are reported. Underlying catalogs are never actually queried, but their value is abstracted in this view

```

CREATE OR REPLACE FORCE EDITIONABLE VIEW "C##CONTROL_USER"."CHECK_VIEW_2"
("ID", "DB_ID", "DB_NAME", "TABLE_ID", "TABLE_NAME", "COLUMN_ID",
"COLUMN_NAME", "DATATYPE", "ALGO_NAME", "RESULT", "TIMESTAMP") AS
SELECT
  c.id,
  d.id           AS "DB_ID",
  d.dbname      AS "DB_NAME",
  t.id          AS "TABLE_ID",
  t.name        AS "TABLE_NAME",
  clmn.id       AS "COLUMN_ID",
  clmn.column_name AS "COLUMN_NAME",
  c.result,
  c.timestamp
FROM
  "C##CONTROL_USER"."CHECK_2"      c,
  "C##CONTROL_USER"."DATABASES"   d,

```

```

"C##CONTROL_USER"."TABLES"      t,
"C##CONTROL_USER"."COLUMNS"    clmn,
"C##CONTROL_USER"."CHECK_ALGO"  ca
WHERE
  c.database_id = d.id
  AND c.table_id = t.id
  AND d.id = t.database_id
  AND t.id = clmn.table_id

```

ID	DB_ID	DB_NAME	TABLE_ID	TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_ID	COLUMN_NAME	RESULT	TIMESTAMP
1	1	ORCL	13	REGIONS	671	REGION_ID	(null)	(null)
2	2	ORCL	13	REGIONS	671	REGION_ID	(null)	(null)
3	1	ORCL	13	REGIONS	672	REGION_NAME	(null)	(null)
4	2	ORCL	13	REGIONS	672	REGION_NAME	(null)	(null)
5	3	ORCL	14	LOCATIONS	743	LOCATION_ID	(null)	(null)
6	4	ORCL	14	LOCATIONS	743	LOCATION_ID	(null)	(null)
7	5	ORCL	14	LOCATIONS	743	LOCATION_ID	(null)	(null)
8	6	ORCL	14	LOCATIONS	743	LOCATION_ID	(null)	(null)
9	7	ORCL	14	LOCATIONS	743	LOCATION_ID	(null)	(null)
10	8	ORCL	14	LOCATIONS	743	LOCATION_ID	(null)	(null)
11	3	ORCL	14	LOCATIONS	744	STREET_ADDRESS	(null)	(null)
12	4	ORCL	14	LOCATIONS	744	STREET_ADDRESS	(null)	(null)

Figure 2.17: Master view

Delphix and orchestration appliance users are specifically configured to guarantee LPP. Their permissions are restricted solely to the operations they are intended to execute, strictly on the target instances, tables spaces and single tables. In the design phase, it was decided to not apply a role-based approach to permissions control, since there are only two users the applications are executing operations on behalf and in any potential scaled scenarios users should be always two. Furthermore, this purely grant-based approach allowed a fine-grained object access, guaranteeing lowest privilege principle to its maximum extent, which was indeed difficult with a role-based approach given the complexities of the multi-tenant database architecture : multiple databases tenants, inner table spaces and table schemas. Hence, we can identify two application users : “c##delphix” and “c##control_user”, both are by default common oracle database users with CDB wide administration scoping and centralised management, but initially they don’t have any read/write permissions. The former, as the name suggests, is the user that both vault and discovery engine act on behalf, its write(i.e. INSERT, UPDATE, ALTER) permissions regard all tables within the not-system table spaces(exclusion of

table spaces in tables catalog definition) of all databases tenants, excluding the database container, besides on table : results table(CHECK_2) where discovery engine data clustering extraction results must be written. These permissions are granted to allow vault engine to refresh the virtual database with new data provisioned from the source site and the discovery engine to write in the results table. Likewise its read permissions(i.e. SELECT) span on all tables across all table spaces, and additionally it can select on aforementioned catalog tables and view in the container database scope. This is configured to allow the discovery engine to read actual values from all tables interested of control.

As stated briefly, such catalog tables as well as results and expected values tables are excluded from provisioning, hence they aren't overwritten by vault engine refresh operation. They reside on the container database scope under a specifically crafted tables space whose owner is the user that the orchestration appliance uses to execute operations. Vault engine is configured to exclude the container database scope from provisioning.

Finally, I would like to clear out the reasons why the client had the necessity to perform a full database comparison instead of just an hash-based verification. Hash-based verification, while it has some major perks such as begin fast($O(1)$) since digest length transcend from data size, therefore being efficient for large size files; or guaranteeing cryptographic security as even single-bit change in the file result in a completely different hash; it comes with some drawbacks : the main one is the inability to detect minimal or partial changes, and a critical aspect not to be overlooked is that a savvy attacker may manipulate the hash which result in an hash collision. In this specific case, since data is highly heterogeneous and it is submitted by end users, it is highly subject to misinterpretation and mismatch with expected values, hence hashed will often be different causing false positives. Furthermore, the native features of full database comparison strategy allows data versioning control, which enables rollback to previous versions and in depth forensic analysis, a fundamental request of the project.

2.3 Delphix Engines' Key Role in ERV Solution

It's needless to say that each engine is a critical component in the infrastructure of the solution. In the solution architecture chapter the conceptual and logical function that each engine serve has already been illustrated, in this chapter most of the technical details of all processes related to Delphix

engines that appear in the solution will be covered, including deployment choices adopted to guarantee the highest possible security.

Delphix Session Protocol(DSP)

One of the most technical peculiar characteristics of Delphix engines is their proprietary protocol used at the Session and Presentation layer in network communication. The Delphix Session Protocol (DSP) is a proprietary communication protocol developed by Delphix and facilitates efficient and secure data exchange between Delphix Engines and associated services. DSP operates over TCP port 8415, officially registered under the service name "dlpx-sp" with the Internet Assigned Numbers Authority (IANA).

DSP supports the request-reply pattern for communication between two networked peers. In contrast to the traditional remote procedure call (RPC) models, which focus exclusively on low-level details such as data encoding and wireframing, DSP implements a generic session layer that supports a number of advanced functionalities desired for network communication, including :

- Full-duplex remote operation execution and end-to-end cancellation support
- Advanced connectivity model with connection trunking and ordered delivery
- Fault resilience with automatic connection and session recovery, exactly-once semantics, and optional data digest
- High performance with concurrent execution, session flow control, optional data compression, and bandwidth throttling
- Built-in security support with pluggable SASL authentication mechanisms and optional TLS encryption
- Asynchronous model for session management and remote operation
- Supports Java language binding and provides a java based service framework for distributed applications.

DSP is a robust communication protocol under all non-functional fundamental aspects of a network protocol including :

Security: DSP is designed with security in mind from the onset. DSP guarantees strong authentication and encryption between parties :

Application Layer	application specific logic
Presentation Layer	data encoding, digest, compression, encryption
Session Layer	connection management, error recovery, security, remote operation
Transport Layer	end-to-end connection, message segmentation, sequencing, reliability, flow control
Network Layer	packet fragmentation, routing, logical addressing
Data Link Layer	physical addressing
Physical Layer	media, signal, binary transmission

Figure 2.18: DSP featuring in ISO/OSI stack session and presentation layers [8]

- **Authentication** : employs the Simple Authentication and Security Layer (SASL) framework for authentication, a session-based authentication model that supports mechanisms such as DIGEST-MD5, PLAIN with TLS, CRAM, and ANONYMOUS. Each connection must authenticate before joining a session
- **Encryption** : DSP supports data encryption to ensure privacy. Optionally, Transport Layer Security (TLS) can be negotiated between the client and server for data encryption.

Performance: high performance network applications are supported through multiple features, including :

- **Simultaneous Bidirectional Requests:** multiple requests can be exchanged in both directions simultaneously; while maintaining effective pipelining of data transfer, minimizing the impact of network latency and ensuring total ordering.
- **Trunking Support:** allows trunking, which effectively aggregates throughput across multiple connections. Crucial for long fat networks (LFN) and 10GigE environments.

- **Optional Compression Support:** provides optional compression to enhance performance over bandwidth-limited networks.

Fault and transition Resiliency : DSP automatically recovers from transient connection loss without any application involvement. It may also detect random data corruption on the wire and automatically recovers from it. In both cases, outstanding requests are retried once the fault condition is resolved. In the rare event of a session loss, a new session creation request will be held until the old session has been reinstated. It ensures that we never leave any unknown or unwanted activities on the remote side and provides better predictability and consistency guarantees over an otherwise unreliable network

Diagnosability: application exceptions encountered during remote execution of a request are communicated back to the initiator through DSP. A standard Java API is used to facilitate the handling of remote exceptions that is in many ways identical to local ones. DSP provides detailed information and statistics at the session level. The information may be used to examine the state of the session as well as diagnose performance problems. It is currently exposed via an internal support tool called the JMX tool.

Overall, Delphix Session Protocol (DSP) can be considered a foundational element that enables Delphix to function as a Programmable Data Infrastructure (PDI), therefore by fact being a priming feature of the Data Platform.

Data Replication

One of the core connections relying heavily on DSP is the replication connection between the data engine in the source site and the vault engine in the control site. DSP is the key enabler of a secure and efficient data transfer. Replication is therefore based on a request-reply communication model, with initial authentication and handshake between peers to ensure legitimacy and tunnelling, while session management and monitoring is integrated with DSP features.

The communication flow involves :

1. Session Establishment:
 - (a) Connection initiation: The source engine initiates a connection to the target engine over TCP port 8415. This port must be open and accessible on both engines to facilitate DSP communication.
 - (b) Authentication: Upon connection, the source engine authenticates using credentials specified in the replication profile. This ensures

that only authorized engines can participate in replication activities.

- (c) DSP Handshake: Following successful authentication, a DSP handshake establishes a secure session, enabling full-duplex communication between the engines.

2. Data Transfer Process:

- (a) Initial Synchronization: the initial transfer request warns the receiver about the initiation of a data transfer. If the target engine accepts the transfer, it replies with an acknowledgment and prepares to receive data. The full dataset is transmitted, in a number of frames that varies based on transfer size. Resources binding between source and target engines is based on replication profiles, specular between each other.
- (b) Incremental Updates: following transfers include solely the changed or new data blocks, optimising bandwidth usage. Authentication and DSP handshake in most of the cases are performed again, if the interval from the latest transfer is short is avoided as DSP support session resumption by ticketing.

3. Session Management and Monitoring: DSP employs a heartbeat mechanism to monitor the health of the connection. Regular heartbeat messages are exchanged to detect and address any connectivity issues promptly.

4. Session Termination : once data transfer is complete, the source engine sends a completion message. The target engine acknowledges, and both engines gracefully terminate the session, ensuring all resources are appropriately released.

Besides replication communications, DSP is also present in the network packets stack of many communications to source and target environments. DSP communication with other environments is permitted through specific binaries installed in the environments and a daemon that listens for DSP based connections in most cases, or otherwise in rare cases the environment's socket is configured to recognise DSP by the port and protocol binding and start the script that handles requests on-demand. Hence, following gaining access to an environment with SSH key authentication or service accounts, delphix installs in a dedicated directory all utilities and modules required for communicating with the environment through its intended means(e.g. `/var/opt/delphix/toolkit/`). The Delphix toolkit is a suite of scripts and utilities that

facilitate seamless communication between the Delphix Continuous Data Engine and remote environments. It plays a pivotal role in operations such as Virtual Database (VDB) management, data synchronization, and compliance enforcement. Its key components include :

- DBMS related scripts : automate tasks related to database provisioning, refresh, and management.
- Delphix Session Protocol (DSP) Binaries: Enable secure and efficient data transfer between the Delphix Engine and target environments.
- Delphix HostChecker: Assesses the readiness of target environments for integration with Delphix services.
- Java Development Kit (JDK): Provides necessary Java libraries and tools required by the toolkit.
- dxToolkit : A collection of Perl-based scripts that offer command-line interface (CLI) capabilities to automate and extend Delphix Engine functionalities. These scripts are designed to resemble UNIX executables, making them accessible to users without extensive programming experience.
- dxmToolkit : A set of compiled Python CLI executables aimed at automating and enhancing the Delphix Masking Engine's features via APIs.

The toolkit deployment requires a dedicated system user. His permissions should be strictly related to delphix operations, conforming to Lowest Privilege Principle(LPP).

Oracle Database Configuration

As introduced formerly, the relational databases technologies of both source and control environments are both Oracle multi-tenant c19. Technology parity has been configured to avoid any kind of data replication obstacle, like data provisioning block due to blocks size difference. In this section, many of the technical aspects involved in both databases configurations will be illustrated.

The following diagram describes the engine topology of Oracle environments. This is considered the general settings scenario, with a continuous data engine which respectively ingests and provisions a source database and target virtual database. It illustrates the recommended ports to be open from the

Figure 2.19: Oracle environment standard topology [8]

engine to remote services, to the engine, and to the Source and Target Environments.

Based on the above diagram a series of network requirements, communication protocols both at control and higher layers and therefore ports can be depicted for oracle dSources and VDBs

Outbound from the Delphix engine

Protocol	Port	Use
TCP	22	SSH connections to source and target environments
TCP	NA	s Connections to the Oracle SQL*Net Listener on the source and target oracle environments(typically to port 1521)

Table 2.1: Outbound requests port allocation

Inbound to the Delphix engine

Protocol	Port	Use
TCP/UDP	111	Remote Procedure Call(RPC) port mapper for NFSv3 mounts
TCP	1110	NFSv3 server daemon status and keep-alive(client info)
TCP/UDP	2049	NFSv3 server daemon from VDB to the Delphix engine, both v3 and v4
TCP	8341	Logsync communication data from source to the Delphix engine
TCP	8415	SnapSync control and data from source to Delphix engine
TCP	54043	NFSv3 mount daemon
TCP	54044	NFSv3 stat daemon(lock state notification service)
TCP	54045	NFSv3 lock daemon/manager
TCP	54046	Encrypted NFS connection from source and target environments

Table 2.2: Inbound requests port allocation

In this connections overview, protocols used by Delphix to interact with remote source/target environments for different scopes are pointed out :

- SSH : Delphix engines leverage SSH to connect to both source and target host
- HTTP : an inbound connection to the engine from the source environment wrapped in DSP
- NFS : likewise an inbound connection to the engine from the source environment wrapped in DSP
- SQLNet : SQL*Net (also known as Oracle Net Services), Oracle's networking component, is used to communicate with both source and target RDBMS agent

The configuration of the host and database component themselves are pretty straightforward, as default oracle deployment integrates seamlessly with Delphix engine base settings. The most demanding aspect of the oracle environment configuration is the set up of correct permissions of Delphix engine specific user. Delphix requires specific file permissions, OS group memberships, and system configurations to properly discover, manage, and provision Oracle databases. In order to achieve these capacities, the Delphix user, labelled as 'delphix_os' here for simplicity, needs :

- Auto-Discovery : reading access to system inventory files, including '/etc/oratab' or '/var/opt/oracle/oratab' ; '/etc/orainst.loc' or '/var/opt/oracle/orainst.loc' and oracle specific inventory (inventory.xml). As well as, sudo access to 'ps' utility or any other process discovery utility
- Source Host : a specifically created \$ORACLE_HOME env variable must be set to the instance startup path and delphix_os user must have execute permissions on all binaries in \$ORACLE_HOME/bin, which requires also to set the PermitUserEnvironment parameter to True in ssh config(ssh_config)
- Target Host : suggested requirements involve adding delphix_os as a member of SYSDBA OS group, which grants to members of the group direct access to oracle instance bypassing credential authentication. Whereas in the solution scenario, to guarantee better fault resilience, a more secure approach was adopted by just granting the Delphix user(c##delphix) connection, session, read and write permissions to specific table spaces. Likewise at the system level, NFS related

permissions were granted, like the /mnt/provision/ directory must be owned by the user with all files with permissions 0770 (rwxrwx—). Next, specific utilities execution permissions were granted, including : mount, umount, mkdir, rmdir and ps. Regarding sudo privileges, it is required to specify the NOPASSWD qualifier within the "sudo" configuration file, in order to ensure that no password is demand on super-user assumption.

All outlined file paths, utilities and any other system objects are part of linux-based systems, which are the hosts used in the solution over Azure infrastructure.

Starting with ingestion, ingestion is the important process by which a consistent, ready-to-run copy of the data is prepared and captured, and persisted as a Delphix snapshot in Delphix storage, so that it can be provisioned to virtual copies as Delphix vDB(s). Before beginning, it's important to understand the recommended ways to ingest. There are two architectural models by which Delphix performs ingestion in Oracle databases and any other technology : direct Ingestion and staging push ingestion. The former is the approach preferred for our solution so only that will be covered.

Direct ingestion is an approach where the Delphix Continuous Data Engine is able to extract (directly from the true production source) the necessary information to reconstruct the source database and persist it into storage on the Delphix Continuous Data Engine. This direct methodology requires no intermediate host nor instance of the source database. The Delphix connector must interact directly with the true production source system to request the data to be persisted. There is no activity whatsoever on an intermediate staging host; instead the blocks are directly written to storage on the Delphix Continuous Data Engine. Once an environment is added, Delphix Engine will automatically 'discover' databases on it, which are compatible to ingest from, to create new dSources. Following the creation of a dSource, delphix continuous engine will leverage RMAN(Recovery Manager) utility and JDBC to create snapshots of the source by taking a full database backup. The newer snapshots take incremental backups of the database to ingest incremental data between snapshots. The result is a TimeFlow with various snapshots from which you can provision a VDB. The key component in this process is Oracle RMAN utility, the built-in backup and recovery utility for Oracle databases. It is designed to automate backup, restore, and recovery tasks while providing efficient management of database files. Hence, it is able to ship the entire storage block map to Delphix when Delphix requests it initially, then later just the changed blocks since the previous ingestion (an incremental roll forward capability).

Following, VDB provisioning involves, initially the creation of the virtual database, whose settings are a copy of the source environments settings, linked in the dSource, which must be compatible with the target environment, therefore source and target environments are almost identical storage solutions. Hence, as of the solution context a vCDB will be created on the target environment during initial provisioning. Creating a vCDB seems conceptually easy but in reality resolves around several complex steps, all the steps can be gathered in two main phases :

1. Data mounting : leveraging the binaries installed during environment configuration, Delphix mounts the virtualised data files onto the target environment, this involves the export of the storage containers associated with the VDB, making them available for mounting; and then mounts the exported storage containers over NFS to designated directories. These mount points correspond to the VDB's data files and structures.
2. Environment configuration : Delphix sets up the Oracle environment on the target host, ensuring that environment variables such as 'ORACLE_HOME' and 'ORACLE_SID' are correctly configured to recognise the mounted file systems. Respectively, they define the root directory where oracle is installed containing all executables, libraries and configuration file; and a unique name assigned to an Oracle instance which defines the instance to connect to. These variables play a fundamental role to ensure Oracle tools and applications correctly interact with the intended database.

Following virtual database refreshes are similar to the initial data mounting phase, with a middle action of comparison between data in the snapshot intended to be provisioned and current data, in order to adopt an incremental approach and therefore write solely new/changed data. Hence, refresh process can be summarised in three steps :

1. Unmount. : the current NFS file system is un mounted, which involves first of all gracefully stopping the running VDB instance and if configured unregister it from the oracle listener; then actually unmounting the NFS file system underlying the VDB
2. Update : updating data set includes checking for actual changes and new data in advance, by performing a thorough comparison. This comparison is employed at file system data blocks level and it is performed directly on Delphix with the Block Change Tracking (BCT) process. BCT fundamentally involves comparing the latest with the previous

dSource snapshot, block by block through their hashes, which are indexed, where differences or new blocks are revealed, Delphix analyse redo and archive logs to track committed transaction which resulted in the changes, finally database control files are evaluated for structure consistency to detect any table spaces and schemas change. Based on comparison results, data blocks are updated in the target unmounted NFS file system, including adding new blocks, updating current ones and removing deleted ones.

3. Mount : the updated NFS file system is re mounted in the environment file system, database service is restarted along with the VDB instance. Database availability and consistency is checked with a test connection leveraging JDBC, fetching for some metadata like its status.

Data masking

When Delphix performs in-place masking on an Oracle VDB, multiple components are involved on both the Delphix and Oracle database side. The interaction is primarily SQL-based, using SQLNet (Oracle Net Services). Delphix compliance engine connector leverages JDBC to interact with target Oracle database and the connection follows the SQLNet paradigm, where substantially request payloads are in plain SQL DML language and similarly authentication use clauses defined by Oracle standard, used by sql plus default oracle utility. Hence, the masking workflow involves the following macro steps :

1. Establish connection : Delphix Oracle connector initiates a JDBC based connection wrapped in a TLS tunnel, through SQLNet to the oracle VDB at standard port 1521, obviously in advance there is the establishment of the TLS tunnel with a TLS1.2/1.3 handshake. On port 1521 an Oracle listener process is listening for new connection initiations, once it detect the request it spawns a dedicated Oracle Server process to handle the masking session
2. Sensitive data detection : once a connection has been established, delphix engine communicate with the associated oracle service to detect sensitive to be masked according to the profiling set assigned to the rule set, this detection involves a series of batched SELECT queries executed by the Oracle SQL execution engine, which retrieves data from buffer cache or NFS file system if there are any cache miss.
3. Data update : following the detection and association with predefined masking algorithms according to the domain associated with the classifier. SQL UPDATE queries are prepared for batch execution and

they are sent in batches with a size pre-defined in the Delphix masking job configuration. In the solution, masking is multi-threaded with updated rows partitioned between threads and write collision avoided by row level lock handled by the SQL execution engine. Simultaneously, updates are stored in the redo log buffer before being committed and likewise undo Tablespace store pre-masking values to allow rollback.

4. Commit and Storage update : finally each thread commit all transaction performed in parallel, hence changes are written to the redo logs, and gradually the Oracle checkpoint process write in the NFS storage. Commit size is pre-configured in the engine and actual transactions size could exceed the limit, it is a fundamental to set it correctly to balance performance and redo log growth.

The following is the configuration panel of the masking job, among others in-place masking method, 5 update threads, 20000 rows batch size, 10000 transaction commit size are reported. Additionally, further noteworthy parameters are feedback size and memory boundaries, which respectively are the number of rows processed before sending a status update to the job execution logs and the amount of JVM heap memory allocated to the masking job in megabytes. With these settings the job is configured to split total rows to be updated as much as possible evenly across five threads, each thread further split rows to be updated in batches of 20000 rows and execute an update by which every 10000 rows updated transaction is committed and every 50000 rows a status feedback is sent back to the engine, with details of any encountered error and number of rows processed before the error.

JDBC

A core component of Delphix engines software architectures is JDBC (Java Database Connectivity). JDBC is a Java module which provide an API to interact with relational databases objects through java objects, therefore abstracting the complexities of relational database technologies and ease the interaction with them. JDBC is leveraged to interact with several types of relational databases, enabling virtualisation, masking, and replication. Delphix uses JDBC in several ways :

- Database Discovery & Inventory : gather environment metadata, including fetching information on schemas, tables, users, and storage configurations.
- Data Masking : execute SQL queries over JDBC to apply masking rules on sensitive data.

Figure 2.20: Masking job configuration panel

- Replication & Synchronization : When synchronizing datasets across environments, JDBC is used to retrieve change logs or execute queries for replication.

API

Delphix provides a comprehensive API that facilitate seamless integration and automation within its ecosystem. Its API is designed to manage and interact with various components of the Delphix Engine, including data ingestion, virtualization, and masking processes. Delphix API blends RESTful architecture with RPC-like (Remote Procedure Call) behavior, making it a hybrid approach that borrows concepts from both REST and gRPC. It's an hybrid approach since the communication channel at application level is HTTP and data is exchanged in JSON format conforming to RESTful principles but the API connection employs a stateful approach with a session based communication mechanism and additionally some endpoints effectively expose procedure-driven actions rather than pure CRUD, belonging to the gRPC paradigm.

As mentioned, communication with the API require the establishment of an

HTTP, or optionally HTTPS if wrapped in TLS tunnel, session before actually authenticating. Session is established by sending a POST request to a specific endpoint, the request involves a 'Session' object to the URL '/resources/json/delphix/session'. This session object will specify the 'APIVersion' to use for communication. Once a session has been established a POST request can be sent to the authentication endpoint, which differs between data and compliance engines, with credentials as payload, by fact using basic HTTP Auth as authentication method. Following the authentication API interaction in terms of request legitimacy control differs between data and compliance engine. As the former does not require an authorisation header with a token in following requests as it implicitly tracks the authenticated session using a server-side session mechanism, while it's documented that it lasts 30 minutes by default Delphix does not document low-level details of this mechanism, allegedly it bind the session to the TCP connection or if wrapped within a TLS channel the TLS connection or performs a client fingerprinting. Whereas, the compliance engine API requires an authorisation header with a token provided in response of the successful authentication request. Regarding the structure of the API, mainly when it comes to the data engine, it is strongly resource oriented which translate in endpoint organised by resource type; i.e. : database, environment, job.

Custom Masking Algorithm Plugins & Masking Extensible SDK

The Delphix Continuous Compliance Engine offers an Extensible Masking Model which enables the integration of custom masking algorithm plugins. This capability allows for tailored data protection strategies, accommodating unique data formats and compliance requirements.

The Extensible Masking Model is designed to enhance the Delphix Masking Engine's flexibility by supporting the creation and integration of custom masking algorithms. This model is facilitated through the Delphix Masking Extensible SDK, a toolkit that provides the necessary resources for developers to build, test, and deploy custom plugins, including the masking Java framework to build algorithms upon. This framework abstracts the core masking logic, enabling developers to focus on implementing their specific algorithms, it outlines clear interfaces and APIs that custom plugins must adhere to, ensuring seamless integration with the engine software. These plugins can introduce new masking algorithms or extend support to additional data sources, thereby broadening the engine's applicability. A custom masking algorithm plugin developed using the Delphix Masking Extensible SDK is constituted by the following macro components:

- **Algorithm Class:** The core of the plugin, this Java class implements the 'MaskingAlgorithm' interface provided by the SDK. It contains the

logic for the custom masking operation.

- **Metadata Files:** These files describe the plugin's properties, such as its name, version, author, and any dependencies.
- **Build Scripts:** dependencies managers and builders like Gradle which automate the compilation and packaging of the plugin into a deployable JAR file.

Once installed, the plugin becomes an integral part of the Masking Engine's ecosystem. The engine dynamically loads the plugin, making its functionalities available for use in masking jobs. Plugins operate within a sandboxed environment on the Masking Engine. This sandboxing ensures that the plugin's operations do not adversely affect the overall system stability or security.

2.4 Custom Masking Algorithm

As introduced formerly in the overall solution illustration, a custom masking algorithm was developed to perform a data clustering on target columns and write results in the corresponding column of the result table in JSON format along with a timestamp. This functionality is implemented leveraging a key feature and a fundamental characteristic of the compliance engine, respectively sensible data masking and its extendibility, both covered in previous chapter. Though, the in-place kind of masking performed in this solution does not replace sensitive data identified with fictitious values as intended natively by the feature design but essentially perform custom SQL queries according to the data retrieved from the results table. This custom masking algorithm therefore leverages extendibility as it is integrated with the engine through a masking plugin. The algorithm attached with the plugin is then associated with a pre defined making job which employs in advance the automatic sensitive data discovery. Hence, during job creation the discovery is configured by setting rule set, classifier, domain, profile set. Initially, after the source critical environment has been connected the whole set of tables among all pluggable databases, besides catalog tables, have been defined in the scope of the rule set. Since the data in the results table are not masked but simply read for further dynamic query creation, it is therefore known that discovery does not require complex domain or classifiers. In this scenario, a general purpose "CHECK" domain, with associated the custom masking algorithm, has been defined to identify sensitive data and therefore select it as input to the algorithm to create dynamic queries. Likewise a profile set

has been specifically crafted to be used in this mechanism, it includes a classifier with PATH frameworks and previously defined check domain, creating by fact an ASDD mechanism. Next, this profile set is associated to the rule set and the classifier PATH framework implemented specifying the path to all results table columns as target.

The plugin is written in Java as it is the chosen language by Delphix to implement the masking interface to interact with the masking engine, and allegedly to implement the masking engine itself. Therefore, plugin code is wrapped in a fat JAR package with all necessary JARs of libraries and Gradle to be built and executed, adhering to the self-contained requirement, besides the classes that comprehend the plugin API itself, which are already present on the compliance engine.

Hence, the following is the plugin architecture with compiled classes

Figure 2.21: Plugin architecture

Third Party Libraries

Starting with the third party java libraries used, Delphix defines a small set of libraries already embedded in the interface between the engine and plugins, whereby the plugins code must link against the exact version already used by the engine. Among these special libraries in the plugin are being used `com.delphix.masking:masking-algorithm-api`, `com.fasterxml.jackson.core:jackson-annotations` and `com.google.code.findbugs:jsr305`, whose usage is basically forced by the plugin recommended methods definitions, covered later. A thorough overview of libraries is illustrated below

- `jackson-annotations` : provides JSON serialization/deserialization control in Java. Key annotations include ‘`@JsonProperty`‘ (rename fields), ‘`@JsonIgnore`‘ (exclude fields), ‘`@JsonCreator`‘ (custom constructors), and ‘`@JsonFormat`‘ (date formatting). It abstracts the complexities of JSON processing with fine-grained control over field inclusion, mapping, and customization in Jackson-based applications. In the plugin scenario it is used to declare fields of the input file in json format
- `javapasswordsdk` : provide an API to ease the integration with CyberArk Password Vault. It enables secure retrieval of credentials, supports password rotation, and automates authentication. Key features include password fetching via APIs, vault policy enforcement, and secure storage handling, enhancing security in enterprise applications
- `json-simple` : seamless JSON parsing and generation. It provides simple APIs for reading, writing, and manipulating JSON data using ‘`JSONObject`‘ and ‘`JSONArray`‘
- `jsr305` provides annotations for static code analysis in Java. Key annotations include ‘`@Nullable`‘, ‘`@NonNull`‘ (null-safety), ‘`@ThreadSafe`‘, and ‘`@CheckReturnValue`‘. It is currently deprecated(not actively maintained) but the usage is limited to basic ‘`@Nullable`‘ annotations in the code.
- `masking-algorithm-api` : library provided by Delphix among which there is the `MaskingAlgorithm` interface to implement in order to define a new algorithm; other relevant classes that implement key features are data types processed by the algorithm(in the pluing scenario `GenericDataRow`), masking exceptions, and JDBC implementation utils.
- `semantic` : Not really used, but provides tools for working with semantic web technologies, including RDF (Resource Description Framework)

and OWL (Web Ontology Language). It was initially used to ease even more the communication with CyberArk.

Build Management

Next, as notable by few related files, Gradle is leveraged for dependency management and build automation. Gradle is a really powerful tool for java artifacts build management with a declarative task-based model, build tasks along with required dependency libraries paths and artifact metadata are declared in a configuration file in Groovy language, enabling a flexible, incremental and highly scalable build automation. An exhaustive illustration of Gradle is out of the scope of this paper, nevertheless for a proper comprehension all configurations file role and content will be depicted in the following paragraph. For this plugin scenario, Gradle package(gradle-wrapper.jar), package properties, his wrappers(gradlew and gradle.bat) and indeed its declaration and setting files are contained within the plugin JAR, making the plugin by fact fully build portable, enabling the build execution on any machine even without gradle installed and with a consistent version of Gradle and execution pattern. In this scenario, the following gradle-wrapper.properties file is defining gradle details

```
distributionBase=GRADLE_USER_HOME
distributionPath=wrapper/dists
zipStoreBase=GRADLE_USER_HOME
zipStorePath=wrapper/dists
distributionUrl=https\://services.gradle.org/distributions/
gradle-8.13-all.zip
```

Here it's been defined the URL where the Gradle JAR should be retrieved, which forces also the version, and declared to cache it locally with 'distributionBase=GRADLE_USER_HOME'. Hence when ./gradlew or gradle.bat are run, one of their first task is downloading Gradle using gradle-wrapper.jar based on gradle-wrapper.properties: Gradle wrapper JAR contains the compiled classes required to download and launch the specified version of Gradle, allowing by fact Gradle to bootstrap itself on-demand. Both wrappers have the same execution pattern, and three macro steps can be identified :

- Set JVM options by using default values('Xmx64m -Xms64m') but allows overriding with 'JAVA_OPTS' and 'GRADLE_OPTS'.
- Determine java executable location - exit with error if java is missing
- Construct java execution command which launches org.gradle.wrapper.GradleWrapperMain which downloads and run Gradle

Whereas Gradle build tasks declaration file have the following content :

```

buildscript {
    repositories {
        mavenCentral()
        mavenLocal()
    }
    dependencies {
        classpath files("${project.rootDir}/libs/masking-
            algorithm-api-${maskingAlgoVer}.jar")
        classpath files("${project.rootDir}/libs/semantic-
            version-${semanticVer}.jar")
        classpath files("${project.rootDir}/libs/
            javapasswordsdk.jar")
    }
}

apply plugin: 'java'

repositories {
    mavenCentral()
    mavenLocal()
}

jar {
    from {
        configurations.runtimeClasspath.collect { it.
            isDirectory() ?
            it : zipTree(it) }
    }
    includeEmptyDirs = false

    manifest {
        attributes(
            (PluginMetadata.PLUGIN_NAME_KEY)      : "
                ransomCheck",
            (PluginMetadata.AUTHOR_NAME_KEY)     : "Diego
                Gobbetti",
            (PluginMetadata.PLUGIN_VERSION_KEY)   : "1.0",
            (PluginMetadata.ALGORITHM_API_VERSION_KEY):
                "$maskingAlgoVer",
            'Build-Timestamp':
                new java.text.SimpleDateFormat
                    ("yyyy-MM-dd'T'HH:mm:ss.SSSZ").format(new
                    Date()),
            'Created-By' : "Gradle ${gradle.gradleVersion}",
            'Build-Jdk' :
                "${System.properties['java.version']}
                (${System.properties['java.vendor']}
                ${System.properties['java.vm.version']})",
            'Build-OS' : "${System.properties['os.name']}"
        )
    }
}

```

```

        ${System.properties['os.arch']}
        ${System.properties['os.version']}]",
    )
}

dependencies {
    compileOnly fileTree(dir: "${project.rootDir}/libs",
        include: '*.jar')
    implementation files('/libs/javapasswordsdk.jar')
}

```

here as well three macro blocks can be distinguished :

- **buildscript** : here dependencies and repositories to fetch them are defined, they are solely needed by Gradle itself, therefore only available for gradle configuration not for compiling or at runtime.
 - **Repositories** : mavenCentral is referencing a public remote repository, while mavenLocal a local one usually available at `/.m2/repository`. Both are based on Maven, another tool for dependency management, xml-based, which offers also a public repository where libraries are hosted.
 - **Dependencies** : dependencies are retrieved by declaring the path where they are located within the project directory, the declaration is also based on local variables defined in specifically crafted `gradle.properties` file.
- **jar** : these declaration customise how the JAR file is structured, including additional components. In order to guarantee the creation of a self-contained fat JAR, all runtime dependencies are included, unzipping if they are zipped and excluding empty directories.
 - The core part is the artifact manifest definition, where basically are reported all relevant artifact metadata. Data is dynamically created as it is based on java expressions, a result is reported below for reference

```

Manifest-Version: 1.0
Implementation-Version: 1.0
Build-Timestamp: 2024-06-12T11:01:47.645+0200
Delphix-Algorithm-API-Version: 1.2.0
Build-OS: Windows 11 amd64 10.0
Delphix-Plugin-Name: ransomCheck
Created-By: Gradle 5.6 Build-Jdk: 1.8.0_402-402 (
    OpenLogic-OpenJDK 25.402-b06)
Implementation-Vendor: Diego Gobbetti

```

- Runtime dependencies : finally all library dependencies are declared, similarly to the previous declaration in the buildscript block. Likewise, here all JARs in the lbs directory are limited to compile time, not runtime, besides javapasswords.jar. This is made in order to avoid the aforementioned collision between dependencies in the plugin code and engine plugins interface, hence code is written with the same version used by the engine so when the plugin is injected and run code will be compatible with the interface but required libraries will be retrieved by jars on the engine, whereas javapasswords is used to connect to CyberArk password vault and not used by the engine

Lastly, settings.gradle role is to define JAR wide settings like name, which is this plugin use case.

Source Code

The last, and indeed most important, macro component of the plugin is the actual Java executive source code. The plugin source can be additionally divided in two main blocks, the actual source code inside the sample directory and the final JAR name declarations inside the file at META-INF/services directory com.delphix.masking.api.plugin.MaskingComponent. In order to comprehend fully the source code, few software objects established by Delphix, to provide the masking extendibility features properly and target a broad range of data types, must be understood in advance :

MaskingAlgorithm: One of these and probably the most noteworthy is the afore introduced MaskingAlgorithm interface. Any Java class that should be recognized as a masking algorithm (whether standalone or configurable) must implement this interface. This interface is parameterized with the data type that the algorithm masks, which defines the input and output data type of the mask method. Interface, class and method Parameterization in Java is employed with Generics, a powerful software components configuration concept, which allows such components to operate on objects of various types while providing compile-time type safety; the type specified as a placeholder in your code will be replaced by a specific type when the class is instantiated or method invoked, in this plugin case when the class implementing the masking interface is instantiated. The masking class can be parameterized to a specific set of data types, in order to simplify algorithm development while maintaining the ability to mask data from many sources :

- Binary data - java.nio.ByteBuffer
- String data - java.lang.String

- Numeric data - `java.math.BigDecimal`
- Date time data - `java.time.LocalDateTime`
- Multi-column data - `com.delphix.masking.api.plugin.utils.GenericDataRow`

Each algorithm is expected to input, process, and emit objects of one of the above Java types, but is free to use any intermediate types (as needed) to access library methods.

The `MaskingAlgorithm` interface inherits from another masking general interface, always provided in the masking algorithm jar, `MaskingComponent`, an higher level component for masking algorithms, providing the methods `getAllowFurtherInstances()` , `getDefaultInstances()`, `setup()` and `tearDown()` covered later. This interface extends further parent interfaces :

- `JsonConfigurable` : class with the responsibility of ensuring the JSON configuration data is valid, including its json compliant overall data format; values proper format, lenght and any other constraint; empty or null properties. provide this functionality through the method `validate()` leveraging the Jackson JSON deserializer.
- `PluginComponent` : kernel interface that all plugins of all types looking to expose functionality to the Delphix Masking engine must implement. It provides the methods `getName()`, `getDescription()` and `getDocumentation()` covered later.

Hence, when it comes to all the methods offered by the masking interface, the following can be identified :

- `getName` and `getDescription` - These methods are used to determine the name and description of frameworks and algorithm instances included in the plugin. For user-created instances, these methods are never called.
- `getDefaultInstances` and `getAllowFurtherInstances` - These methods control the set of instances of the algorithm framework that are defined by the plugin, and whether the user should be allowed to create additional instances.
- `validate` - This method is called after configuration is applied to allow the algorithm class to check whether the injected configuration is valid.

- setup and tearDown - These methods are called before the algorithm object is used for masking, and after, respectively. Typically, any resources, such as input files, are acquired during setup and released during tearDown.
- mask - This is the method that does the actual data masking in the algorithm class. The input and output values are parameterized for type safety.
- listMultiColumnFields - This method needs to be implemented only for Multi-Column Algorithms. It returns a list of AlgorithmLogicalField objects that define the set of fields that the multi-column algorithm masks. For each column it is required to define the core data type using the Delphix enumeration, and optionally the method offers the possibility to declare a description, permissions(i.e. : read-only/read-write). Usually, the specular listMaskedFields method is preferred to it, similarly it returns a map of field names (String) to the Core Data Type

GenericDataRow: A GenericDataRow is by fact a map of field names (String) to GenericData objects. Each GenericData object contains the value, along with methods to return the respective typed object. When accessing the value from a GenericData Object it will be necessary to read it into a core data type. To do so, one of the following methods must be used :

- getStringValue()
- getBigDecimalValue()
- getLocalDateTimeValue()
- getByteBufferValue()

Once the value has been masked it should be re-set by calling setValue and passing as an argument the value as a core data type. GenericDataRow objects are mainly used in contexts where the target data type is unknown before the configuration or anyway dynamic; this is usually the scenario when masking is the function of multiple related columns, which is the solution setting.

MultiColumn: this type allows the definition of masking algorithms whose result is the function of multiple columns. Each column processed must be defined as AlgorithmLogicalField by the previously illustrated listMultiColumnFields. Furthermore, columns must be configured engine

side through web UI or API, configuring a column means defining column's metadata with the following information :

- `AlgorithmFieldId` : index of the column among fields processed by the associated algorithm
- `AlgorithmGroupNo` : is a group number (integer) for the columns treated by the same algorithm instance. It is introduced for cases where there are multiple columns of a similar type, which are masked by the different Masking Jobs using the same algorithm. In such a case that's important to unite the columns per algorithm run, by assigning the same group number
- `AlgorithmName` : name of the sensitive data classifier framework, previously illustrated.
- `DomainName` : domain assigned to column data, previously illustrated.

A final important concept is algorithms configurability, the extensible algorithms feature supports the creation of algorithm frameworks. When an algorithm class is constructed to be a framework, the Continuous Compliance Engine may create additional instances of the algorithm - with different configurations - after the plugin has been installed, based on provided JSON data. The JSON schema for configuration is determined by which data members in the framework class are marked as configurable, and may vary from framework to framework. To integrate an algorithm as a configurable framework within the Continuous Compliance Engine, specific requirements must be met:

- **Method requirement:** The algorithm class should have the `getAllowFurtherInstances` method implemented to return `true`.
- **Data member annotation:** The algorithm class must include one or more public data members. These members are crucial for configuration and must be annotated with `@JsonProperty` from the `com.fasterxml.jackson.annotation.JsonProperty` package. This annotation enables the data members to be recognized and processed as configurable parameters.

For each algorithm marked as configurable, the SDK or Continuous Compliance Engine inspects the class annotations to identify which parameters can be configured. When new JSON data is provided and the process of creating a new instance of the algorithm is triggered, the system tries to apply the

user-provided JSON configuration to the algorithm class object, this process includes a level of validation described before by the `JsonConfigurable` component.

So given all of these functional and software concepts, in the following paragraphs snippets of final production code will be depicted according to the masking algorithm workflow, with the premise that basic concepts will be overlooked. Most of the code belong to the `RansomCheck` class implementing the `MaskingAlgorithm` interface, but three further are defined to properly separate functional responsibilities : `TableDetails`, `WhereCondition` and `Toolbox`; all fall within the utilities category as they provide a functionality that ease the masking workflow abstracting the complexities of underlying java native modules.

A short parenthesis on non functional aspects is necessary, the plugin source code follows design best practices to guarantee most non functional requirements at a professional level. An high degree of modularity ensures maintainability, reusability, interoperability and therefore scalability; whereas the broad coverage of not expected execution scenarios with constructs try-catch strongly supports reliability, fault tolerance and security, similarly the highly meaningful scenarios descriptions allows ease the debugging also at scale; and of course the core set of design principles outlined by the SOLID are respected, as demonstrated by the following examples :

- Single Responsibility Principle (SRP) : `RansomCheck` class is solely handling data extraction process logic, outlining all various step of the algorithm, while functions like executing queries, logging, connecting to database instances, storing data in efficient data structure, are all handled by specifically crafted classes.
- Open Closed Principle(OCP) : all software entities are open for extension, new amasking algorithms can be defined just by creating another class that implements the `MaskingAlgorithm` interface. Similarly, a new data processing query can be defined by writing a further class that builds a different kind of query and calling it inside the build query step, which will be eventually appended by the final table scoping part.
- Liskov Substitution Principle (LSP) : there are not really sub-classes in the code, but current classes design set a proper base for an easy future extension that guarantees proper interchangeability.
- Interface Segregation Principle (ISP) : this is guaranteed by Delphix interface requirements, since the masking engine is the only real client that interacts with the plugin, the correct way of interaction is through the class implementing the `MaskingAlgorithm` interface.

- Dependency Inversion Principle(DIP) : just like the previous, the degree of complexity of the code does not require multiple level classes with a higher level interface that allows choice flexibility, but any future extension is facilitated by the current design.

Software entities names besides being highly meaningful being made of few descriptive words, comply under all aspects to Java naming convention, hence Pascal case for classes and interfaces, camel cases for methods and attributes, while full upper case for constants and enumerations.

The methods and attributes surrounding the actual masking workflow logic, previously illustrated, will be depicted. All of these fall belong to the core RansomCheck class, among them there is getAllowFurtherInstances method to establish the algorithm as a framework, enabling it's further configuration

```
@Override
public boolean getAllowFurtherInstances() {
    return true;
}
```

Illustrated before, being inherited from MaskingComponent it features the Override annotation. Which is required at compile time to verify the implementation of the interface contract. This method combined with the following declaration of configuration public variables, makes by fact the algorithm a framework from which instances can be released

```
@JsonProperty("db_dbType")
public String db_dbType;
@JsonProperty("db_hostname")
public String db_hostname;
@JsonProperty("db_port")
public String db_port;
@JsonProperty("db_username")
public String db_username;
@JsonProperty("db_schema")
public String db_schema;
@JsonProperty("db_password")
public String db_password;
@JsonProperty("db_instance")
public String db_instance;
@JsonProperty("db_addParams")
public String db_addParams;
```

All variables are annotated with the annotation @JsonProperty to allow the recognition as configuration data members, by the engine during plugin inspection. Hence, a file with a specular structure must be provided as framework configuration on the engine once the pluing has been loaded. This configuration features all technical details to establish a connection and reach the

database general view(CHECK_VIEW_2), peculiar is the db_dbType which is effectively the name of a technology as defined by the enumeration that the connection class relies on. This data is the igniting point of the algorithm, it's fundamental to avoid hardcoding which would make the algorithm insecure and preclude its interoperability with different databases.

Further class variables comprehend mainly private objects designed to provide a specific functionality and therefore leveraged along the data processing workflow. As a matter of fact these attributes have been declared at the class level to be visible by all methods, though the keyword private is leveraged to limit their visibility within the class. Since a masking algorithm constructor wasn't defined, once the engine plugins interface will instantiate the algorithm, the java Object default no arguments constructor will be invoked and all reference types variables will be initialised to null, including the list and String.

```
private LogService logger;
private Toolbox toolbox;
private Connection containerConnection;
private Connection targetTableConnection;
private ArrayList<String> values_list;
private WhereCondition condition;
private TableDetails resultRowData;
private TableDetails targetTableData;
private String checkQuery;
private ResultSet valuesClustersResultSet;
private JSONObject retrievedValuesClusters;
```

These objects assume a proper initial value once the setup() method is called. Each reference typed variable is initialised with an instance of the respective objet, besides the java sql module ResultSet which is abstract. Setup method is called only once following object creation, its intended usage is to initialise class variables and let computational space to elaborate on the algorithm metadata in advance, leveraging the ComponentService argument.

```
@Override
public void setup(@NonNull ComponentService serviceProvider)
{
    this.logger = serviceProvider.getLogService();
    this.toolbox = new Toolbox();
    this.condition = new WhereCondition();
    this.values_list = new ArrayList<String>();
    this.checkQuery = "";
    this.valuesClustersResultSet = null;
    this.retrievedValuesClusters = new JSONObject();
}
```

Another fundamental method is the aforementioned method to declare the

list of columns with their core data type of the target table(rule set) which should be object of processing by the algorithm. This method is listMaskedFields() and returns a map with column name and masking core data type, VARCHAR used for index parameters on database side correspond to string core data type, whereas the result column is parameterised as byte.buffer being a BLOB(Binary Large Object), which holds binary data.

```

@Override
public Map<String, MaskingType> listMaskedFields() {
    Map<String, MaskingType> maskedFields = new HashMap<
        String, MaskingType> ();
    maskedFields.put("DATABASE_ID", MaskingType.STRING);
    maskedFields.put("TABLE_ID", MaskingType.STRING);
    maskedFields.put("COLUMN_ID", MaskingType.STRING);
    maskedFields.put("RESULT", MaskingType.BYTE_BUFFER);
    maskedFields.put("TIMESTAMP", MaskingType.LOCAL_DATE_TIME
    );
    return maskedFields;
}

```

The actual data extraction and processing logic is defined in the mask() method, as mentioned formerly.

```

@Override
public GenericDataRow mask(@Nullable GenericDataRow
    genericData) throws MaskingException {
    try {
        getResultRowData(genericData);
        getTargetTableData();
        getColumnExpectedValues();
        buildClusteringQuery();
        extractColumnEffectiveValuesClusters();
        parseEffectiveValues();
    } catch (Exception e) {
        if (e instanceof InvalidIndexParametersException) {
            writeEffectiveValues(((
                InvalidIndexParametersException) e).
                printMessageWithIndexes());
            return genericData;
        } else if (e instanceof IllegalArgumentException) {
            writeEffectiveValues(((IllegalArgumentException)
                e).getMessage());
            return genericData;
        } else {
            StringWriter sw = new StringWriter();
            e.printStackTrace(new PrintWriter(sw));
            throw new MaskingException(sw.toString() + "\n
                Exception message : \n" + e.getMessage() + " \n
                With following parameters : \n db_id : " +

```

```

        resultRowData.getDb() + "\n tb_id : " +
        resultRowData.getTable() + " \n col_id : " +
        resultRowData.getCol() + " \n\n With following
        values : \n " + String.join(", ", values_list));
    }
}
return genericData;
}

```

This method has a central role, receiving as input, through an argument, the `GenericDataRow` element, map of `genericData` variables, and return it following an elaboration, which in this solution scenario are performed on the `RESULT` column. All the instructions inside are wrapped within a try-catch construct, that catches for a general exception, since all the nested methods which will be covered later can return several different kinds of exceptions. The exception handling is performed according to the exception type. A specific exception `InvalidIndexParametersException` has been crafted to properly handle invalid index parameters in the results table, in case of such exception through the `writeEffectiveValues` method, the exception message is written in the result column and the current iteration of the algorithm ends returning the `genericData` object, the method input.

```

public class InvalidIndexParametersException extends
    Exception {

    ArrayList<String> indexes;

    public InvalidIndexParametersException(String message) {
        super(message);
    }
    public InvalidIndexParametersException(String message ,
        String... Idx) {
        super(message);
        this.indexes = new ArrayList<String>(Arrays.asList(
            Idx)); // Directly convert array to list
    }

    @Override
    public String getMessage() {
        return super.getMessage();
    }

    public ArrayList<String> getIndexes() {
        return this.indexes;
    }
    public void setIndexes(ArrayList<String> indexes) {
        this.indexes = indexes;
    }
}

```

```

    }

    public String printMessageWithIndexes() {
        return getMessage() + "\n" + String.join(", ",
            getIndexes());
    }
}

```

Whereas the `IllegalArgumentException` exception is sought for to handle null values retrieved in the general database view, such case is handled by writing the exception message into the result column and returning the `GenericData` object. All additional exceptions are handled by throwing a `MaskingException`, retrieved from the masking plugin library, which stops the engine masking process and prints the passed argument in the masking job info logger. The passed string reports the current execution stack trace, along with the current analysed database, table and column indexes and the list of values being checked looked upon.

The first step of the algorithm is to place current row data in a specifically crafted data structure, which ease its elaboration. Since index parameters are encoded as `VARCHAR` database side, a proper parsing requires the use of `getStringValue()` method, this method belongs to the object crafted by Delphix to hold cell values, which likely is an interface to multiple data types

```

private void getResultRowData(GenericDataRow genericData) {
    this.resultRowData.setDetails(
        genericData.get("DATABASE_ID").getStringValue(),
        genericData.get("TABLE_ID").getStringValue(),
        genericData.get("COLUMN_ID").getStringValue(),
        genericData.get("RESULT"),
        genericData.get("TIMESTAMP")
    );
}

```

This data structure is implemented with a class `TableDetails` which exposes all database related details with several attributes and respective getter methods.

```

public class TableDetails{
    // results table data
    private String db; // all for security purposes
    private String table;
    private String col;
    private GenericData result;
    private GenericData timestamp;
    // data required to connect to table where reside column
    // to extract values from
    private String technology;
}

```

```

private String host;
private String port;
private String sid;
private String schema;
private String username;
private String password;

private ArrayList<String> null_values;
// builder for results table details
public void setDetails(String db, String table, String
    col, GenericData result, GenericData timestamp) throws
    IllegalArgumentException {
    this.db = db==null ? addNullValue("db") : db;
    this.table = table==null ? addNullValue("table") :
        table;
    this.col = col==null ? addNullValue("col") : col;
    this.result = result;
    this.timestamp = timestamp;
    checkNullValues();
}

public void setDetails(String technology, String host,
    String port, String sid_service, String schema, String
    table, String col, String username, String password)
    throws IllegalArgumentException {
    this.technology = technology==null ? addNullValue("
        technology") : technology;
    this.host = host==null ? addNullValue("host") : host;
    this.port = port==null ? addNullValue("port") : port;
    this.sid = sid==null ? addNullValue("sid") : sid;
    this.schema = schema==null ? addNullValue("schema") :
        schema;
    this.table = table==null ? addNullValue("table") :
        table;
    this.col = col==null ? addNullValue("col") : col;
    this.username = username==null ? addNullValue("
        username") : username;
    this.password = password==null ? addNullValue("
        password") : password;
    checkNullValues();
}

// handler for null values
public String addNullValue(String value) {
    null_values.add(value);
    return "";
}

public void checkNullValues() throws

```

```

        IllegalArgumentException {
            if (!null_values.isEmpty()) {
                throw new IllegalArgumentException("Missing
                    required parameter(s) to establish connection/
                    perform query: " + String.join(" ",
                        null_values));
            }
        }
    }

    // getters
    public String getDb() { return db; }
    public String getTable() { return table; }
    public String getCol() { return col; }
    public GenericData getResult() { return result; }
    public GenericData getTimestamp() { return timestamp; }
    public String getTech() { return technology; }
    public String getHost() { return host; }
    public String getPort() { return port; }
    public String getSid() { return sid; }
    public String getSchema() { return schema; }
    public String getUsr() { return username; }
    public String getPwd() { return password; }
}

```

It offers two constructor methods, since two different kind of data sets in two different scenario are passed to instantiate it. Further future data sets can be handled by declaring another constructor. Hence, when it comes to holding data of a row being processed, the first constructor is called, whereas when all database details required to query the target table must be handled the second is called.

This data is then used to query the general database view(CHECK_VIEW_2) for target table details to establish a connection. This step is implemented in the getTargetTableData() method

```

private void getTargetTableData() throws SQLException,
    ClassNotFoundException, IllegalArgumentException,
    InvalidIndexParametersException{
    try{
        this.containerConnection = toolbox.
            prepareDBConnection(databaseType.valueOf(db_dbType
            ),db_hostname,db_port,db_instance,db_addParams,
            db_username,db_password);
        ResultSet rs = toolbox.executeQuery(this.
            containerConnection, "SELECT TECHNOLOGY, HOSTNAME,
            PORT, COALESCE(SID, SERVICE, LOCATOR), DB_SCHEMA,
            TABLE_NAME, COLUMN_NAME, USERNAME, PASSWORD FROM

```

```

        ?.CHECK_VIEW_2 WHERE DB_ID = '?' AND TABLE_ID =
        '?' AND COLUMN_ID = '?'", db_schema, resultRowData
        .getDb(), resultRowData.getTable(), resultRowData.
        getCol());
    if(rs != null && rs.next()) {
        this.targetTableData.setDetails(
            rs.getString(1).split(" ")[0],
            rs.getString(2),
            rs.getString(3),
            rs.getString(4),
            rs.getString(5),
            rs.getString(6),
            rs.getString(7),
            rs.getString(8),
            rs.getString(9)
        );
        rs.close();
    } else {
        this.logger.info("No table/column found in the
            general database view with these parameters\n
            db_id : " + resultRowData.getDb() + "\n tb_id
            : " + resultRowData.getTable() + "\n col_id : "+
            resultRowData.getCol());
        throw new InvalidIndexParametersException("No
            table/column found in the general database
            view with these parameters", resultRowData.
            getDb(), resultRowData.getTable(),
            resultRowData.getCol());
    }
} catch(SQLException e){
    throw new SQLException(e.getMessage() + "\n Error
        connecting to or querying the general
        database view");
}
}

```

instructions are wrapped first in a try-catch construct to handle gracefully SQL-specific errors, including connections errors, raised by external object methods; secondly if the query result is null the execution falls within the else branch, which handles this scenario raising an `InvalidIndexParametersException` exception, which has been specifically crafted to signal an error due to the parameters in the row currently being processed, not associated with any actual table/column in the general database view, which is a very rare corner case, since the view is built upon the table from where filter values are retrieved. Further exceptions raised by called external objects are just passed to the wider scope, which will handle them. Similarly to `getResultRowData()`, query results are encoded in a proxy data structure through the

setDetails() method, which simultaneously checks for these values emptiness, and report in a IllegalArgumentException message if any are detected. The connection establishment is implemented with a proper method in the toolbox class, prepareDBConnection()

```
public Connection prepareDBConnection(databaseType dbType,
    String hostname, String port, String instance, String
    additionalParams, String username, String password) throws
    ClassNotFoundException, SQLException {
    try {
        Connection connection = null;
        if (dbType == databaseType.ORACLE) {
            Class.forName("oracle.jdbc.OracleDriver");
            String dbURL = new String("jdbc:oracle:thin:@" +
                hostname + ":" + port + "/" + instance);
            connection = DriverManager.getConnection(dbURL,
                username, password);
        } else if (dbType == databaseType.DB2) {
            Class.forName("com.ibm.db2.jcc.DB2Driver");
            String dbURL = new String("jdbc:db2://" +
                hostname + ":" + port + "/" + instance +
                additionalParams);
            connection = DriverManager.getConnection(dbURL,
                username, password);
        }
        else if (dbType == databaseType.POSTGRES) {
            Class.forName("org.postgresql.Driver");
            String dbURL = new String("jdbc:postgresql://" +
                hostname + ":" + port + "/" + instance +
                additionalParams);
            connection = DriverManager.getConnection(dbURL,
                username, password);
        }
        return connection;
    } catch(SQLException e) {
        throw new SQLException(e.getSQLState() + " \n" + e.
            getMessage());
    }
}
```

Which is processing as input the details required for connection, provided in the configuration file engine side. According to the database technology resolved through an enumeration, different connection URLs are built appending provided username and passwords, any problem in the connection is raised as a SQLException.

Whereas, query crafting and execution are implemented through a couple of linked methods : executeQuery(), which calls prepareStatement(), adopting by fact an approach with a dynamic statement filled with bind variable at the

time of execution. Actually three similar `executeQuery()` methods to handle query requests in different manners and provide different levels of control can be distinguished

```
public ResultSet executeQuery(Connection conn, String query,
    int fetchSize) throws SQLException {
    PreparedStatement preparedStatement = conn.
        prepareStatement(query);
    ResultSet rs = preparedStatement.executeQuery();
    rs.setFetchSize(fetchSize);
    return rs;
}
```

```
public ResultSet executeQuery(Connection conn, String query,
    String... variables) throws SQLException {
    PreparedStatement preparedStatement = prepareStatement(
        conn, query, variables);          //conn.
    prepareStatement(query);
    ResultSet rs = preparedStatement.executeQuery();
    rs.setFetchSize(5000);
    return rs;
}
```

```
public ResultSet executeQuery(Connection conn, String query)
    throws SQLException {
    PreparedStatement preparedStatement = conn.
        prepareStatement(query);
    ResultSet rs = preparedStatement.executeQuery();
    rs.setFetchSize(5000);
    return rs;
}
```

The first variation allows explicit control over the fetch size parameter, which determines how many rows are retrieved from the database at once, useful for memory optimization when dealing with large result sets.

The second version handles parameterized queries by accepting variable arguments (varargs) for query parameters. It uses `prepareStatement` to safely bind variables to the query, preventing SQL injection. The fetch size is also set to 5000.

The third variation is the basic scenario, where a static query is passed and a fetch size of 5000 is applied.

Likewise, two kind of `prepareStatement()` have been defined

```
public PreparedStatement prepareStatement(Connection conn,
    String query, String... variables) throws SQLException {
    PreparedStatement stmt = conn.prepareStatement(query);
    if(variables == null)
        throw new IllegalArgumentException("variables can't
```

```

        be empty");
    for(int i = 1; i <= variables.length; i++) {
        stmt.setString(i, variables[i]);
    }
    return stmt;
}
// stmt preparation for scenario with whereCondition
presenting bindVariables, not used atm
public PreparedStatement prepareStatement(Connection conn,
    String query, WhereCondition condizione, String db_schema,
    String tb_name) throws SQLException {
    PreparedStatement stmt = conn.prepareStatement(query);
    if(!condizione.getValues().isEmpty() && condizione.getCol
        () != null)
        throw new IllegalArgumentException("la colonna deve
            esistere e deve avere almeno un valore da cercare"
        );
    int j = 1;
    for(int i = 1; i <= condizione.getValues().size(); i++) {
        stmt.setString(j, condizione.getValues().get(i));
        stmt.setString(++j, condizione.getCol());
        stmt.setString(++j, condizione.getValues().get(i));
    }
    stmt.setString(++j, db_schema);
    stmt.setString(++j, tb_name);

    return stmt;
}

```

The first variation is the base scenario method that handles simple parameterized queries. It takes variable String arguments and binds them sequentially to the prepared statement replacing placeholders using `setString()`.

The second variation is implemented to handle a scenario where the where condition is previously built with bind variables, hence the replacement of bind variables with expected values and column occurs at runtime, guaranteeing more safety. Though, this scenario is not occurring in the current implementation.

Moving on, expected values for the column being processed are retrieved by the method `getColumnExpectedValues()`

```

private void getColumnExpectedValues() throws SQLException,
    ClassNotFoundException, InvalidIndexParametersException{
    ResultSet values_rs = toolbox.executeQuery(this.
        containerConnection,
        "SELECT DISTINCT VALUE FROM ?.CHECK_BASE WHERE
            ID_CHECK = (SELECT DISTINCT ID FROM ?.CHECK_2
                WHERE DATABASE_ID = '?' AND TABLE_ID = '?' AND
                COLUMN_ID = '?')", db_schema, db_schema,

```

```

        db_schema, resultRowData.getDb(), resultRowData.
            getTable(), resultRowData.getCol());
if(values_rs != null && values_rs.next()) {
    while(values_rs.next()) {
        values_list.add(values_rs.getString(1));
    }
    values_rs.close();
    this.containerConnection.close();
} else {
    this.logger.info("No expected values found in
        expected values table(CHECK_BASE) with these
        parameters\n db_id : " + resultRowData.getDb() + "
        \n tb_id : "+
resultRowData.getTable() +"\n col_id : "+ resultRowData.
    getCol());
    throw new InvalidIndexParametersException("No expected
        values found in expected values table(CHECK_BASE) with
        these parameters", resultRowData.getDb(),
        resultRowData.getTable(), resultRowData.getCol());
}
}
}

```

Distinct values are retrieved executing a parameterized query using `toolbox.executeQuery()` from the CHECK_BASE table, filtering by the parameters indexing the column being processed : database ID, table ID, and column ID, held by the `resultRowData` object. If no values are found (result set null), detailed information are logged in the job execution logging interface and likewise an `InvalidIndexParametersException` is thrown with the same information. Whereas if the query was successful and there is at least one row, through an iteration values are added to the list, finally the connection to the container instance of the database is closed as queries to general view won't be executed anymore.

Next, the query crafting is wrapped in the `buildClusteringQuery` method, including the build of the where condition and its appending to the whole final query

```

private void buildClusteringQuery() throws SQLException,
    ClassNotFoundException, InvalidIndexParametersException {
    if(values_list.size() > 1) {
        condition.setValues(values_list);
    } else {
        this.logger.info("No expected values found in expected
            values table(CHECK_BASE) with the following parameters
            \n db_id : " + resultRowData.getDb() + "\n tb_id : "+
            resultRowData.getTable() +"\n col_id : "+
            resultRowData.getCol());
        throw new InvalidIndexParametersException("No expected

```

```

        values found in expected values table(CHECK_BASE) with
        the following parameters", resultRowData.getDb(),
        resultRowData.getTable(), resultRowData.getCol());
    }
    condition.setCol(targetTableData.getCol());
    checkQuery += condition.getWhere();
}

```

The where condition is build with the previously retrieved values list, after checking that the list actually contains at least one value, which is, by fact, a redundant control since in the previous method the values result set has already been checked in this view.

The WhereCondition object exposes the list of values and the column name that is processed by the current iteration, along with the the relative getter and setter methods. Additionally, both a constructor with only values and one with the column as well is implemented.

```

public class WhereCondition {
    private ArrayList<String> values;
    private String column;
    public WhereCondition(ArrayList<String> values) {
        this.values = values;
    }
    public WhereCondition(ArrayList<String> values, String
        column) {
        super();
        this.values = values;
        this.column = column;
    }
    public String getCol() {
        return column;
    }
    public void setCol(String col) {
        this.column = col;
    }
    public ArrayList<String> getValues() {
        return values;
    }
    public String getValue(int index) {
        return values.get(index);
    }
    public void setValues(ArrayList<String> value) {
        this.values = value;
    }
    public String getWhereBindvar() {
        String where = "";
        for (int i = 0; i < values.size(); i++) {
            if(where.equals(""))
                where += "SELECT ";

```

```

        where += " '?' || sum(case when(TRIM(UPPER(?)) =
            '?' ) then 1 else 0 end) ||';' ||";
    }
    if(!where.equals(""))
        where = where.substring(0, where.length()-7);
        where += " AS "+this.getCol()+"";
return where;
}
public String getWhere() {
    String where = "";
    for (String val : values) {
        if(where.equals(""))
            where += "SELECT ";
        where += " '"+val+":' || sum(case when(TRIM(UPPER
            ("+this.getCol()+")) = '"+val.toUpperCase()+"'
            ";
        where += ") then 1 else 0 end) ||';' ||";
    }
    if(!where.equals(""))
        where = where.substring(0, where.length()-7);
        where += " AS "+this.getCol()+"";
return where;
}
}
}

```

Where Condition Crafting is Implemented in the `getWhere()` method. Essentially, a specialized SQL-like query string that performs aggregation and formatting of results is built leveraging SQL language native constructs and clauses. Its crafting involves the iteration on the values list and for each value creates a CASE expression that counts occurrences of the value in the columns, by performing an SQL comparison with WHEN-THEN-ELSE-END clause, between the column normalized with TRIM and UPPER clauses, and the value likewise normalised with Java String object native methods. Hence, an iteration on all rows is integrated in the expression as the column name resolves to all values in the column, and if the column resolves to the value being checked, the expression resolves to 1, the sum of these resolutions is calculated with the SUM clause and equals by fact to the value occurrences in the column. The output is formatted in a flavor of JSON format : 'value : count ; value : count'. The string 'value:' is concatenated to the whole expression resolution leveraging the SQL '——' text chaining operator, and the whole text is object of selection, with the SELECT clause, finally the result trailing test is removed and the whole text aliased with the column name, the result set is a column with the same name of the column being processed and one row, which contains list of values occurrences in the format 'value : count' separated by ';'. A template of the resultant query is reported

below :

```

SELECT
    'VALUE_1:' ||
SUM(CASE WHEN (TRIM(UPPER('NOME_COL')) = 'VALUE_1') THEN 1
    ELSE 0 END) || ';' ||
    'VALUE_2:' ||
SUM(CASE WHEN (TRIM(UPPER('NOME_COL')) = 'VALUE_2') THEN 1
    ELSE 0 END) || ';' ||
    .....
    ....
    ..
    'VALUE_3:' ||
SUM(CASE WHEN (TRIM(UPPER('NOME_COL')) = 'VALUE_3') THEN 1
    ELSE 0 END) AS NOME_COL

```

All the unusual SQL clauses, operators and constructs are illustrated briefly below :

- CASE : the case statement implements the general Switch-case paradigm, as it chooses from a sequence of conditions and runs a corresponding statement. In this scenario it is used with its searched flavour as defined by Oracle documentation as it evaluates multiple Boolean expressions and chooses the first one whose value is TRUE

Figure 2.22: Execution Diagram Searched Case Statement [20]

- SUM : returns the sum of values of expr. This function takes as an argument any numeric data type or any nonnumeric data type that can be implicitly converted to a numeric data type

Figure 2.23: Execution Diagram Sum Statement [21]

The algorithm workflow proceeds with the execution of this query which features the where condition previously built, with the implementation of the method. `extractColumnEffectiveValuesClusters()`

```
private void extractColumnEffectiveValuesClusters() throws
    ClassNotFoundException, SQLException {
    if(targetTableData.getTech().equals("DB2")) {
        db_addParams = ":securityMechanism=9;
            encryptionAlgorithm=2;defaultIsolationLevel=1;";
    }
    this.targetTableConnection = toolbox.prepareDBConnection(
        databaseType.valueOf(targetTableData.getTech()),
        targetTableData.getHost(), targetTableData.getPort(),
        targetTableData.getSid(), db_addParams,
        targetTableData.getUsr(), targetTableData.getPwd());
    this.logger.info(checkQuery + " FROM " + targetTableData.
        getSchema() + ".\" + targetTableData.getTable() + "\"
    ");
    this.checkQuery += " FROM ?.\"?\"";
    this.valuesClustersResultSet = toolbox.executeQuery(this.
        targetTableConnection, checkQuery, targetTableData.
        getSchema(), targetTableData.getTable());
}
```

It passes exceptions raised by called methods to the outer scope(mask method) which will handle them gracefully as mentioned formerly. If the technology is DB2 a required string is added as additional parameters to execute properly the query. Next, a new connection is established to the target table database instance, if successful the query is first logged to the job logging interface for any future debugging activity and finally executed, appending target table schema and name held by the `targetTableData` object.

The result text in a JSON flavoured format is then parsed. This parsing is implemented in a specific method `parseEffectiveValues()`

```
private void parseEffectiveValues() throws SQLException {
    HashMap<String, String> values = new HashMap<String,
        String>();
    if(this.valuesClustersResultSet != null && this.
        valuesClustersResultSet.next()) {
        while(this.valuesClustersResultSet.next()) {
            if(this.valuesClustersResultSet.
                getString(1).split(";", -1).length-1 != 2 &&
                this.valuesClustersResultSet.getString(1).split(":0",
                    -1).length-1 != condition.getValues().size()) {
                // check verfiica almeno un match
            }
            for (String t:this.valuesClustersResultSet.getString(1).
                split(";")) {
                if(!t.split(":") [1].equals("0"))
                    values.put(t.split(":") [0], t.split(":") [1]);
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```

    }
    } else {
        this.valuesClustersResultSet.close();
        this.logger.info("neither one match found or ':'; bug
            occurred in results writing, raise problem to
            support");
        writeEffectiveValues("neither one match found or ':';
            bug occurred in results writing, raise problem to
            support");
    }
    }
    retrievedValuesClusters.putAll(values);
    this.valuesClustersResultSet.close();
    writeEffectiveValues();
    } else {
        this.logger.info("error in query to retrieve
            effective values execution");
        writeEffectiveValues("error in query to retrieve
            effective values execution");
    }
}
}

```

nitially, a temporary HashMap type data structure for processed values is initialised. the result set is checked for it's validity and not emptiness, in such scenario a detailed description of the faulty scenario is both logged to the job logging interface and written in the result column though the method writeEffectiveValues(), result set and connection are then detached. Likewise, if the format validation isn't passed or no expected value has neither one occurrence, detailed description of the faulty scenario is both logged to the job logging interface and written in the result column always though the method writeEffectiveValues(). Contrarily, if checks are passed, results are processed, splitting based on elements and values separator, ',' and ':', values with zero occurrences are filtered out while values with at least one occurrence are encoded as key-value pairs in the temporary HashMap. Finally the Java native JSON object retrievedValuesClusters is valued with the crafted HashMap and the result set is detached.

Finally results are assigned to the data structure referencing the genericData object, along with a date-time timestamp. This final write is implemented in the writeEffectiveValues() method.

```

private void writeEffectiveValues() throws SQLException {

this.resultRowData.getResult().setValue(ByteBuffer.wrap(
    retrievedValuesClusters.toJSONString().getBytes(
        StandardCharsets.UTF_8)));
    this.resultRowData.getTimestamp().setValue(LocalDateTime.
        now());
}

```

```

        toolbox.closeConnection(this.targetTableConnection);
    }
    // faulty scenario, description of the error is written
    private void writeEffectiveValues(String errorString) throws
        SQLException {
        this.resultRowData.getResult().
            setValue(ByteBuffer.wrap(errorString.getBytes(
                StandardCharsets.UTF_8)));
        this.resultRowData.getTimestamp().setValue(LocalDateTime.now
            ());
        toolbox.closeConnection(this.targetTableConnection);
    }
}

```

Similarly to some of the previous depicted methods, two version of the method are defined in order to handle both contrary scenarios. If it is called with a string as argument the latter is executed, otherwise the former. Nevertheless, the execution logic is specular, assign results or error through the data structure referencing genericData, assign timestamp and close the connection. Since the result property(GenericData) has been declared as Byte Object, the results or error string must undergo a specific data transformation sequence before being actually assigned to genericData, which involves converting retrievedValuesClusters to JSON string, encoding the JSON string to UTF-8 bytes and wrapping bytes in a ByteBuffer for efficient handling. Once the mask method returns the genericData object, Delphix engine will apply its properties values to the corresponding columns in the results table.

Service Discovery

Java service discovery is used to determine which classes in the plugin JAR present relevant functionality to the Delphix Masking Engine. When a plugin is loaded, the file com.delphix.masking.api.plugin.MaskingComponent under META-INF/services in the JAR is consulted for a list of classes that implement the MaskingComponent interface. As MaskingAlgorithm includes this interface, each algorithm in the plugin will be discovered this way. If an algorithm class is missing from the services file, it will not be usable when the plugin is loaded. It is essentially invisible to the extensibility framework. If a class is mentioned in this file but not present in the JAR, the plugin will fail to load [6]. Hence such a file has been created in META-INF/services directory containing the value 'com.sample.RansomCheck' which is java format path to the file hosting the class that implements the MaskingAlgorithm interface.

Plugin Security

Plugin design and implementation considered to an high degree security concerns, as demonstrated by the hefty error handling part across the whole codebase. Faulty scenarios are mainly related to null data, or discrepancies between code expected and processed data types.

During execution, all plugin code is sandboxed using the Java Security Manager, being run with a Delphix defined security police [7]. Plugins are granted all permissions except for few non-FilePermission like :

- Communication to localhost through sockets : the `java.net.SocketPermission` class can't accept, connect, listen or resolve connection with target localhost and any port.
- VM settings modification : the `java.lang.RuntimePermission` class methods `exitVM`, `createClassLoader`, `AccessClassInPackage.sun` and `setSecurityManager` can't be called
- Security Police modification : the `java.security.SecurityPermission` class methods `setPolicy` and `setProperty.package.access` can't be called.

Whereas, regarding file permissions read access is granted to all, though write is only allowed for the masking user's home directory (`System.getProperty("user.home")`) and the JVM's default temp directory (`System.getProperty("java.io.tmpdir")`) [7]. The JSON document describing the configuration of each algorithm is stored encrypted on the Continuous Compliance Engine, and the actual values are made visible only to users with access privileges through the UI and web API.

The whole codebase, both production and testing, can be consulted at the following public GitHub repository [13]

Life cycle of custom algorithms loaded through plugins

In the following paragraphs, the steps involved to execute the custom algorithm, once uploaded to the engine, are depicted. As mentioned, compliance engine feature an extendibility framework, which handle plugins from uploading to execution of contained algorithm. It relies on multiple software components, illustrated formerly, which are required to be implemented by the plugin. Three main phases in the life cycle of a plugin can be distinguished, from the engine outlook :

Plugin discovery: the extensibility framework evaluates the capabilities present in a class implementing the `MaskingAlgorithm` interface :

1. Java object creation - an object of the algorithm class is created
2. `getName` - determines framework name
3. `getDescription` - determines framework description
4. `getDefaultInstances` - determines all plugin-provided algorithm instances. For each instance:
 - (a) `getName` - determines instance name

- (b) getDescription - determines instance description
 - (c) validate - ensure object passes validation
 - (d) Serialize configurable fields - these are saved as a JSON document defining the instance's configuration
 - (e) Disposal - the Java object is discarded
5. getAllowFurtherInstances - determines whether the framework is visible in the algorithm/framework API endpoint
 6. Disposal - the Java object is discarded

Algorithm configuration: a new instance of a plugin algorithm framework is created by uploading a configuration file. The algorithm definition is saved only if each step succeeds.

1. Java object creation - an object of the algorithm class is created
2. Configuration injection - the values in the user-provided JSON document are injected into the object
3. validate - the object's validate method is called
4. Disposal - the Java object is discarded

Algorithm use: finally the algorithm object is used to mask data.

1. Java object creation - an object of the algorithm class is created
2. Configuration injection - the saved JSON document defining this instance is injected in the object
3. setup - the setup method is called once
4. mask - the mask method is called on each value to be masked
5. tearDown - the tearDown method is called once
6. Disposal - the Java object is discarded

2.5 Orchestration Appliance

The beating heart of this solution is with no surprise the orchestration unit. This unit has been properly developed to talk with all engines through their REST API to trigger replication to the control site, refresh of virtual database and control execution. Then, it executes a fundamental final query to evaluate control results and extract discrepancies. Eventually, if an amount of discrepancies higher than custom predefined threshold is revealed it alerts all stakeholders through pre-configured medias and delete the latest virtualised

data snapshot from the data engine in source site, otherwise data engine is instructed to provision fast recovery database. It plays a key role as it is the component enabling a full detection and response automation. The orchestration directives, being centralised, allow a central management. It has been purposefully built to offer a central point of management of the integrity control and set a proper context for any future expansion to further controls, of different kind. This is also the main reason why it couldn't be implemented leveraging technologies, natively built for orchestration (Jenkins, Github Actions, GitLab CI).

Being an appliance whose purpose is to orchestrate a process, implementing a workflow which handles all scenarios, the computational consumption is rather low and it is limited to the monitoring of single tasks execution. Besides in the scenario of several discrepancies revealed, where a result set with multiple rows must be parse to extract actual values and write them along with the column in the report, in such case an high speed is required to trigger the attack response as soon as possible.

The design and implementation choices made guarantee reliability, security (both of data processed and executive), efficiency (both in term of memory capacity and compute time), interoperability, flexibility and indeed scalability. With this outlook, the appliance has been implemented in Python, fully functionally tested for Python3.9+ with version 3.12.8 highly recommended for seamless integration with dependant modules used version. It has been implemented and tested on a 64-bit ARM machine with Ubuntu 22.04, and even though it is meant to be always hosted on such machine, the final artifact is wrapped in a container which replicated the settings of the machine and include all its dependencies, being by fact a stand-alone package. Python has been chosen for its simplicity, readability, ease of integration, rich standard library and ecosystem, including its backing community which provide a wide range of modules and frameworks, but first of all for its by design affinity to automation and scripting contexts. These characteristics allowed myself to implement a solution that features :

- Complete flexibility to the target database technology and architecture, leveraging third party database API modules maintained by the community to communicate with any Oracle, PostgreSQL, MySQL, Microsoft SQL or IBM database, and easily extendible with any other technology. All these modules are compliant to PEP-249 specification for database API design.
- High degree of observability in the process by being transparent to the execution of tasks committed to peers, showing their progress and logging all steps. Furthermore, discrepancies are listed reported in a

report file, with an high level of detail. All control cycles are archived in a local lightweight database, along with results and optionally name of file listing discrepancies, which contains the timestamp of creation.

- Deep discrepancies details. Once any discrepancy is revealed, it is written in a report file, in order to archive controls even if the number of discrepancies does not overtake the alert threshold. The discrepancy description includes indexing including database, table and column name along with expected and actual number of occurrences.
- General purpose database control extendibility. The class implementing the integrity control extends a general lower level control class, which exposes a constructor, start and finish methods. Controls are wrapped in a dedicated method which call start and finish of the passed method, abstracting the control workflow, enabling the implementation of any control process.
- Exhaustive coverage of unexpected and faulty scenarios, gracefully handling with proper exceptions providing an high degree of error details.
- Configurability : as introduced the unit set itself to be a framework configurable based on target resource(s) details and control needs. Hence, control details are provided in configuration file in JSON format. Depicted in the following paragraphs

Indeed, similarly to the masking plugin, aforementioned design best practices(SOLID) are ensured, with a particular attention to modularity.

In the following picture the appliance components architecture, along with testing components is depicted

Figure 2.24: orchestration appliance architecture

Third Party Modules

Starting with third party modules, package management during development has been employed with pip module, therefore packages are all retrieved from the public de-facto standard repository Python Package Index(PyPi). Given Python version 3.12.8, for all packages, the source code distribution is retrieved, besides for the PostgreSQL database API module(psycopg2-binary), whereby, in order to resolve dependencies collisions, the pre-compiled binaries distribution(.so) is retrieved. In the following picture all used modules and their dependencies are listed, along with the tested version. These versions have been tested for compatibility with Python3.9+.

```
certifi==2025.1.31
cffi==1.17.1
charset-normalizer==3.4.1
cryptography==44.0.2
ibm_db==3.2.6
idna==3.10
iniconfig==2.0.0
mysql-connector-python==9.2.0
oracledb==3.0.0
packaging==24.2
pluggy==1.5.0
progress==1.6
psycopg-binary==3.2.5
psycopg-pool==3.2.6
psycopg2-binary==2.9.10
pycparser==2.22
pymssql==2.3.2
pytest==8.3.5
python-dateutil==2.9.0.post0
requests==2.32.3
setuptools==76.0.0
six==1.17.0
typing_extensions==4.12.2
urllib3==2.3.0
```

Configuration Data

As mentioned formerly, the appliance set itself to be a framework, hence one of its core feature is configurability. Configurability is employed through a configuration file and initial parsing of its data. The configuration file follows JSON format and allows to declare a list of controls, taken from the implementation list. The implementation list effectively “as is” contains only the data integrity control which requires at least two Delphix engines, with pre-configured dataset replication, virtual database refresh and data masking jobs. Depicted below is the template of the configuration file

```
{
```

```

    "dpx_engines" : {
        "source_engines": List[data_engine],
        "vault_engines": List[data_engine],
        "discovery_engines": List[compliance_engine]
    },
    "vdfs_control" : List[target_database],
    "mail": [MailObject],
    "Controls": List[control]
}
-----

```

```

<data_engine> : {
    "data_1": {
        "host": String,
        "apiVersion" : String,
        "usr" : String,
        "pwd" : String
    }
}

<compliance_engine> : {
    "compl_13" : {
        "host": String,
        "usr" : String,
        "pwd" : String
    }
}

<target_database> : {
    "control1" : {
        "host": String,
        "port": Integer,
        "sid": String,
        "tech" : String,
        "usr" : String,
        "pwd" : String,
        "addParams" : String
    }
}

```

```

<MailObject> : {
    "smtpServer": String,
    "usr": String,
    "pwd": String
}

```

```

<control> : {
    "ID" : Integer,
    "name" : String,
}

```

```

        "vdbRef" : String,
        "mailReceivers": List[String]
    }

<control>:<integrity_control> : {
    "ID" : Integer,
    "name" : String,
    "sourceEngine" : String,
    "vaultEngine" : String,
    "discEngine" : String,
    "vdb" : String,
    "procedures" : List[String],
    "expected_proc" : String,
    "replicationSpec": String,
    "vdbContainerControl": String,
    "vdbContainerRecovery" : String,
    "dSourceContainer": String,
    "jobId": Integer,
    "max_discrepancies" : Integer,
    "mailReceivers": List[String]
}

```

As shown the configuration features two macro parts, resources required for control(“dpx_engines”, “vdbs_control”, “mail”) and control details(“controls”). These declarations outline the general control paradigm : Delphix data infrastructure composed of three engine(source, vault and discovery) for data management, one virtual target database where data to be controlled is archived and the networking details of the mail server used to send alerts. Each single control implementation is built upon these details. Delphix engines are grouped in three main categories according to their role in the architecture, illustrated in previous chapter, each category is a list of engine. This design choice has been taken to model robust control infrastructures, which require an high throughput or multiple data streams of different nature, which could be potentially handled differently. As described previously, both source and vault engine are Continuous Data engines and expose networking details to establish an HTTP session with them, along the engine API version; whereas the discovery engine is a Continuous Compliance engine which expose only networking details. Likewise target databases are implemented as a list to model data stored across multiple databases or contained tenants. Instead, control details are modelled with a general control object which exposes the properties that all kind of control must implement(ID, name, and alert mail addresses), then single controls may present multiple additional attributes required by the introspective control features and infrastructure resources, as showcased in the current control configuration. The integrity control, exposes :

- Source engine name (sourceEngineRef) : reference to one of the source engines in the respective list
- Vault engine name (vaultEngineRef) : reference to one of the vault engines in the respective list
- Discovery engine name (discEngineRef) : reference to one of the discovery engines in the respective list
- Virtual database name (vdbRef) : reference to one of the virtual databases in the respective list
- Replication job identification (replicationSpec) : name of the replication job in the source engine
- Virtual database identification (vdbContainerRef) : name assigned to the target virtual database on the vault engine
- Source data set identification (dsourceContainerRef) : name assigned to the compressed data(dSource) replicated to the control site, on the vault engine, required to fetch latest snapshot
- Masking Job ID(jodId) : ID of the masking job with the custom algorithm on the discovery engine
- List of recipient mail addresses(mailReceivers) : list of email addresses that should receive the alert mail

The production configuration file won't be reported to avoid the disclosing of client sensitive data **Source Code**

In the following paragraphs, code snippets, both classes and singular core methods, will be illustrated, according to the control execution workflow, deepening in peculiar fundamental technical concepts.

Hence, the starting point is depicted below

```

cfg_dict = load_config()
for ctrl in cfg_dict.get('Controls'):
    try:
        ctrl_factory = controlFactory(controlClass=ctrl.
            get('name'))
        rcheck = ctrl_factory.instance_control(
            control_data=ctrl, cfg_data=cfg_dict)
        controlDatabase(rcheck)
    except Exception as e:
        print((str(e) if str(e) else f"Error executing
            control {ctrl.get('control')} : \n Error : {e}
            "))

```

```

        continue
    os.system('clear')
    print("Controls Terminated")

```

Indeed, the execution starts with the parsing of the configuration json file, through a specifically crafted utility method 'load_config()'

```

def load_config():
    try:
        with open('config.json', 'r') as cfg:
            cfg_dict = json_load(cfg)
        return cfg_dict
    except Exception as e:
        print(f"Error opening config: {str(e)}")

```

Inside the context created by opening the configuration file with the python built in open procedure, it is deserialized leveraging JSON standard library load method, aliased as json_load. It essentially returns a dictionary which models the configuration file elements, hence it will have controls, dpx_engines, vdbs_control and mail keys whose values are further dictionaries, and so on all nested dictionaries represent all the configuration data.

Following the parsing, all retrieved controls, and therefore the whole execution is wrapped in a loop that first instantiate the control through a specifically crafted factory class and then effectively execute the instantiated control within the controlDatabase method. The control factory class responsibility is to strengthen the framework polymorphism by instantiating a control instance according to the retrieved control name.

```

class controlFactory:
    def __init__(self, controlName : str):
        self.control = controlName
    def instance_control(self, control_data : dict, cfg_data
: dict) -> None:
        try:
            match self.control.strip().lower():
                case 'ransomcheck': return ransomCheck(
                    control_data=control_data, cfg_data=
                    cfg_data)
                case _: # Default case to handle any
                    unmatched control type
                    raise Exception(f"Control {self.control}
                        not supported")
        except Exception as e:
            raise Exception(f"Error creating control instance {
                self.control}. \n Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e
                }")

```

This design employs the factory pattern : the framework delegates the creation of controls to the factory, which based on the control name a control-

kind of factory is instantiated, and the respective control is then instantiated. The general factory expose a method which returns sub-classes(RansomCheck) that implement the general lower level ControlClass

```
class ControlClass(ABC):

    @abstractmethod
    def __init__(self, data: dict) -> None:
        return

    @abstractmethod
    def start(self) -> None:
        return
```

All control sub-classes must implement the constructor, control start and finish methods. Below is reported the implementation of the constructor by RansomCheck, called within the factory instantiation method.

```
class RansomCheck(ControlClass):

    def __init__(self, control_data: dict, cfg_data: dict) ->
        None:

        for key, val in control_data.items():
            setattr(self, key, val)
        try:
            self.initialize_objs(cfg_data=cfg_data)
        except Exception as e:
            raise Exception((str(e) if str(e) else f"Error
                initializing engines. \n Error : {e}"))
```

The core class which exposes methods that implement the effective integrity check phases, 'RansomCheck', present a constructor that process two dictionaries, respectively control type specific details and all required resources details. First, control-specific details are assigned to the object leveraging the python built-in method setattr(), then all objects modelling required resources are instantiated and referenced by an object attribute, through the class method initialize_objs

```
def initialize_objs(self, cfg_data: dict) -> None:
    try:
        cfg_source_engines = cfg_data.get('dpx_engines').get(
            'source_engines')
        cfg_vault_engines = cfg_data.get('dpx_engines').get(
            'vault_engines')
        cfg_disc_engines = cfg_data.get('dpx_engines').get(
            'discovery_engines')
        cfg_vdbs_control = cfg_data.get('vdbs_control')
```

```

if not (isinstance(cfg_source_engines, dict) and
        isinstance(cfg_vault_engines, dict) and isinstance(
            cfg_disc_engines, dict) and isinstance(
                cfg_vdbs_control, dict)):
    raise Exception("Engines are not configured
                    properly in config file")

for key, val in cfg_source_engines.items():
    if key == self.sourceEngine:
        self.source_engine = DelphixEngine(
            decrypt_value(val['host']))
        self.source_engine.create_session(val['
            apiVersion'])
        self.source_engine.login_data(
            decrypt_value(val['usr']),
            decrypt_value(val['pwd']))

for key, val in cfg_vault_engines.items():
    if key == self.vaultEngine:
        self.vault_engine = DelphixEngine(
            decrypt_value(val['host']))
        self.vault_engine.create_session(val['
            apiVersion'])
        self.vault_engine.login_data(
            decrypt_value(val['usr']),
            decrypt_value(val['pwd']))

for key, val in cfg_disc_engines.items():
    if key == self.discEngine:
        self.disc_engine = DelphixEngine(
            decrypt_value(val['host']))
        self.disc_engine.login_compliance(
            decrypt_value(val['usr']),
            decrypt_value(val['pwd']))

for key, val in cfg_vdbs_control.items():
    if key == self.vdb:
        if isinstance(val, dict):
            self.vdb_target = val.copy()
            self.vdb_target.tech = DBConnector.
                get_technology(self.vdb_target.tech)
        else:
            raise Exception(f"Error in config data:
                            missing or wrong formatted vdb control
                            details")

if isinstance(cfg_data.get('mail'), dict):
    self.mail = cfg_data.get('mail').copy()
else:

```

```

        raise Exception(f"Error in config data: missing
            mail details")

except AttributeError as e:
    raise Exception(f"Error initializing engines. Invalid
        config, missing parameter in control data")
except Exception as e:
    raise Exception(f"Error initializing engines. \n
        Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e}")

```

It process a dictionary with further nested dictionaries and besides checking for a proper data formatting, it retrieves and instantiate the referenced source, vault, discovery engines and target virtual database. For each engine, a session is established and authentication is performed. Below are reported related engines class methods along with the constructor.

```

class DelphixEngine:
    def __init__(self, ip: str):
        self.ip = ip
        self.base_uri = f"https://{ip}"
        self.session = Session()
        header = {
            "Content-Type": "application/json"
        }
        self.session.headers.update(header)

def create_session(self, api_version: str) -> Dict:
    uri = r"resources/json/delphix/session"
    major, minor, micro = api_version.split('.')
    data = {
        "type": "APISession",
        "version": {
            "type": "APIVersion",
            "major": int(major),
            "minor": int(minor),
            "micro": int(micro)
        }
    }
    try:
        response = self._post(uri, data)
        return response.json()
    except RequestException as e:
        raise Exception(f"error creating session version {
            api_version} with engine {self.ip}, bad request
            likely. Response received {e.response}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"error creating session version {
            api_version} with engine {self.ip} \n Error : {str
            (e) if str(e) else e}")

```

For continuous data engines sessions are established through an HTTP post request to the endpoint provided in the documentation, leveraging Session class from requests library, which models an http session. In the body of the request, API version is declared.

```
def _post(self, uri: str, data: Optional[Dict] = None, key:
Optional[str] = None) -> Dict:
    api = f"{self.base_uri}/{uri}"
    try:
        response = self.session.post(api, json=data, verify=
False)
    except RequestException as e:
        raise RequestException(response=e.response)
    if "Authorization" in self.session.headers or uri == "
masking/api/login":
        if not response.ok or "errorMessage" in response.json
():
            raise Exception(f"{uri}: {response.json()}\ndata:
{data} \n code : {response.status_code}")
        elif not response.ok or response.json().get('status')
== 'ERROR':
            raise Exception(f"{uri}: {response.json()}\ndata:
{data}")
    return response
```

This method is strictly mean for internal use in the class and shouldn't be called by external classes, it wraps requests library 'post' method, crafting the uri and handling gracefully any faulty scenario with constructs try-catch, the object modelling the http response is returned.

Two similar methods are implemented to perform authentication to both types of engines.

```
def login_data(self, username: str, password: str) -> Dict:
    uri = r"resources/json/delphix/login"
    data = {
        'type': 'LoginRequest',
        'username': username.strip(),
        'password': password.strip(),
        'target': 'DOMAIN'
    }
    try:
        response = self._post(uri, data)
        return response
    except RequestException as e:
        raise Exception(f"error logging in data engine {self.
ip}, bad request likely. Response received {e.
response}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"error logging in data engine {self.
```

```

        ip} \n Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e}")

def login_compliance(self, username: str, password: str) ->
str:
    uri = "masking/api/login"
    data = {
        'username': username.strip(),
        'password': password.strip()
    }
    try:
        response = self._post(uri, data)
        self.session.headers.update({'Authorization':
            response.json()["Authorization"]})
        return response.json()["Authorization"]
    except RequestException as e:
        raise Exception(f"error logging in compliance engine
            {self.ip}, Bad request likely. Response received {
            e.response}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"error logging in compliance engine
            \n Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e}")

```

In both methods, login request uri and payload are crafted, before sending the post request, though while for the continuous data engine the response is simply returned, for the compliance the authorization header is parsed to retrieve the authentication token used in subsequent requests, basically a bearer token encoded in base64, adhering to REST API standard, as explained in the Delphix engine overview.

Hence, once the control object has been completely instantiated, it is passed to the controlDatabase method, an utility method which provide a further level of abstraction, as it calls the starting point of all controls(start)

```

def controlDatabase(check):
    print(f"Starting control {check.name} ")
    s_time = datetime.now()
    try :
        check.start()
        f_time = datetime.now()
        os.system('clear')
        print(f"Finished control {check.name} in {f_time -
            s_time} seconds")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(msg=(e.msg if e.hasattr('msg') else f
            "Error executing control {check.name}: \n Error :
            {e}"))
        raise Exception(f"{str(e) if str(e) else f"Error
            executing control {check.name}: \n Error : {e}"}")

```

It's sole responsibility is to set a context for the control, including start e finish time for analysis.

The start procedure is the execution starting point and all controls must implement it

```
try:
    self.source_engine.replication(self.replicationSpec)
    self.vault_engine.refresh_control_vdb(self.
        vdbContainerControl, self.dSourceContainer)
    self.update_catalogs()
    self.disc_engine.mask(self.jobId)
    self.evaluate()
    if len(self.discrepant_values) > self.max_discrepancies:
        self.register_report()
        self.create_report()
        self.send_alert()
        self.source_engine.delete_latest_snap(self.
            dSourceContainer)
        self.register_discrepancies()
        self.stop()
    else:
        self.source_engine.refresh_recovery_db(self.
            vdbContainerRecovery)
        self.update_expected_values()
        if not len(self.discrepant_values)==0:
            self.register_report()
            self.create_report()
            self.register_discrepancies()
            self.backup_report()
except Exception as e:
    raise Exception(f"Error executing control. \n Error : {(
        str(e) if str(e) else e)}")
```

The list of methods wrapped within this method implement the various control steps with the same degree of granularity used formerly in the control process.

Hence, as explained the control starts with the replication of the dataset in the control scope to the control site.

```
def replication(self, reference: str) -> None:
    uri_repExe = rf"resources/json/delphix/replication/spec/{
        reference}/execute"
    uri_SourceState = r"resources/json/delphix/replication/
        sourcestate"
    try:
        job_id = (self._post(uri_repExe)).json()['job']
        uri_jobId = rf"resources/json/delphix/job/{job_id}"

        with IncrementalBar(message=rf"Preparing replication
```

```

        job {(self._get(uri_jobId, key='result'))['target
        ']}", suffix='%(%(index)d/%(max)d [%(elapsed)d / %(
        eta)d / %(eta_td)s] (%(iter_value)s)', color='blue
        ', max=100) as bar:
            while self.filter_by_string(self._get(
                uri_SourceState, key="result"), reference,
                "spec")[0]["activePoint"] is None:
                bar.next(1)
    with IncrementalBar(message=rf"Waiting for
    replication {(self._get(uri_jobId, key='result'))
    ['target']} to finish", suffix='%(%(index)d/%(max)d
    [%(elapsed)d / %(eta)d / %(eta_td)s] (%(iter_value
    )s)', color='blue', max=100) as bar:
        while self.filter_by_string(self._get(
            uri_SourceState, key="result"), reference, "
            spec")[0]["activePoint"] is not None:
            bar.next(1)
except RequestException as e:
    raise Exception(f"error executing replication job,
    Bad request likely. Response received {e.response}
    ")
except Exception as e:
    raise Exception(f"error executing replication job \n
    Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e}")

```

All methods that implement engines operations execution follow the same pattern, initially the required endpoints URI of the engine API are declared, a get or post request is sent with internal formerly covered methods and with the job ID returned in the response by the engine the job execution is monitored. Additionally, to offer a better user experience, the job execution is showed with a progress bar, implemented leveraging the progress module. Next, the target database is refreshed with the received virtual dataset.

```

def refresh_control_vdb(self, vdb_ref: str, dSource_ref: str)
-> None:
    uri_snap = rf"resources/json/delphix/capacity/snapshot"
    uri_refresh = rf"resources/json/delphix/database/{vdb_ref
    }/refresh"
    try:
        self.snaps = self.filter_by_string(self._get(uri_snap
            , key="result"), dSource_ref, "container")

        data = {
            "type": "OracleRefreshParameters",
            "timeflowPointParameters": {
                "type": "TimeflowPointSnapshot",
                "snapshot": self.snaps[0]['snapshot']
            }
        }
    }

```

```

        job_id = (self._post(uri_refresh, data)).json()['job'
        ]
        uri_jobId = rf"resources/json/delphix/job/{job_id}"

        with IncrementalBar(message=rf"Waiting for refresh of
            {vdb_ref} to finish", suffix='%(index)d/%(max)d
            [%(\elapsed)d / %(eta)d / %(eta_td)s] (%(iter_value)
            s)', color='blue', max=100) as bar:
            while self._get(uri_jobId, key="result")['
                jobState'] != "COMPLETED":
                bar.next(1)
    except RequestException as e:
        raise Exception(f"error executing vdb refreshing
            job, Bad request likely. Response received {e.
            response}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"error executing vdb refreshing
            job \n Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e}")

```

This involves, first fetching the id of the latest data set snapshot, which is used also in some following methods.

Once the latest source data snapshot has been provisioned to the control virtual database, all catalogs must be updated, as the new data set could have new data repositories or removed some. As illustrated formerly, the update of such catalogs is executed by stored procedures on the database. Triggering the execution of these procedures is implemented in a specific method

```

def update_catalogs(self):
    try:
        with self.vdb_target.tech(**self.vdb_target) as
            db_conn:
            for proc in self.procedures:
                db_conn.execute_procedure(proc_name=proc)
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error refreshing catalogs by
            triggering execution of stored procedures \n Error
            : {e} ")

```

Just like with any other connection to the control database, the dictionary with database networking details is unpacked, with this data is created the database connector object whose class is referenced by the property 'tech' of the vdb_target dictionary, contained method 'execute_procedure' is covered later.

Next, the custom masking algorithm, against expected values calculated at step t-1, is triggered.

```

def mask(self, jobId: str) -> None:
    uri = "masking/api/executions"
    data = { "jobId": jobId }
    try:
        execId = self._post(uri, data).json()['executionId']
        uriExec = rf"masking/api/executions/{execId}"

        with IncrementalBar(message=rf"Waiting for control to
            finish", suffix='%(index)d/%(max)d [%](elapsed)d /
            %(eta)d / %(eta_td)s] %(iter_value)s)', color='
            blue', max=100) as bar:
            while self._get(uriExec, key="status") == "
                RUNNING":
                bar.next(1)

        if self._get(uriExec, key="status") == "SUCCEEDED":
            print(rf"Control completed successfully")
        elif self._get(uriExec, key="status") == "FAILED":
            print(rf"Error encountered during Control")
            raise Exception(f"values control job with
                discovery engine failed. Check delphix
                dashboard")
    except RequestException as e:
        raise Exception(f"error executing masking job to
            check values, Bad request likely. Response
            received {e.response}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"error executing masking job to
            check values \n Error : {str(e) if str(e) else
            e}")

```

Finally, the algorithm results are evaluated against expected values

```

def evaluate(self) -> None:
    try:
        start_time = datetime.now()
        with self.vdb_target.tech(**self.vdb_target) as
            db_conn:
            self.discrepant_values = db_conn.execute_query(
                query=
                """
                SELECT DB_NAME, TABLE_NAME, COLUMN_NAME, VALUE, result,
                RES_ATTESO FROM \
                ( SELECT DB_NAME, TABLE_NAME, COLUMN_NAME, VALUE, result,
                RES_ATTESO, \
                CASE WHEN CAST(result AS VARCHAR(200)) = RES_ATTESO THEN 1
                ELSE 0 END AS EVALUATION \
                FROM C##control_user.CHECK_BASE CB LEFT JOIN ( \
                WITH numbers AS( \
                SELECT LEVEL AS n \

```

```

FROM DUAL \
CONNECT BY LEVEL <= 1000) \
SELECT ID, DATABASE_ID, TABLE_ID, COLUMN_ID, REGEXP_SUBSTR(
    REGEXP_SUBSTR(RESULT, '\w+\d+)', 1, n), \
'\w+\d+') as chiavi, \
REGEXP_SUBSTR(REGEXP_SUBSTR(RESULT, '\w+\d+', 1, n), '\w+\d+') as result \
FROM C##control_user.CHECK_2, numbers \
WHERE n <= REGEXP_COUNT(RESULT, '\w+\d+') \
ORDER BY ID, n ) CR ON CB.VALUE = CAST(CR.chiavi AS VARCHAR
(200)) AND CB.ID_CHECK = CR.ID \
JOIN CHECK_VIEW_2 CV2 ON CB.ID_CHECK = CV2.ID) WHERE
EVALUATION = 0")
""",
        all=True)
end_time = datetime.now()
print(f"Discrepancies evaluation finished in {end_time -
start_time}")
except Exception as e:
    raise Exception(f"Couldn't evaluate discrepancies in the
target database \n : {e}")

```

The sophisticated query developed for the evaluation, includes multiple nested queries and ephemeral datasets. Starting from the most nested query

```

WITH numbers AS( \
SELECT LEVEL AS n \
FROM DUAL \
CONNECT BY LEVEL <= 100000) \
SELECT ID, DATABASE_ID, TABLE_ID, COLUMN_ID, REGEXP_SUBSTR
(REGEXP_SUBSTR(RESULT, '\w+\d+', 1, n), '\w+\d+') as chiavi, \
REGEXP_SUBSTR(REGEXP_SUBSTR(RESULT, '\w+\d+', 1, n), '\w+\d+') as result \
FROM C##control_user.CHECK_2, numbers \
WHERE n <= REGEXP_COUNT(RESULT, '\w+\d+') \
ORDER BY ID, n )

```

The result of an inner join between :

- A selection that involves parsing values and occurrences.
- A pseudo table built leveraging Oracle virtual table DUAL, with the clause CONNECT BY which generates a sequence of rows using the pseudo column LEVEL that indicates the level number of a node in a tree structure

An essential role is played by the REGEXP_SUBSTR clause which extracts from the source data some text based on a pattern declared with a regex

expression, n times, with n being initially set to 100.000 and then reduced to the number of distinct values across all column in the scope(indexed in CHECK_2). Finally results are ordinated according to ID and the index of a value in the list(LEVEL) in order to group all values in the same column and additionally order them according to their appearance in the result column.

Figure 2.25: REGEXP_SUBSTR clause syntax diagram [22]

The result is the 'CHECK_RESULTS' ephemeral table illustrated formerly, which is inner joined with expected values table(CHECK_BASE) on row ID of results table and value; subsequently joined with database general view(CHECK_VIEW_2). From the result of these nested joins are selected only rows with discrepancies among values occurrences and all required columns to detail the report.

Within the evaluate method is leveraged a polymorphic database connector, implemented for this use case.

```
class DBConnector(ABC):
    def __init__(self, host: str, port: int, sid: str, tech:
str, usr: str, pwd: str):
        self.hostname_or_ip = host
        self.port = port
        self.username = usr
        self.password = pwd
        self.sid = sid
        self.tech = tech
        self.connection = None
        self.cursor = None
    def __enter__(self):
        try:
            self.connection = self.connect()
            self.cursor = self.connection.cursor()
        except Exception as e:
            logging.error(e, exc_info=True)
            raise Exception(f"Connection to the target
database failed \n {e} \n {type(e)}") from e
    def __exit__(self, *kwargs):
        self.connection.close()
```

The adopted paradigm requires the creation of a python context, to establish a connection. As in the method built in method `__enter__`, called when a context of this class is created, the connection is established by the `connect()` method implemented by sub-classes, which are PEP-249 compliant, for reference below is reported oracle connector implementation

```
class OracleConnector(DBConnector):

    def connect(self):
        connection = oracle_connect(
            host=self.hostname_or_ip,
            port=self.port,
            user=self.username,
            password=self.password,
            sid=self.sid,
        )
        return connection
```

Whereas the method that implement query execution and results parsing mechanism is shared among all sub-classes as property of the general connector class

```
def execute_query(self, query: str, all: bool = False,
                 fetchsize: int = None, *variables: list) -> object:
    try:
        self.cursor.execute(query, variables)
        if all:
            return self.cursor.fetchall()
        elif fetchsize and fetchsize > 1:
            results = self.cursor.fetchmany(fetchsize)
            while results:
                for r in results:
                    yield r
                results = self.cursor.fetchmany(NUM_LINES)
        else:
            r = self.cursor.fetchone()
            yield r
    except Exception as e:
        logging.error(e, exc_info=True)
    finally:
        self.cursor.close()
```

For an optimal memory usage rows are returned through a generator using native procedure yield, unless the arg 'all' is passed True. It allows also to define a fetch size to process data in batches of that size, always in order to improve memory management with large result set.

Following the algorithm results evaluation, according to the number of retrieved discrepant values, two branch of execution can be distinguished. If the number of discrepancies is higher than the pre defined threshold, first the discrepancies report file is registered in the local persistent layer, implemented with a lightweight SQLite database, which features two tables, reports and discrepancies table, which are related by the report id.

```
def register_report(self) -> None:
    self.report_file_name = f"discrepancies_{datetime.now().
                             strftime('%d_%m_%Y-%H_%M_%S')}"
    try:
        self.connect_local_db(file_name='reports.db')
        cursor = self.db_conn.cursor()
    except InterfaceError or sqlite_error as e:
        if self.db_conn:
            self.db_conn.rollback()

    try:
        self.connect_local_db(file_name='reports.db')
        self.register_report()
```

```

        except sqlite_error as e:
            raise Exception((str(e) if str(e) else f"
                Error getting cursor from db connection: {
                e}"))
    try:
        processing_status = "REPORT TO BE GENERATED"
        cursor.execute('''
INSERT INTO reports (report_name,
    processing_status, created_at)
VALUES (:report_name, :processing_status, :
    created_at)
''', {
    'report_name': self.report_file_name,
    'processing_status': processing_status,
    'created_at': datetime.now().strftime('%d_%m_
        %Y-%H_%M_%S'),
    })
        self.report_id = cursor.lastrowid
    except sqlite_error as e:
        if self.db_conn:
            self.db_conn.rollback()
        try:
            self.connect_local_db(file_name='reports.db')
            self.register_report()
        except sqlite_error as e:
            raise Exception((str(e) if str(e) else f"
                Error registering reports: {e}"))

```

Next, the report file listing discrepancies with a level of detail that include database, table and column is created

```

def create_report(self) -> None:
    try:
        if not path.exists("Evaluation"):
            makedirs("Evaluation")
        chdir("Evaluation")
        self.report_file_path = f"discrepancies_{datetime.now()
            ().strftime('%d_%m_%Y-%H_%M_%S')}.txt"
        flags = O_CREAT | O_WRONLY
        mode = 0o666
        fd = open(self.report_file_path, flags, mode)

        for row in self.discrepant_values:
            write(fd, f"discrepancy revealed in database {row
                [0]} table {row[1]} column {row[2]}, expected
                value is {row[4]} while the actual value is {
                row[3]} \n".encode())
        close(fd)
        self.zip_report()
    except OSError as e:

```

```

        raise Exception(f"Error creating report: \n {(e.
            strerror if e.hasattr('strerror') else e)} \n
            error number: {e.errno}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error creating report: \n {(str(e)
            if str(e) else e)}")

```

The report creation involves the creation of the folder if it doesn't exist, file path declaration which embodies the current timestamp and even though optional declaration of flags and permissions and finally effective and expected values along with respective indexing are written. Additionally, the file is compressed with to maximum compression extent degree. This compression is implemented in a specific method, which before compressing, assess the file dimension and if it is higher than 300MB, split the report into multiple 150 MB chunks and encrypts each.

```

def zip_report(self) -> Union[str, list, None]:
    try:
        self.reports_zip_path = self.report_file_path.replace
            (".txt", ".zip")
        with ZipFile(self.reports_zip_path, "x") as zip:
            zip.write(self.report_file_path, compresslevel=9)
        remove(self.report_file_path)
        del self.report_file_path
        self.assess_dimensions()
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error zipping report: \n {str(e) if
            str(e) else e}")

def assess_dimensions(self) -> Union[List[str], None]:
    try:

        CHUNK_SIZE = 150 * 1024 * 1024
        MAX_SIZE = 300 * 1024 * 1024

        file_size = path.getsize(self.reports_zip_path)

        if file_size <= MAX_SIZE:
            self.update_report_status(self.reports_zip_path
                [-4], "REPORT ZIP CREATED")
            self.reports_zip_path = [self.reports_zip_path]

        file_parts = []
        with open(self.reports_zip_path, 'rb') as f:
            total_parts = ceil(file_size / CHUNK_SIZE)
            base_name, ext = path.splitext(self.
                reports_zip_path)

            for i in range(total_parts):

```

```

        part_file_path = f"{base_name}_part_{i + 1}{
            ext}"
        with open(part_file_path, 'wb') as chunk_file
            :

            chunk_data = f.read(CHUNK_SIZE)
            if chunk_data:
                chunk_file.write(chunk_data)
                file_parts.append(part_file_path)
            self.update_report_status(self.reports_zip_path[:-4],
                "MULTIPLE REPORT ZIP CREATED")
            self.reports_zip_path = file_parts
except OSError as e:
    raise Exception(f"error opening file, reading or
        writing in chunks: {e} \n {e.strerror if e.hasattr
            ('strerror') else e}")
except Exception as e:
    raise Exception(f"Error assessing dimensions: \n {str
        (e) if str(e) else e}")

```

Diego Gobbetti > orchestration_ransom_check > Evaluation > Cerca in Evaluation

Ordina Visualizza

Nome	Ultima modifica	Tipo	Dimensione
Evaluation	25/09/2024 11:06	Cartella di file	
discrepancies_25_09_2024-11_06_51	25/09/2024 11:06	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-11_33_18	25/09/2024 11:33	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-11_46_32	25/09/2024 11:46	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-12_07_29	25/09/2024 12:07	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-12_15_10	25/09/2024 12:15	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-12_24_28	25/09/2024 12:24	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-12_38_02	25/09/2024 12:38	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-12_59_05	25/09/2024 12:59	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-14_34_37	25/09/2024 14:34	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-14_45_25	25/09/2024 14:45	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-15_45_03	25/09/2024 15:45	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-16_00_12	25/09/2024 16:00	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-16_06_46	25/09/2024 16:06	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-16_31_56	25/09/2024 16:31	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-16_37_38	25/09/2024 16:37	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-16_41_36	25/09/2024 16:41	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-16_57_23	25/09/2024 16:57	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-17_09_38	25/09/2024 17:09	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-17_35_43	25/09/2024 17:35	Cartella compressa	1 KB
discrepancies_25_09_2024-17_41_44	25/09/2024 17:41	Cartella compressa	1 KB

Figure 2.26: reports file directory example

Next, an alert mail with attached the report file is sent to all stakeholders

```
def send_alert(self) -> None:
    try:
        with SMTP(decrypt_value(self.mail.smtpServer)) as
            mail_server:
                mail_server.starttls()
                mail_server.login(decrypt_value(self.mail.usr),
                                decrypt_value(self.mail.pwd))

                for report in self.reports_zip_path:
                    content = self.add_content(report)
                    mail_server.send_message(content,
                                             decrypt_value(self.mail.usr), self.
                                             mailReceivers)

                    if len(self.reports_zip_path) == 1:
                        self.update_report_status(report[:-4], f"
                            REPORT SENT")
                    elif len(self.reports_zip_path) > 1:
                        self.update_report_status(report[:-4], f"
                            PART {report.split('_')[2].strip()
                               [:-4]} OF REPORT SENT")

    except SMTPException as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error sending email: {(e.strerror
            if e.hasattr('strerror') else e)}")
    except MessageError or MessageDefect as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error sending email: {str(e)}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error sending email: {str(e) if str
            (e) else e}")
```

Communication to the mail server is tunnelled in a TLS channel, leveraging the SMTP module of python standard library. All mail server details are encrypted, including login credentials, with an encryption key stored in an environment variable visible only to host admins. The employed algorithm is AES in ECB mode with a 16 bytes encryption key, represented by 32 hexadecimal characters. Before the first execution the config file must be encrypted with provided utility method, `encrypt_json_file`, which creates the encryption key if not already present and encrypts all sensitive data.

```
def encrypt_keys(obj):
    if isinstance(obj, dict):
        for key, value in obj.items():
            if key in ENCRYPT_KEYS and isinstance(value, str)
                :
                    obj[key] = encrypt_value(value, key_enc)
            elif isinstance(value, (dict, list)):
```

```

        encrypt_keys(value)
elif isinstance(obj, list):
    for item in obj:
        encrypt_keys(item)
encrypt_keys(data)
with open(filepath, 'w') as file:
    json.dump(data, file, indent=4)
print(f"File '{filepath}' has been encrypted successfully
      .")

```

On the other hand, when sensitive data must be retrieved, it is decrypted with the utility method `decrypt_value()`, which retrieves the key with the environment variable name and raises an exception if it is not present

```

def decrypt_value(encrypted_value):
    try:
        try:
            encrypted_data = b64decode(encrypted_value)
        except binascii.Error or Exception as e :
            raise Exception(f"Error decoding encrypted value
                              {encrypted_value} from base64: \n {e}")
        iv = encrypted_data[:16]
        ciphertext = encrypted_data[16:]
        _key = os.environ.get(ENV_KEY_NAME)
        if _key == None:
            raise Exception(f"env variable {ENV_KEY_NAME}
                              with encryption key not found, impossible to
                              decrypt values")
        key = _key.encode()[:32]
        cipher = Cipher(algorithms.AES(bytes(key)), modes.CBC
                        (iv), backend=default_backend())
        decryptor = cipher.decryptor()
        try:
            padded_data = decryptor.update(ciphertext) +
                            decryptor.finalize()
            unpadder = padding.PKCS7(128).unpadder()
            plaintext = unpadder.update(padded_data) +
                            unpadder.finalize()
        except ValueError or TypeError as e:
            raise Exception(f"Error decrypting or unpadding
                              decrypted value. \n Error : {e}")
        return plaintext.decode()
    except InternalError as e:
        raise Exception(f"Internal Error while decrypting
                          value. \n Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e} \n
                          Error code : {e.err_code if e.hasattr('err_code')
                          else ''}")
    except InvalidTag as e:
        raise Exception(f"invalid key or authentication tag :
                          \n {e}")

```

```

except Exception as e:
    raise Exception(f"Error decrypting value. \n Error :
                    {e}")

```

All the response phases are registered in the reports table in a dedicated column, parallelly updated with the steps execution

```

def update_report_status(self, report_name: str, status: str)
-> None:
try:
    cursor = self.db_conn.cursor()

    cursor.execute('''
        SELECT name FROM sqlite_master WHERE type='table
        ';
        ''')

    cursor.execute("""
        UPDATE reports
        SET processing_status = :status
        WHERE report_name = :report_name
        """, {
            'status': status,
            'report_name': report_name
        })
    self.db_conn.commit()
    print(f"Report {report_name} status updated to {
        status}")
except sqlite_error as e:
    raise Exception(f"Error updating report status: \n {e
        }")

```

Finally, in terms of control registering, the final step is the registering of all the discrepancies along with database, table and column in a dedicated table, with a reference to the report that list them in the reports table.

```

def register_discrepancies(self):
try:
    for row in self.discrepant_values:
        self.db_conn.cursor().execute('''
            INSERT INTO discrepancies (db, "table", "column",
            value, discrepancy, report_id)
            VALUES (:db, :table, :column, :value, :
            discrepancy, :report_id)
            ''', {
                'db': row[0],
                'table': row[1],
                'column': row[2],
                'value': row[3],

```

```

        'discrepancy': f'effettivo {row[3]} != atteso
                        {row[4]}',
        'report_id': self.report_id
    })

    self.db_conn.commit()
except sqlite_error as e:
    if self.db_conn:
        self.db_conn.rollback()
    try:
        self.connect_local_db(file_name='reports.db')
        self.register_report()
    except sqlite_error as e:
        raise Exception((str(e) if str(e) else f"
                        Error registering reports: {e}"))

```

Once all stakeholders have been alerted, the snapshot revealed as infected which by fact correspond to the last, is deleted from the source engine in the source site, posting a request to a dedicated endpoint exposed by its API

```

def delete_latest_snap(self, dSource_ref):
    try:
        uri = "resources/json/delphix/snapshot/delete"
        data = {
            "dSource" : dSource_ref,
            "snapshot" : self.snaps[0]['snapshot']
        }
        self._post(uri, data)
    except RequestException as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error deleting latest snapshot with
            id {self.snaps[0]['snapshot']} in dSource {
            dSource_ref} \n Error : Response received {e.
            response}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error deleting latest snapshot with
            id {self.snaps[0]['snapshot']} in dSource {
            dSource_ref} \n Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e}"
        )

```

Eventually, the appliance execution is terminated, since the data is infected. Its execution should be resumed once the incident has been managed, all the malicious artifact have been removed and the infrastructure restored to its original state before the attack.

Otherwise if the number of discrepancies detected is lower than the threshold, the recovery virtual database in the source site is refreshed with the latest clean snapshot, which have just been checked. This step is implemented in a specific method, which essentially execute a post request to the relative endpoint exposed by the engine API

```

def refresh_recovery_db(self, vdb_ref):
    uri_refresh = rf"resources/json/delphix/database/{vdb_ref}
        }/refresh"
    try:
        data = {
            "type": "OracleRefreshParameters",
            "timeflowPointParameters": {
                "type": "TimeflowPointSnapshot",
                "snapshot": self.snaps[0]['snapshot']
            }
        }
        job_id = (self._post(uri_refresh, data)).json()['job'
            ]
        uri_jobId = rf"resources/json/delphix/job/{job_id}"
        with IncrementalBar(message=rf"Waiting for refresh of
            {vdb_ref} to finish", suffix='%(index)d/%(max)d
            [%d / %d / %d] (%d)' % (elapsed, eta, eta_td, iter_value),
            color='blue', max=100) as bar:
            while self._get(uri_jobId, key="result")['
                jobState'] != "COMPLETED":
                bar.next(1)
    except RequestException as e:
        raise Exception(f"error executing vdb refreshng
            job, Bad request likely. Response received {e.
            response}")
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"error executing vdb refreshng
            job \n Error : {str(e) if str(e) else e}")

```

The last step in the not-infected execution scenario is to update expected values for the next control cycle with the current data evaluated as clean. The first micro phase of this last step is retrieval of columns in the control scope, as meanwhile new columns could have been added or removed. This involves querying first the result table, then the general database view and finally subsequently target column, where data is grouped by values and the length of the group is extracted along with the value itself. The resulting data structure is a list of tuples

```

def update_expected_values(self):
    procedure_data = [(row[0], row_values[0], row_values[1])
        for row in self.retrieve_target_columns()
        for row_values in self.retrieve_values(row)
    ]
    types = [{"value" : "CheckBaseTableType", "collection":
        True, "type" : {"value" : "CheckBaseRecType", "
            collection" : False} }]
    with self.vdb_target.tech(**self.vdb_target) as db_conn:
        db_conn.execute_procedure(self.expected_proc, [
            procedure_data], types=types)

```

```

def retrieve_target_columns(self, results_table: str = "
CHECK_2"):
    try:
        with self.vdb_target.tech(**self.vdb_target) as
            db_conn:
                return db_conn.execute_query(f"SELECT ID,
                    DATABASE_ID, TABLE_ID, COLUMN_ID FROM C##
                    control_user.{results_table}", all=True)
    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error retrieving target columns
            from results table \n Error : {e} ")

def retrieve_values(self, row):
    try:
        with self.vdb_target.tech(**self.vdb_target) as
            db_conn:
                cv2_rs = db_conn.execute_query("SELECT
                    TABLE_SCHEMA, TABLE_NAME, COLUMN_NAME FROM :
                    schema.CHECK_VIEW_2 WHERE DB_ID = ':
                    database_id' AND TABLE_ID = ':table_id' AND
                    COLUMN_ID = ':column_id'", True, None, "C##
                    control_user", row[1], row[2], row[3])
                return db_conn.execute_query("SELECT :column_name
                    AS VALUE, COUNT(*) AS COUNT, FROM :
                    table_schema.:table_name GROUP BY :column_name
                    ", True, None, cv2_rs[2], cv2_rs[0], cv2_rs
                    [1], cv2_rs[2])

    except Exception as e:
        raise Exception(f"Error retrieving values from
            database \n Error : {e} ")

```

The procedure and related data types to update expected values, as covered formerly, includes specifically crafted types to handle a collection of elements composed of three sub elements, respectively values, occurrences and relative results table id. Hence, the database connector class method that implements the procedure call, before calling the 'callproc' method of the underlying database API module, checks for potential input data, if it must be modelled in a custom type and if the type includes a collection.

```

def execute_procedure(self, proc_name, input_args: Optional[
    Union[list, tuple]] = None, **kwargs) -> object:
    try:
        if input_args:
            if 'types' in kwargs:
                _input = []
                for i in range(0, len(kwargs['types'])):
                    _type = self.connection.gettype(kwargs['types

```

```

        '][i]['value'])
    if kwargs['types'][i]['collection']:
        rec_type = self.connection.gettype(kwargs
            ['types'][i]['type']['value'])
        rec_collection = _type([rec_type(row) for
            row in input_args[i]])
        _input.append(rec_collection)
    else:
        record = _type(input_args[i])
        _input.append(record)
        self.cursor.callproc(proc_name, [_input +
            input_args[len(kwargs['types']):]])
    else:
        self.cursor.callproc(proc_name, input_args)
    else:
        self.cursor.callproc(proc_name)
except Exception as e:
    logging.error(e, exc_info=True)
finally:
    self.cursor.close()

```

The whole codebase, along with testing, can be consulted at the following public GitHub repository : [14]

Conclusion

The primary objective of this project was to develop a data integrity control and anomaly response solution for mission-critical databases in the client system, which are exposed to testing environments in less protected perimeter segments. The main threat targeted by this solution was ransomware, with a focus on ensuring a robust data recovery strategy that minimizes both data loss and downtime. This translates into the reduction of both Recovery Point Objective (RPO) and Recovery Time Objective (RTO) to acceptable levels.

Given these requirements and the client infrastructure, the solution has been modeled as a Ransomware Managed Detection and Response system, significantly leveraging Delphix engines as logical Programmable Data Infrastructure. The final solution successfully satisfies the outlined requirements. Tests were performed with a User Acceptance Testing (UAT) environment storing an 800 GB dataset in a multi-instance Oracle database, connected to the control site over a network with up to 10 Gbps bandwidth, replicating production environment settings. A total of 100 columns were targeted for control in the control results table. As shown by test results, once the incremental approach is employed, after the first control cycle, the full control workflow—from replication to the control site to the backup of the discrepancies report—takes between 4 and 15 minutes, depending on the size of data updates and network traffic.

Hence, RPO and RTO vary depending on when the production data is maliciously encrypted relative to the control execution, the number of columns controlled, and the time taken by stakeholders to trigger the provisioning of a backup copy to the source site. Assuming that the latter is negligible, in the worst-case scenario given a replication execution at time t , if data is encrypted maliciously just before the next replication cycle at $t+15$, the latest clean data snapshot will be roughly 15 minutes old. Conversely, if encryption occurs just after replication, the next control cycle will detect it, and the latest snapshot saved by the current control cycle could be identical to the status of the data before encryption. Therefore, the guaranteed

RPO is 0÷15 minutes, with a seamless restoring mechanism by provisioning data from the recovery database. Whereas, the time required to fully recover the system's original operational functionality depends on multiple factors, including potential infection of additional environments, overhead from additional restoration operations, and status validation processes. Assuming these factors are negligible, in the worst-case scenario where data is encrypted immediately after a replication execution at time t , the ransomware attack will be detected at $t+(4\div 15)+(4\div 13)$, where the second and third parameters represent the time taken for a full control cycle and for sending an alert in the next control cycle, respectively. The alert time is capped at 13 minutes since further steps, such as registering discrepancies, will be executed following the alert. In the best-case scenario, the attack will be detected 4÷15 minutes after its occurrence, but given the expected high rate of data updates, it should generally fall within the range of 10÷15 minutes. Consequently, the RTO ranges from 10 to 30 minutes, considering all the aforementioned assumptions.

Another requirement that has been successfully met is control robustness. This was originally addressed at the design level of the solution. The comparison mechanism, which operates at cell granularity, ensures that each individual cell value is validated. This approach prevents control evasion and obfuscation attempts by attackers, such as replicating file system signatures or masking malicious processes as legitimate ones.

Throughout the development process, several design and implementation challenges were encountered. Beyond fulfilling the core requirements, the solution needed to guarantee scalability, reliability, security, and observability. The client's infrastructure was already heavily reliant on Delphix, with a Delphix data engine replicating masked data to testing environments in another perimeter segment. As a result, designing a solution based on the Delphix platform was a natural choice. This decision led to the development of a Programmable Data Infrastructure at the logical level, abstracting data management complexities.

To ensure high efficiency in data analysis, the process was engineered into two macro steps. The first step extends the Delphix engine's native masking algorithm capabilities. Splitting the analysis into two steps allowed for the implementation of response mechanisms while providing greater visibility for stakeholders through reports and discrepancies logging. Given that Delphix engines are provided in a SaaS model—where arbitrary socket connections cannot be opened or accepted, and modifications to the underlying file system are denied—this two-step approach was a key design choice.

One of the major challenges faced was the creation of a reliable values oracle that required minimal time and computational resources to maintain.

Given the nature of the data, the final design involved the periodic update of a values oracle table containing data from the results table columns. This table is updated at the end of each cycle and serves as the reference oracle for the next cycle. The table, like the results table, is built using database metadata catalogs and stored as physical tables based on system catalog views. This design choice enables further views to be created on top of these catalogs, which would not be possible with non-materialized system catalog views. The decision to update these tables cyclically using stored database procedures was made to offload computational tasks to the database system, aligning with the general approach of the solution.

One of the highest-priority updates is replacing the configuration file with a lightweight local database that mirrors its properties. This change will be crucial once the service is offered in self-service mode, as it will allow seamless management of controls and each control's details. By leveraging a structured database instead of a static configuration file, the system will gain better scalability, easier maintainability, and enhanced flexibility for managing multiple configurations simultaneously.

Additionally, the analysis process could be slightly overhauled to offload more work to the database itself. By modifying the final query executed by the plugin, it could directly compare calculated values with expected ones. Instead of storing intermediary results, the values written in the results table would contain a 0/1 flag, which the evaluation component of the orchestration appliance could parse more efficiently. This enhancement would simplify data processing, reduce overhead, and improve the system's responsiveness in handling large datasets.

The solution has been highly appreciated by the client and has been recognized as an outstanding relational data integrity control service. As a testament to its value, the organization has decided to develop a web interface to offer the solution to clients in self-service mode. This new interface will provide full configurability and observability of the control process, enabling clients to manage their own data integrity controls with greater ease and flexibility.

The success of this project underscores the importance of integrating advanced security, automation, and data governance measures into modern enterprise infrastructures. By leveraging Delphix engines and a well-architected orchestration framework, this solution demonstrates how an intelligent, scalable, and programmable approach can effectively mitigate ransomware threats while ensuring data integrity and regulatory compliance. With continuous improvements and a broader scope of applicability, this framework has the potential to evolve into a more comprehensive and technology-agnostic data control solution, capable of extending beyond relational databases to support

other modern storage paradigms.

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